

Simultaneous Representations of Selfie Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci and Triangular Numbers¹

Inder J. Taneja²

Abstract

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as *selfie numbers*. There are many ways of representing *selfie numbers*. It can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. In this work, we have written *selfie numbers* in such a way that these are simultaneously equal by use of **Fibonacci sequence** as well as **Triangular numbers**. This is done by use of **basic operations** along with **factorial** and/or **square-root**.

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¹It is revised and combine version author's works <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a55.pdf> [17] done in 2017.

²Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978). **E-mail:** ijjtaneja@gmail.com; **Web-site:** <https://inderjtaneja.com>; **Twitter:** @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

1 Selfie Numbers

Recently, author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Subsections below give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers** and **centered polygonal numbers**.

1.1 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 13825 &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 14641 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 &= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 \\
 15552 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 16377 &:= (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \\
 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8 - 2)^{3+3} / 2 \\
 116565 &:= (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) &= 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 131072 &:= (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

1.2 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\
 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 145 := 1! + 4! + 5! & 363239 := 36 + 323 + 9! \\
 733 := 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363269 := 363 + 26 + 9! \\
 5177 := 5! + 17 + 7! & 403199 := 40319 + 9!
 \end{array}$$

1.3 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 936 := (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! & = 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 := \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} & = 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\
 2896 := 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) & = (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\
 331779 := 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} & = \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\
 342995 := (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 & = -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\
 759375 := (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 & = (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7} \\
 759381 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 & = -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.
 \end{array}$$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15].

1.4 Fibonacci Sequence

The examples given in subsections, 1.2 and 1.3 are with **factorial** and **square-root**. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Fibonacci sequence** values. See below:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 235 := 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) & 63 := 3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 256 := 2^5 \times F(6) & 882 := 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\
 4427 := (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) & 1631 := F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\
 46493 := F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 & 54128 := 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))
 \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [25].

1.5 Triangle Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics [5]. These are given by

$$1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, \dots$$

The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The letter "C" represents as "binomial coefficient". The examples given in above subsections are with factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using Triangular numbers. See below:

$1069 := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$	$874 := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$
$1081 := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$	$0105 := 50 + T(10)$
$2887 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$	$1155 := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$
$4965 := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$	$1224 := T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1$
$4999 := 49 + T(99)$	$2418 := T(81) - T(42)$
$99545 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$	$99632 := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$
$99546 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6$	$99633 := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's work [23].

1.6 Binomial Coefficients

The examples given in subsection 1.4 and 1.5 are with **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular numbers** respectively. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **Binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways, digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$6435 := C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6)$	
$15504 := C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1)$	
$42504 := C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24)$	
$54264 := C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4 + 5})!)$	
$74613 := C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!)$	
$12650 := C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!)$	$28 := C(8, 2)$
$12870 := C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!)$	$792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7)$
$14950 := C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!)$	$924 := C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!)$
$18564 := C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!)$	$2024 := C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!)$
$19448 := C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8)$	$4845 := C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4)$
$26334 := C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4})$	$00378 := C(C(8, \sqrt{7 - 3}), 0! + 0!)$
$43758 := C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8)$	$00792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!)$
$53130 := C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!)$	$00924 := C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!))$

The symbol C used for binomial coefficients is given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m - r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

Above numbers are in **digit's order, reverse order of digits** and in **both ways**. For more details refer [24].

1.7 S-gonal numbers

The examples given in subsection 1.6 are with **binomial coefficients**. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **s-gonal numbers**. See below some examples in **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 4992 &:= P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & 8967 &:= 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\
 7744 &:= (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & 9504 &:= 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\
 7896 &:= 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & 9744 &:= 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\
 65485 &:= -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & 49281 &:= 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \\
 65943 &:= P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & 49548 &:= -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4 \\
 67977 &:= (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & 50424 &:= 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!}) \\
 72495 &:= -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 & 52895 &:= (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5 \\
 83544 &:= \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} & 53995 &:= (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5
 \end{aligned}$$

The symbol P used for **s-gonal numbers** and is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

For more details refer author's work [16].

1.8 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The examples given in subsection 1.6 and 1.7 are with **binomial coefficients** and **s-gonal numbers** respectively. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **centered polygonal numbers**. See below some examples in **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 2883 &:= K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3 & 00938 &:= K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!) \\
 2888 &:= K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8 & 01051 &:= K(15, 010) \\
 3640 &:= K(3!, 6) \times 40 & 01199 &:= K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10) \\
 14939 &:= -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9 & 59938 &:= K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5 \\
 14959 &:= (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9 & 62424 &:= 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6) \\
 15144 &:= K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4! & 63384 &:= 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6! \\
 15347 &:= (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7) & 63744 &:= 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!) \\
 15399 &:= K(1 \times 5!/3!, 9) \times 9 & 63973 &:= K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6)
 \end{aligned}$$

The symbol K used for **centered polygonal numbers** and is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{tn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

For summary of author's work on numbers refer [18, 19, 20]. For study on **s-gonal numbers** and **centered polygonal numbers** refer to [1, 3, 6, 7]. Also refer [2, 4] for historical books on numbers.

1.9 Binomial Coefficients, S-gonal, and Centered Polygonal Numbers

There are very few selfie numbers connecting three formulas: **binomial coefficients**, **s-gonal** and **centered polygonal numbers**. In some cases the ordered in not same, it is either in digit's order or reverse.

$$\begin{aligned}
 13448 &:= 8 + (4 + 4)! / C(3, 1) &= (8! + 4!) / \sqrt{P(4, 3) - 1} &= K(-1 + 3!, 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8 \\
 39435 &:= C(5 + 3!, \sqrt{4}) \times (-\sqrt{9} + 3!!) &= (3!! - \sqrt{9}) \times (4 + P(3!, 5)) &= (K(5, 3) + 4!) \times (-\sqrt{9} + 3!!) \\
 39648 &:= 8! - (\sqrt{4} + 6) \times C(9, 3) &= -P(3 + 9, 6 \times \sqrt{4}) + 8! &= K(3!, \sqrt{9}) - 6! + \sqrt{4} + 8! \\
 98464 &:= C(9 + 8, \sqrt{4}) \times (6! + 4) &= (4 + 6!) \times P(4! - 8, \sqrt{9}) &= (4 + 6!) \times K(\sqrt{4} + 8, \sqrt{9})
 \end{aligned}$$

From above, we observe that there is not a even a single numbers that connects above three formulas in digit's order or in reverse. Two by two there are many numbers given in [16].

The aim of this paper is to bring **selfie numbers** those can be written together with **Fibonacci sequence** as well as **triangular Numbers** at the same time.

2 Fibonacci Sequence and Triangular Numbers

This section deals with **selfie numbers** written simultaneously in terms of **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular numbers**. The work is done in two ways: one in digit's order and second in reverse order of digits. We have divided the work following four subsections:

- (i) Basic operations: addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation;
- (ii) Basic operations with factorial;
- (iii) Basic operations with square-root;
- (iv) Basic operations with factorial and square-root together.

2.1 Basic Operations

In this subsection, we shall bring **selfie numbers written in terms of Fibonacci sequence and Triangular numbers** at the same time. The numbers are just with used of **basic operations**, such as, **addition, subtraction, multiplication, division and potentiation**. Again, the work is divided in two subsections, one in digit's order and another in reverse order of digits.

2.1.1 Digit's Order

$$\begin{aligned}
 34 &:= F(3 \times F(4)) & 168 &:= 1 \times F(6) \times F(8) \\
 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(4)) & &:= 1 \times T(6) \times 8 \\
 55 &:= F(5 + 5) & 233 &:= F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3)) \\
 &:= T(5 + 5) & &:= 2 + T(T(3 + 3)) \\
 63 &:= F(F(6)) \times 3 & 234 &:= F(2) + F(F(3 + 4)) \\
 &:= T(6) \times 3 & &
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(2) \times T(3 \times 4) \\
 \mathbf{237} & := F(2) + 3 + F(F(7)) \\
 & := T(T(2)) + T(3 \times 7) \\
 \mathbf{245} & := 2 + F(4)^5 \\
 & := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{256} & := 2^5 \times F(6) \\
 & := 25 + T(T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{466} & := F(F(4)) \times F(-F(6) + F(F(6))) \\
 & := 4 + T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{630} & := F(F(6)) \times 30 \\
 & := T(6) \times 30 \\
 \mathbf{693} & := F(F(6)) \times (F(9) - F(F(3))) \\
 & := (T(T(6)) \times (9/3)) \\
 \mathbf{784} & := (7 + F(8))^{F(F(4))} \\
 & := T(7)^{8/4} \\
 \mathbf{882} & := F(8) \times F(8) \times 2 \\
 & := T(T(8)) + T(8) \times T(T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{1165} & := F(F(1 \times 1 + 6)) \times 5 \\
 & := (1 + 1 + T(T(6))) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{1364} & := -F(13) + F(F(F(6))) - 4 \\
 & := T(T(T(1 + 3))) - T(T(6)) + T(T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{1365} & := 13 \times F(F(6)) \times 5 \\
 & := 13 \times T(6) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{1368} & := (1 - 3 + F(F(F(6))))/8 \\
 & := T(1 \times 3 \times 6) \times 8 \\
 \mathbf{1429} & := 1 + 42 \times F(9) \\
 & := -1 - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2))) \times 9 \\
 \mathbf{1487} & := -F(14) + 8 \times F(F(7)) \\
 & := T(T(1 \times 4) + T(8)) + T(T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{1525} & := F(15)/2 \times 5 \\
 & := -15 + T(T(2 \times 5)) \\
 \mathbf{1575} & := F(F(1 + 5)) \times 75 \\
 & := T(1 + 5) \times 75 \\
 \mathbf{1576} & := F(-1 + 5 + F(7)) - F(F(6)) \\
 & := 1 + T(5) \times T(-7 + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{1593} & := 1 - 5 + F(F(9)/F(3)) \\
 & := T(1 + T(T(-5 + 9))) - 3 \\
 \mathbf{1594} & := (1 + 5) \times 9 + T(T(T(4))) \\
 & := F(F(1 + 5) + 9) - F(4) \\
 \mathbf{1596} & := -1^5 + F(9 + F(6)) \\
 & := T(1 \times 5 + T(9)) + 6 \\
 \mathbf{1617} & := -1 + F(F(6)) + F(17) \\
 & := 1 \times T(T(6)) \times 1 \times 7 \\
 \mathbf{1618} & := F(16 + 1) + F(8) \\
 & := 1 + T(T(6)) \times (-1 + 8) \\
 \mathbf{1645} & := F(16)/F(4) \times 5 \\
 & := (-1 + 6 \times T(T(4))) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{1680} & := 1 \times F(F(6)) \times 80 \\
 & := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 0 \\
 \mathbf{1684} & := -1 + F(F(F(6))) - F(8)^{F(4)} \\
 & := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 4 \\
 \mathbf{1687} & := (F(F(1 + 6)) + 8) \times 7 \\
 & := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1763 &:= -1 + (7 \times 6)^{F(3)} & &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5) + T(7) + T(7)) \\
 &:= -1 + T(7) \times 63 \\
 1764 &:= 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{F(F(4))} & &:= 2 \times (-5 + T(8)^2) \\
 &:= T(-1 + 7) \times T(6) \times 4 \\
 1778 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (F(F(7)) + F(8)) & &:= -F(2) + F(-5 + F(8) + F(3)) \\
 &:= T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 8 & &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)/T(3)) \\
 1785 &:= F(1 + 7) \times 85 & &:= 2584 := F(2 \times (5 + 8 - 4)) \\
 &:= (-1 + T(7 + 8)) \times T(5) & &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5 \times (-T(8) + T(T(4))) \\
 1824 &:= (-1 + F(F(8))/2)/F(4) & &:= 2585 := F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) \\
 &:= T(18) + T(2 + T(T(4))) & &:= T(25) \times 8 - T(5) \\
 1847 &:= -1 - 8 \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) & &:= 2586 := 2 + F((-5 + 8) \times 6) \\
 &:= -1 + 8 \times T(T(T(-4 + 7))) & &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + T(86) \\
 1848 &:= (1 + F(8)) \times 4 \times F(8) & &:= 2597 := F(F(-2 + 5) \times 9) + F(7) \\
 &:= T(T(T(1 + 8/4))) \times 8 & &:= T(2 + T(T(5)) - T(9)) - T(T(7)) \\
 1864 &:= (1 + T(T(8) - 6)) \times 4 & &:= 2646 := 2 \times F(F(6)) \times F(4) \times F(F(6)) \\
 &:= F(F(-1 + 8)) \times (6 + F(F(4))) & &:= T(T(2) + T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(6)) \\
 1925 &:= (1 + F(9)) \times F(2 \times 5) & &:= 2648 := 2^6 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \\
 &:= -T(T(1 + 9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(5) & &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(6) + 4)) \times 8 \\
 1995 &:= F(-1 + 9) \times 95 & &:= 2688 := 2 \times F(6) \times F(8) \times 8 \\
 &:= 19 \times T(9 + 5) & &:= 2 \times T(6) \times 8 \times 8 \\
 2079 &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9 & &:= 2736 := (2 \times 7)^3 - F(6) \\
 &:= T(T(2) \times 07) \times 9 & &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)) + T(3 + T(6)) \\
 2529 &:= -F(2 \times 5) + F(2 \times 9) & &:= 2742 := (2 \times 7)^{F(4)} - 2 \\
 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 9 & &:= 2 \times (-7 + T(T(T(4)) - T(2))) \\
 2563 &:= F(F(2 + 5)) \times (F(6) + 3) & &:= 2744 := (-2 + F(7) + F(4))^{F(4)} \\
 &:= -2 + T(5) \times T(6 \times 3) & &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(74) - T(4) \\
 2577 &:= F(25 - 7) - 7 & &:= 2754 := -2^{F(7)} + F(F(5 + F(4))) \\
 & & &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7 + 5) - 4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2772 &:= (-2 + F(F(7))) \times (F(7) - F(2)) \\
 &:= -T(2) + T(77 - T(2)) \\
 2784 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times (8 + 4) \\
 &:= (2 + T(7)) + T(T(8)) \times 4 \\
 2794 &:= -2 + F(F(7)) \times (9 + F(4)) \\
 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(7) \times (T(9) + T(T(4))) \\
 2796 &:= F(2) \times F(F(7)) \times (-9 + F(F(6))) \\
 &:= T(2 \times (T(7) + 9)) + T(6) \\
 2937 &:= (-F(2) + F(9)) \times F(-F(3) + F(7)) \\
 &:= T(2) \times T(T(9)) - T(3) \times T(7) \\
 3382 &:= (-F(F(3)) + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)))/2 \\
 &:= -T(3 + 3) + T(82) \\
 3384 &:= (3 + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8)))/F(F(4)) \\
 &:= 3 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(8) - T(4) \\
 3495 &:= 3 \times F(4 + 9) \times 5 \\
 &:= T(3 \times 4) \times T(9) - T(5) \\
 3528 &:= F(3 + 5)^2 \times 8 \\
 &:= (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 8 \\
 3575 &:= F(F(3) \times 5) \times F(7) \times 5 \\
 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 5 \\
 3584 &:= (F(3) + 5) \times 8^{F(4)} \\
 &:= -T(T(3)) + 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(4))) \\
 3645 &:= (3 + 6)^{F(4)} \times 5 \\
 &:= -3^6 \times (T(4) - T(5)) \\
 3648 &:= (-F(3) + F(F(F(6))))/F(-4 + 8) \\
 &:= T(3) \times (T(6) + T(T(4))) \times 8 \\
 3649 &:= (3 \times F(F(F(6))) + F(4))/9 \\
 &:= -T(3) + T(-6 + T(4 + 9)) \\
 3738 &:= F(3) \times F(F(7) - F(3)) \times F(8) \\
 &:= T(3 \times T(7)) + T(T(3)) \times 8 \\
 3773 &:= (-F(3) + F(7)) \times 7^3 \\
 &:= T(T(T(3))) - T(7) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\
 3784 &:= 3^7 + F(F(8) - 4) \\
 &:= T(37) + T(T(8 + 4)) \\
 3786 &:= (F(F(3) + F(7)) + F(8)) \times 6 \\
 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 6 \\
 3948 &:= F(3) \times 94 \times F(8) \\
 &:= T(3) \times (T(9 \times 4) - 8) \\
 3966 &:= -3 + 9 \times F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)) \\
 &:= -3 + 9 \times T(6) \times T(6) \\
 3968 &:= (-F(F(3)) + 9 \times F(F(6))) \times F(8) \\
 &:= T((T(T(T(3))) - T(9))/6) \times 8 \\
 3969 &:= F(F(-3 + 9)) \times F(F(6)) \times 9 \\
 &:= T(-3 + 9) \times T(6) \times 9 \\
 4176 &:= -4 - 1 + F(F(7) + 6) \\
 &:= -T(4) + T(T(-1 - 7 + T(6))) \\
 4182 &:= F(F(4 - 1)) + F(F(8) - 2) \\
 &:= -4 + T(T(-1 + 8 + T(T(2)))) \\
 4183 &:= F(F(4)) + 1 \times F(F(8) - F(3)) \\
 &:= T(T(4 + 1 + 8)) - 3 \\
 4277 &:= (F(F(F(4))) + F(2 + F(7))) \times 7 \\
 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 7 \\
 4386 &:= F(F(F(4))) - 3^8 + F(F(F(6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-T(4) + T(38)) \times 6 \\
 \mathbf{4388} & := F(4) - 3^8 + F(F(8)) \\
 & := -T(T(T(4))) + T(38) \times 8 \\
 \mathbf{4427} & := (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) \\
 & := (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4))) \times T(2) - T(7) \\
 \mathbf{4455} & := F(4)^4 \times 55 \\
 & := T(T(4)) \times (T(-4 + T(5)) + T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{4536} & := (F(F(F(4))) + 5)^3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 & := (T(4 \times 5) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{4624} & := (4 + F(6)^2)^{F(F(4))} \\
 & := T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 4 \\
 \mathbf{4632} & := (F(4) + F(F(6))^3)/2 \\
 & := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(3)) \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{4746} & := (-4 + F(F(7)) - F(4)) \times F(F(6)) \\
 & := (T(T(4)) + T(T(7) - T(4))) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{4788} & := (F(4) + F(F(7)) - 8) \times F(8) \\
 & := (T(T(4)) + 78) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{4847} & := -4 - F(8) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(7))) \\
 & := -4 + T(T(8) + T(T(4)) + 7) \\
 \mathbf{4871} & := -F(F(F(4))) + F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - 1) \\
 & := (4 + 8) \times T(T(7)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{4872} & := F(F(F(4))) \times F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2)) \\
 & := T(T(T(4)) + T(8) + 7) + T(T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{4889} & := -4 + F(8) \times F(-F(8) + F(9)) \\
 & := T(T(T(4)) + T(8)) + T(-8 + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{4892} & := -F(F(F(4))) + F(8) \times F(F(9 - 2)) \\
 & := T(T(4)) \times 89 - T(2) \\
 \mathbf{4935} & := F(4 + 9 + 3) \times 5 \\
 & := -T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \\
 \mathbf{5497} & := F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 7 \\
 & := -T(5) + 4 \times T(T(9) + 7) \\
 \mathbf{6300} & := F(F(6)) \times 300 \\
 & := T(6) \times 300 \\
 \mathbf{6615} & := F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)) \times 15 \\
 & := T(6) \times T(6) \times 15 \\
 \mathbf{6744} & := -F(F(6)) + F(F(7) + F(4) + 4) \\
 & := 6 \times (-T(T(7)) - T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 \mathbf{6762} & := -F(F(6))/7 + F(F(F(6)) - F(2)) \\
 & := (T(T(6)) + T(7 + 6)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{6933} & := 6 \times F(9)^{F(3)} - 3 \\
 & := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 3 \\
 \mathbf{6934} & := 6 \times F(9)^{F(3)} - F(F(4)) \\
 & := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 4 \\
 \mathbf{6936} & := 6 \times F(9) \times F(3 + 6) \\
 & := T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 6 \\
 \mathbf{6954} & := 6 \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(5)) + 4) \\
 & := F(F(6)) \times 9 + F(5 \times 4) \\
 \mathbf{6993} & := F(F(6)) \times 9 \times (F(9) + 3) \\
 & := T(6) \times (-T(9) + T(9 \times 3)) \\
 \mathbf{7392} & := (F(F(7)) - F(3)) \times (F(9) - 2) \\
 & := T(7) \times (T(3) \times T(9)) - T(T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{7883} & := -F(7) + 8 \times F(8 \times F(3)) \\
 & := (T(7 \times 8) + T(T(9))) \times 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7924 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 4 \\ &:= 7 \times (T(T(9) + 2) + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8464 &:= (84 + F(6))^{F(F(4))} \\ &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8294 &:= (F(F(8) - 2) - F(9)) \times F(F(4)) \\ &:= 8 \times (T(2) + T(T(9))) - T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9248 &:= F(9)^{-2+4} \times 8 \\ &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8352 &:= (F(F(8) - F(3)) - 5) \times 2 \\ &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(5 + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9586 &:= -F(9) \times 5 \times 8 + F(F(F(6))) \\ &:= T(9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(-8 + T(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8364 &:= F(F(8)) + F(3) - F(6 \times F(4)) \\ &:= -T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)) + T(6)) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9837 &:= 98^{F(3)} + F(F(7)) \\ &:= 9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) \end{aligned}$$

2.1.2 Reverse Order of Digits

$$\begin{aligned} 34 &:= F(F(4))^{F(3)} \\ &:= T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(7 \times 3) + T(T(2))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36 &:= 6^{F(3)} \\ &:= 6 \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 243 &:= 3^{F(4)+2} \\ &:= 3^4 \times T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55 &:= F(5 + 5) \\ &:= T(5 + 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 256 &:= (F(F(6)) - 5)^2 \\ &:= (T(6) - 5)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63 &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) \\ &:= 3 \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 466 &:= F(-F(6) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(4)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 168 &:= F(8) \times F(6) \times 1 \\ &:= 8 \times T(6 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 693 &:= (-F(F(3)) + F(9)) \times F(F(6)) \\ &:= (-T(3) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 231 &:= F(13) - 2 \\ &:= T(T(1 \times 3 \times 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 882 &:= 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\ &:= T(T(2)) \times T(8) + T(T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 233 &:= F(F(3 \times 3 - 2)) \\ &:= T(T(3 + 3)) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0105 &:= 50 + F(10) \\ &:= 50 + T(10) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 234 &:= F(F(4 + 3)) + F(2) \\ &:= T(4 \times 3) \times T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0127 &:= 72 + F(10) \\ &:= 72 + T(10) \end{aligned}$$

$$237 := F(F(7)) + F(3) + 2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0136 &:= -F(6) + F(F(3)) + 10 \\ &:= T(6) \times T(3) + 10 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 0137 &:= -7 + F(F(3) + 10) \\
 &:= -T(7) + 3 \times T(10) \\
 0138 &:= 83 + F(10) \\
 &:= 83 + T(10) \\
 0143 &:= F(3 \times 4) - 1 + 0 \\
 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 4) - 10 \\
 0149 &:= 94 + F(10) \\
 &:= 94 + T(10) \\
 0165 &:= (-5 + F(6)) \times F(10) \\
 &:= T(5) \times (T(6) - 10) \\
 0168 &:= F(8) \times F(6 \times 1 + 0) \\
 &:= -8 + T(T(6)) - T(10) \\
 0186 &:= 6 \times (F(8) + 10) \\
 &:= T(T(6)) - T(8 + 1 + 0) \\
 0231 &:= T(1^3 + 20) \\
 &:= F(13) - 2 + 0 \\
 0253 &:= F(F(F(3) + 5)) + 20 \\
 &:= T(-3 + 5 + 20) \\
 0256 &:= (F(F(6)) - 5)^{2+0} \\
 &:= T(T(6)) + 5 + 20 \\
 0376 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 7) - F(F(3 + 0)) \\
 &:= T(T(6) + 7) - 30 \\
 0378 &:= F(F(8) - 7) + F(F(3 + 0)) \\
 &:= -87 + T(30) \\
 0417 &:= F(F(7) + 1) + 40 \\
 &:= T(T(7)) - 9 + 3 \times 0 \\
 0568 &:= 8 \times (F(F(6)) + 50) \\
 &:= 8 \times (T(6) + 50) \\
 1165 &:= 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1)) \\
 &:= 5 \times (T(T(6)) + 1 + 1) \\
 1536 &:= F(6)^3 \times F(5 - 1) \\
 &:= T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) + T(51) \\
 1546 &:= F(F(F(6)) - 4) - 51 \\
 &:= 6 + T(4 + 51) \\
 1576 &:= F(F(6)) \times 75 + 1 \\
 &:= T(6) \times 75 + 1 \\
 1594 &:= -F(4) + F(9 + F(5 + 1)) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) + 9 \times (5 + 1) \\
 1596 &:= 6 \times T(9) + T(51) \\
 &:= F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1))) \\
 1618 &:= F(8) + F(16 + 1) \\
 &:= (8 - 1) \times T(T(6)) + 1 \\
 1684 &:= F(F(4)) \times F(F(8)) / F(6 + 1) \\
 &:= 4 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1) \\
 1687 &:= (F(F(7)) + 8) \times (6 + 1) \\
 &:= 7 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1) \\
 1764 &:= 4 \times F(F(6)) \times F(7 + 1) \\
 &:= 4 \times T(6) \times T(7 - 1) \\
 1778 &:= (F(8) + F(F(7))) \times 7 \times 1 \\
 &:= 8 + T(T(T(7)) / 7 + 1) \\
 1847 &:= (F(F(7)) - F(F(4))) \times 8 - 1 \\
 &:= T(T(T(7 - 4))) \times 8 - 1 \\
 1848 &:= 84 \times (F(8) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 8 \times T(T(T(-4 + 8 - 1)))$$

$$\mathbf{1864} := (F(F(4)) + 6) \times F(F(8 - 1))$$

$$:= 4 \times (T(-6 + T(8)) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1925} := F(5 \times 2) \times (F(9) + 1)$$

$$:= T(5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9 + 1))$$

$$\mathbf{2079} := 9 \times (F(F(7)) - 02)$$

$$:= 9 \times T(7 \times T(02))$$

$$\mathbf{2478} := -8 + T(T(7)) + T(4^{T(2)})$$

$$:= F(8) \times (F(F(7)) + F(4))/2$$

$$\mathbf{2529} := 9 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2))$$

$$:= F(9 \times 2) - F(5 \times 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2563} := (3 + F(6)) \times F(F(5 + 2))$$

$$:= T(3 \times 6) \times T(5) - 2$$

$$\mathbf{2577} := -7 + F(-7 + 5^2)$$

$$:= T(-7 + T(7 + 5)) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2583} := F(-3 + F(8)) - F(F(5 - 2))$$

$$:= 3 \times T(T(8) + T(5)/T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2584} := F((-4 + 8) \times 5 - 2)$$

$$:= 4 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(5))/T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2585} := F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2)$$

$$:= -T(5) + 8 \times T(5^2)$$

$$\mathbf{2586} := F(6 \times (8 - 5)) + 2$$

$$:= T(68) + T(T(5)) \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{2592} := F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2))$$

$$:= T(T(2))^{9-5} \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{2597} := F(7) + F(9 \times F(5 - 2))$$

$$:= -T(T(7)) + T(-T(9) + T(T(5)) + 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2646} := F(6 \times F(4)) + 62$$

$$:= T(T(6 - 4)) \times T(6)^2$$

$$\mathbf{2648} := F(F(8) - F(4)) + F(6)^2$$

$$:= (T(T(8)) - 4) \times (6 - 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2667} := (F(F(7)) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(6))/2$$

$$:= 7 \times (T(T(6) + 6) + T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2688} := 8 \times F(8) \times F(6) \times 2$$

$$:= 8 \times 8 \times T(6) \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{2736} := (F(F(6)) - F(3)) \times F(F(7) - F(2))$$

$$:= (T(T(6) + 3) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2772} := (-2 + F(F(7))) \times (F(7) - F(2))$$

$$:= -T(2) + T(77 - T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2784} := (4 + 8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$$

$$:= 4 \times T(T(8)) + T(T(7 - 2))$$

$$\mathbf{2794} := (F(4) + 9) \times F(F(7)) - 2$$

$$:= (T(T(4)) + T(9)) \times T(7) - T(T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2796} := (F(F(6)) - 9) \times F(F(7) \times F(2))$$

$$:= T(6) + T((9 + T(7)) \times 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2937} := (F(F(7) - F(3))) \times (F(9) - F(2))$$

$$:= -T(7) \times T(3) + T(T(9)) \times T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{3087} := 7 \times F(8)^{F(03)}$$

$$:= T(78) + T(03)$$

$$\mathbf{3136} := (F(F(6) + F(3)) + 1)^{F(3)}$$

$$:= T(T(6 + T(3))) + T(T(1 + 3))$$

$$\mathbf{3249} := (F(9 + F(F(F(4)))) + 2)^{F(3)}$$

$$:= 9 + T(T(4) \times 2^3)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3372 &:= (2 + F(7))^3 - 3 & &:= T(T(6 + 3)) + T(73) \\
 &:= T(-2 + 7)^3 - 3 \\
 3384 &:= (F(4) + F(F(8) - F(F(3))))/F(3) & &:= 8 \times T(T(3)) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4)) - 8) \times (-3 + T(3)) & &:= F(8) \times F(3) \times F(F(7) - F(3)) \\
 3385 &:= (5 + F(F(8) - F(F(3))))/F(3) & &:= 3773 := (-F(3) + F(7)) \times 7^3 \\
 &:= 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3))) & &:= T(T(T(3))) - T(7) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\
 3495 &:= 5 \times F(9 + 4) \times 3 & &:= 3786 := 6 \times (F(8) + F(F(7) + F(3))) \\
 &:= -T(5) + T(9) \times T(4 \times 3) & &:= 6 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \\
 3528 &:= F(8)^2 \times (5 + 3) & &:= 3789 := 9 \times F(F(8))/(F(7) \times F(3)) \\
 &:= T(82) + 5^3 & &:= 9 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \\
 3575 &:= 5 \times F(7) \times F(5 \times F(3)) & &:= 3864 := -4 \times (F(F(6)) - F(8 \times F(3))) \\
 &:= 5 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) & &:= -(T(T(4)) - T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) \\
 3628 &:= -F(8) + (F(2) + F(F(F(6))))/3 & &:= 3927 := (F(F(7)) - 2) \times F(9)/F(3) \\
 &:= T(82) + T(T(6)) - T(3) & &:= 7 \times T((2 + 9) \times 3) \\
 3645 &:= 5 \times (F(4) + 6)^3 & &:= 3948 := F(F(8) - F(F(4))) - F(F(9 - F(3))) \\
 &:= 5 \times T(-4 + 6)^{T(3)} & &:= T(84) + T(9 \times 3) \\
 3647 &:= (-7 + F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6))))/3 & &:= 3966 := F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)) \times 9 - 3 \\
 &:= -T(7) + T(T(T(4)) - 6) \times 3 & &:= T(6) \times T(6) \times 9 - 3 \\
 3648 &:= (F(F(8)) - F(F(4)))/(6 - 3) & &:= 3968 := F(8) \times F(F(6)) \times 9 - F(F(3)) \\
 &:= T(84) + T(6 + T(3)) & &:= 8 \times T((T(T(6)) - T(9))/T(3)) \\
 3649 &:= (F(F(9/F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))/3 & &:= 3969 := (9 \times 6 + 9)^{F(3)} \\
 &:= T(T(9 + 4) - 6) - T(3) & &:= 9 \times T(6) \times T(9 - 3) \\
 3652 &:= (2 \times 5 + F(F(F(6))))/3 & &:= 4147 := (7 + 4) \times F(14) \\
 &:= T(T(-2 + T(5)) - 6) - 3 & &:= 7 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \\
 3728 &:= 8 \times F(F(2) \times F(7)) \times F(3) & &:= 4176 := F(6 + F(7)) - 1 - 4 \\
 &:= T(82) + T(T(7) - 3) & &:= T(T(6 + 7)) - T(1 \times 4) \\
 3736 &:= F(6) \times (F(3) \times F(F(7)) + F(F(3))) & &:= 4182 := F(2) + F(F(8) + 1 - F(4)) \\
 & & &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 8 - 1)) - 4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4183 &:= F(3) + F(F(8) + 1 - F(4)) \\ &:= -3 + T(T(8 + 1 + 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4889 &:= F(F(9) - F(8)) \times F(8) - 4 \\ &:= T(T(9) - 8) + T(T(8) + T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4277 &:= 7 \times (F(F(7) + 2) + F(F(F(4)))) \\ &:= 7 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4892 &:= F(F(-2 + 9)) \times F(8) - F(F(F(4))) \\ &:= (-T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9))) \times 8 - T(T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4356 &:= (65 + F(F(3)))^{F(F(4))} \\ &:= T(6 + 5)^{T(3)-4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4896 &:= 6 \times F(9) \times 8 \times F(4) \\ &:= T(6 + T(9)) + T(84) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4378 &:= (-8 + F(7)^3) \times F(F(4)) \\ &:= (-8 + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(3)) - T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4935 &:= 5 \times F(3 + 9 + 4) \\ &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times (T(9) - T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4427 &:= F(F(7)) \times (-2 + F(4 + 4)) \\ &:= -T(7) + T(2)^4 \times T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4956 &:= F(F(6)) \times 59 \times 4 \\ &:= 6 + T(5 + 94) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4455 &:= 55 \times F(4)^4 \\ &:= (T(5)/5)^4 \times T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4987 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(8) + 94 \\ &:= 7 \times (T(T(8)) + T(9)) + T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4536 &:= 6^3 \times F(5 + F(4)) \\ &:= T(6) \times (T(3) + T(5 \times 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5376 &:= F(F(6)) \times (F(7) + 3^5) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + 7^3 \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4624 &:= (4 + 2^6)^{F(F(4))} \\ &:= 4 + T(2) \times T(T(6 + 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5497 &:= 7 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) \\ &:= T(7 + T(9)) \times 4 - T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4746 &:= F(F(6)) \times (-F(4) + F(F(7)) - 4) \\ &:= T(6) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(7) - T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6327 &:= -F(F(7)) - F(2) + 3^{F(6)} \\ &:= 7 \times T(2 \times T(T(3))) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4788 &:= F(8) \times (-8 + F(F(7)) + F(4)) \\ &:= (-8 + T(8)) \times T(T(7) - T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6456 &:= -F(F(6)) \times 5 + F(4)^{F(6)} \\ &:= 6 \times (-5 + T(46)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4847 &:= (F(F(7)) - F(F(4))) \times F(8) - 4 \\ &:= T(7 + T(T(4)) + T(8)) - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6472 &:= -F(-2 + F(7)) + F(4)^{F(6)} \\ &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7) + T(4) - 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4871 &:= (-1 + F(F(7))) \times F(8) - F(F(F(4))) \\ &:= -1 + T(T(7)) \times (8 + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6489 &:= -9 \times 8 + F(4)^{F(6)} \\ &:= 9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(4 + 6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4872 &:= (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times F(8) \times F(F(F(4))) \\ &:= T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (8 - 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6744 &:= F(F(4)^{F(4)} - 7) - F(F(6)) \\ &:= (-4 + T(47)) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(-6 + T(9) + 8) \times 7$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6936 &:= 6 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ &:= F(6 + 3) \times F(9) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7924 &:= (4 + T(2 + T(9))) \times 7 \\ &:= F(F(4)) + F(2) \times F(9) \times F(F(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6954 &:= F(4 \times 5) + 9 \times F(F(6)) \\ &:= (4 + T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8294 &:= F(F(4)) \times (-F(9) + F(-2 + F(8))) \\ &:= -T(4) + (T(T(9)) + T(2)) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6993 &:= (3 + F(9)) \times 9 \times F(F(6)) \\ &:= (T(3 \times 9) - T(9)) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8352 &:= 2 \times (-5 + F(-F(3) + F(8))) \\ &:= (T(T(2)) - 5 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7223 &:= (32 - F(2)) \times F(F(7)) \\ &:= (T(T(T(3))) + 2) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8364 &:= F(F(4)) - F(6 \times 3) + F(F(8)) \\ &:= T(4) \times T(T(6) + T(T(3))) - T(T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7392 &:= (-2 + F(9)) \times (-F(3) + F(F(7))) \\ &:= (T(T(2)) \times T(9) - T(3)) \times T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9248 &:= F(8)^{F(4)} - F(-2 + 9) \\ &:= 8 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7776 &:= 6^{F(7) - F(-7 + F(7))} \\ &:= 6^{(T(7) + 7) / 7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9586 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 8 \times 5 \times F(9) \\ &:= T(T(T(6) - 8)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$7896 := F(6) \times 987$$

2.2 With Factorial

In this subsection, we shall bring **selfie numbers written in terms of Fibonacci sequence and Triangular numbers** at the same time. The numbers are with used of basic operations and factorial. Again, the work is divided in two subsections, one in digit's order and another in reverse order of digits.

2.2.1 Digit's Order

- Symmetric

$$5760 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 0 = (T(5) - 7) \times 6! + 0$$

$$5761 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 1 = (T(5) - 7) \times 6! + 1$$

$$5762 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 2 = (T(5) - 7) \times 6! + 2$$

$$5763 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 3 = (T(5) - 7) \times 6! + 3$$

$$5764 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 4 = (T(5) - 7) \times 6! + 4$$

$$5765 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 5 = (T(5) - 7) \times 6! + 5$$

$$5766 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 6 = (T(5) - 7) \times 6! + 6$$

$$5767 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 7 = (T(5) - 7) \times 6! + 7$$

$$5768 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 8 = (T(5) - 7) \times 6! + 8$$

$$5769 := (-5 + F(7)) \times 6! + 9 = (T(5) - 7) \times 6! + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}6480 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 0 = 6!/4 \times T(8) + 0 \\6481 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 1 = 6!/4 \times T(8) + 1 \\6482 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 2 = 6!/4 \times T(8) + 2 \\6483 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 3 = 6!/4 \times T(8) + 3 \\6484 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 4 = 6!/4 \times T(8) + 4 \\6485 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 5 = 6!/4 \times T(8) + 5 \\6486 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 6 = 6!/4 \times T(8) + 6 \\6487 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 7 = 6!/4 \times T(8) + 7 \\6488 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 8 = 6!/4 \times T(8) + 8 \\6489 &:= 6! + F(4)!! \times 8 + 9 = 6!/4 \times T(8) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6720 &:= (F(6))!/(7 - F(2)) + 0 = 6! \times T(7)/T(2) + 0 \\6721 &:= (F(6))!/(7 - F(2)) + 1 = 6! \times T(7)/T(2) + 1 \\6722 &:= (F(6))!/(7 - F(2)) + 2 = 6! \times T(7)/T(2) + 2 \\6723 &:= (F(6))!/(7 - F(2)) + 3 = 6! \times T(7)/T(2) + 3 \\6724 &:= (F(6))!/(7 - F(2)) + 4 = 6! \times T(7)/T(2) + 4 \\6725 &:= (F(6))!/(7 - F(2)) + 5 = 6! \times T(7)/T(2) + 5 \\6726 &:= (F(6))!/(7 - F(2)) + 6 = 6! \times T(7)/T(2) + 6 \\6727 &:= (F(6))!/(7 - F(2)) + 7 = 6! \times T(7)/T(2) + 7 \\6728 &:= (F(6))!/(7 - F(2)) + 8 = 6! \times T(7)/T(2) + 8 \\6729 &:= (F(6))!/(7 - F(2)) + 9 = 6! \times T(7)/T(2) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6840 &:= (6! + 8!)/F(4)! + 0 = (6! - T(8)) \times T(4) + 0 \\6841 &:= (6! + 8!)/F(4)! + 1 = (6! - T(8)) \times T(4) + 1 \\6842 &:= (6! + 8!)/F(4)! + 2 = (6! - T(8)) \times T(4) + 2 \\6843 &:= (6! + 8!)/F(4)! + 3 = (6! - T(8)) \times T(4) + 3 \\6844 &:= (6! + 8!)/F(4)! + 4 = (6! - T(8)) \times T(4) + 4 \\6845 &:= (6! + 8!)/F(4)! + 5 = (6! - T(8)) \times T(4) + 5 \\6846 &:= (6! + 8!)/F(4)! + 6 = (6! - T(8)) \times T(4) + 6 \\6847 &:= (6! + 8!)/F(4)! + 7 = (6! - T(8)) \times T(4) + 7 \\6848 &:= (6! + 8!)/F(4)! + 8 = (6! - T(8)) \times T(4) + 8 \\6849 &:= (6! + 8!)/F(4)! + 9 = (6! - T(8)) \times T(4) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7560 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 0 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 0 \\7561 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 1 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 1 \\7562 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 2 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 2 \\7563 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 3 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 3 \\7564 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 4 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 4 \\7565 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 5 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 5 \\7566 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 6 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 6 \\7567 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 7 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 7\end{aligned}$$

$$7568 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 8 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 8$$

$$7569 := 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 9 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 9$$

• Nonsymmetric

$$21 := F(F((2+1)!))$$

$$:= T(T(2+1))$$

$$23 := 2 + F(F(3!))$$

$$:= 2 + T(T(3))$$

$$123 := F(12) - F(F(3!))$$

$$:= (-1 + T(T(2)))! + 3$$

$$126 := (1+2)! \times F(F(6))$$

$$:= T(1+2) \times T(6)$$

$$143 := -1 + F(4 \times 3)$$

$$:= -1 + 4! \times T(3)$$

$$147 := 1 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 7$$

$$:= T(T(-1+4)) \times 7$$

$$227 := -F(2+2)! + F(F(7))$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2) - 7$$

$$231 := -2 + F(F(3! + 1))$$

$$:= T(T(2 \times 3 \times 1))$$

$$232 := -F(2) + F(F(3! + F(2)))$$

$$:= T(2) + T(T(T(3))) - 2$$

$$235 := 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5))$$

$$:= T(T(2))! / 3 - 5$$

$$248 := 2^{F(F(4)!)} - 8$$

$$:= (T(T(T(2)))) + T(4) \times 8$$

$$254 := F(F(2+5)) + F(F(F(4)!))$$

$$:= -T(T(T(2))) + 5 \times T(T(4))$$

$$264 := 2^{F(6)} + F(F(4)!)$$

$$:= -T(2+6) + T(4!)$$

$$273 := F(2) \times F(7) \times F(F(3!))$$

$$:= T(2) \times T(7+T(3))$$

$$274 := F(2) + F(7) \times F(F(F(4)!))$$

$$:= 2 - T(7) + T(4!)$$

$$315 := F(F(3!)) \times 15$$

$$:= 3 \times T(-1+T(5))$$

$$336 := F(3) \times F(3!) \times F(F(6))$$

$$:= T(3 \times T(T(3))) / 6$$

$$354 := (-F(3) + 5!) \times F(4)$$

$$:= -T(3) + T(5) \times 4!$$

$$384 := F(3) \times 8 \times 4!$$

$$:= T(3)! - T(8) - T(4!)$$

$$420 := F(F(F(4)!)) \times 20$$

$$:= T(4!) + (T(T(2)) - 0!)!$$

$$432 := F(4) \times F(3! \times 2)$$

$$:= 4! \times T(3) \times T(2)$$

$$433 := -F(F(4)!) + F(F(3!))^{F(3)}$$

$$:= T(T(4)) + T(3^3)$$

$$445 := F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \times 5$$

$$:= T(4) + T(4! + 5)$$

$$462 := F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(2))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := 4 \times T(T(6))/2 \\
 \mathbf{472} & := (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 2 \\
 & := -4! + T(T(7) + T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{504} & := F(F(5 + 0!)) \times 4! \\
 & := T(5 + 0!) \times 4! \\
 \mathbf{546} & := (5 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times F(F(6)) \\
 & := T(5) + T(4!) + T(T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{564} & := (5! + F(F(6))) \times 4 \\
 & := (5! + T(6)) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{724} & := (7 - F(2))! + 4 \\
 & := T(7) + T(T(2))! - 4! \\
 \mathbf{727} & := (7 - F(2))! + 7 \\
 & := 7 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7! \\
 \mathbf{733} & := 7 + T(3) + T(3)! \\
 & := F(7) + (3 + 3)! \\
 \mathbf{735} & := 7 \times F(F(3!)) \times 5 \\
 & := (T(7) + T(T(3))) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{748} & := 7 + F(4)!! + F(8) \\
 & := T(7) + T(4!/8)! \\
 \mathbf{842} & := F(F(8))/F(F(4)! + F(2)) \\
 & := T(T(8)) - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{1024} & := (1 + 0!)^{2+F(F(4)!)} \\
 & := (1 \times 02)^{T(4)} \\
 \mathbf{1035} & := F(10) \times F(F((3)!)) - 5! \\
 & := T(10 + 35) \\
 \mathbf{1042} & := F(10) + F(4^2) \\
 & := (1 + T(T(-0! + T(4)))) + T(T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{1045} & := F(10) \times (4! - 5) \\
 & := 10 + T(45) \\
 \mathbf{1175} & := (1 + 1 + F(F(7))) \times 5 \\
 & := -1 + T((-1 + 7)!/T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{1260} & := F(F((1 + 2)!)) \times 60 \\
 & := T(1 + 2) \times T(T(6) - 0!) \\
 \mathbf{1296} & := (1 + T(2))! \times 9 \times 6 \\
 & := F(12) \times 9!/(F(6))! \\
 \mathbf{1323} & := (-1 + F(3!)^2) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 & := T(T(1 \times 3)) \times T(2) \times T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{1324} & := 1 + F(F(3!))^2 \times F(4) \\
 & := T((1 + 3)!) + 2^{T(4)} \\
 \mathbf{1343} & := -1 + F(3)!/(4! + 3!) \\
 & := -1 + T(T(3)) \times 4^3 \\
 \mathbf{1344} & := (1 + F(3! + 4)) \times 4! \\
 & := T(1 + T(3)) \times (4! + 4!) \\
 \mathbf{1345} & := 1 + F(3)!/(F(4)! \times 5) \\
 & := T(-1 \times T(3) + T(T(4))) + 5! \\
 \mathbf{1374} & := (-1 - 3 + F(F(7))) \times F(4)! \\
 & := -1 - 3 + T(T(7) + 4!) \\
 \mathbf{1378} & := 1 + 3! \times F(F(7)) - F(8) \\
 & := T(-1 - 3 + 7 \times 8) \\
 \mathbf{1404} & := (1 + F(F(F(4)! + 0!))) \times F(4)! \\
 & := T(1 + 4! + 0!) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{1427} & := 1 \times F(4)!! \times 2 - F(7) \\
 & := 1 + T(4!) + T(T(2))! + T(T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1434 &:= (1 - 4 + 3!) \times F(F(4)) & &:= T(T(-1 + 4)) \times 70 \\
 &:= (-1 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(3)) + T(4!) \\
 1435 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times 3! - 5 & &1483 := 1 + F(F(4)) \times (F(8) + 3!) \\
 &:= T(-1 + 4)! + T(3)! - 5 & &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - 8!/T(3)! \\
 1436 &:= (1 - F(4)) \times (F(3) - 6!) & &1484 := (1 + F(4)!! + F(8)) \times F(F(4)) \\
 &:= -1 \times 4 + T(3)! + 6! & &:= -1 + T(T(4 + 8) - 4!) \\
 1440 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4 + 0))!! & &1493 := (-1 + (F(F(4)!))!/9)/3 \\
 &:= T(-1 + 4)! + T(4 - 0)! & &:= 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9) - 3 \\
 1444 &:= (14 + 4!)^{F(F(4))} & &1536 := (1 + 5) \times F(3)^{F(6)} \\
 &:= T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - 4! \times 4 & &:= T(1 + T(5)) \times T(3) + 6! \\
 1445 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times F(4)!! + 5 & &1560 := 1 \times 5! \times F(F(6) - 0!) \\
 &:= (-1 + T(4!) - T(4)) \times 5 & &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(6) - 0! \\
 1446 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4) + 6!) & &1572 := (1 + 5!) \times F(7) - F(2) \\
 &:= (1 + 4! \times T(4)) \times 6 & &:= -(-1 + 5)! + T(T(7) \times 2) \\
 1448 &:= -1 + F(4!)/(4 \times 8) & &1637 := -1 + F(F(6)) \times 3! \times F(7) \\
 &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - T(8) & &:= -1 + (T(T(6)) + 3) \times 7 \\
 1456 &:= F(1 + F(4)!) \times (5! - F(6)) & &1664 := -16 + (F(6))!/4! \\
 &:= (1 + T(T(4))) \times (5 + T(6)) & &:= -T(16) + 6 \times T(4!) \\
 1457 &:= 1 + (-F(F(4)!) + 5!) \times F(7) & &1686 := F(16) - F(8) + 6! \\
 &:= T(-T(1 + T(4)) + 5!) - T(7) & &:= (T(-1 + T(6))) \times 8 + 6 \\
 1462 &:= 1 + F(F(F(4)!)) + 6! \times 2 & &1734 := 17^{F(3)} \times F(4)! \\
 &:= (1 + T(4) + 6!) \times 2 & &:= -1 + 7!/3 + T(T(4)) \\
 1463 &:= -1 + 4! + 6! \times F(3) & &1745 := 1 + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) - 5! \\
 &:= -1 + 4! + 6! + T(3)! & &:= T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 5 \\
 1464 &:= (-1 + F(4)) \times 6! + 4! & &1823 := -1 + (F(F(8)) - 2)/3! \\
 &:= (1 + T(4) \times 6) \times 4! & &:= -1 + 8 \times (-T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \\
 1470 &:= 1 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 70 & &1920 := (-1 + 9)!/F(F((2 + 0)!)) \\
 & & &:= (-1 + 9)!/T(T(T(2 + 0)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2016 &:= F((2+0!)!)/(-1+F(F(6))) \\
 &:= T(T(2) \times T(0 \times 1 + 6)) \\
 2048 &:= 2^{F(04)+8} \\
 &:= (T(2) + 0!)^4 \times 8 \\
 2097 &:= (2 \times 0 + 9) \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= T(T(2))! - 0! + T(T(9) + 7) \\
 2136 &:= (2 + 1) \times (3!! - F(6)) \\
 &:= T(2) \times (-1 + T(3)!) - T(6) \\
 2145 &:= (2 + 1) \times (F(4)!! - 5) \\
 &:= T((T(2) + T(1 \times 4)) \times 5) \\
 2147 &:= (2 + 1)!! \times F(4) - F(7) \\
 &:= 2 + T(-1 + T(4 + 7)) \\
 2154 &:= (-2 + (1 + 5)!) \times F(4) \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times (-1 + T(5) \times 4!) \\
 2184 &:= ((2 + 1)!! + 8) \times F(4) \\
 &:= T(21 - 8) \times 4! \\
 2208 &:= F((2 + 2)!)/F(08) \\
 &:= T(T(2) + 20) \times 8 \\
 2214 &:= (F(22) + 1)/F(F(4)!) \\
 &:= T(2) + T(T(2 - 1 + T(4))) \\
 2274 &:= (2 + F(2 \times 7)) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times (-T(2) + T(T(7)) - 4!) \\
 2310 &:= 2 \times F(F(3!)) \times F(10) \\
 &:= 2 \times T(T(3)) \times T(10) \\
 2312 &:= 2 \times F(F(3!) + 1)^2 \\
 &:= 2 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(1 + T(2)) \\
 2317 &:= (2 \times 3)! + F(17) \\
 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 7 \\
 2330 &:= (2 + F(3!)) \times F(F(3! + 0!)) \\
 &:= (2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(3 + 0!) \\
 2373 &:= ((2 + 3)! - 7) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 &:= ((2 + 3)! - 7) \times T(T(3)) \\
 2375 &:= 2 + F(F(3!)) \times (-7 + 5!) \\
 &:= 2 - T(T(3)) \times (7 - 5!) \\
 2376 &:= (2^3! + F(F(7))) \times F(6) \\
 &:= (-T(-2 + T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times 6 \\
 2439 &:= -F(2) + 4 \times F(3! + 9) \\
 &:= T(T(2) \times 4!) - T(T(3)) \times 9 \\
 2444 &:= (F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - F(4)!)) \times 4 \\
 &:= (T(T(2 \times 4)) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \\
 2448 &:= F(2 \times F(4)!) \times (-4 + F(8)) \\
 &:= (T(2) \times 4! - 4) \times T(8) \\
 2449 &:= F(2) + 4! \times F(4) \times F(9) \\
 &:= -2 - 4! + T(T(4)) \times T(9) \\
 2464 &:= -(F(2) + 4)! + F(-6 + 4!) \\
 &:= T(-2 + 4!) + T(T(T(6) - T(4))) \\
 2465 &:= F(2) + F(4! - 6) - 5! \\
 &:= (-T(2) + T(T(4) + T(6))) \times 5 \\
 2474 &:= 2 \times F(4! - 7) - F(4)!! \\
 &:= T(T(2))! \times 4 - T(7 \times 4) \\
 2519 &:= -F(2) + 5! \times F(-1 + 9) \\
 &:= T(T(2))! \times 5 - T(1 + T(9)) \\
 2540 &:= (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(5) - 4) - 0!$$

$$\mathbf{2541} := (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F((4 - 1)!))$$

$$:= T(T(T(2))) \times (5 \times 4! + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{2542} := (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + F(2)$$

$$:= T(T(T(2))) \times 5! + 4! - 2$$

$$\mathbf{2544} := (2 + 5)! / F(F(4)) + 4!$$

$$:= (T(T(2 + 5)) - T(4!)) \times 4!$$

$$\mathbf{2545} := 25 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times 5!$$

$$:= 2 \times T(5 \times T(4)) - 5$$

$$\mathbf{2561} := (2 + 5!) \times F(F(6)) - 1$$

$$:= (2 + 5!) \times T(6) - 1$$

$$\mathbf{2562} := (2 + 5!) \times F(6 + 2)$$

$$:= (2 + 5!) \times T(T(6/2))$$

$$\mathbf{2583} := -F(2) + F((-5 + 8) \times 3!)$$

$$:= (T(2) + 5!) \times T(T(8)/T(3))$$

$$\mathbf{2634} := 2 \times (F(F(6)) + 3!^4)$$

$$:= 2 \times (T(6) + T(3)^4)$$

$$\mathbf{2638} := -2 + 6! + F(3!)! / F(8)$$

$$:= T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(T(3)) - 8$$

$$\mathbf{2640} := (F(2) + F(F(6))) \times (4 + 0)!)$$

$$:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(T(4) + 0!))$$

$$\mathbf{2644} := -2 + F(F(6))^{F(F(4))} \times F(4)!$$

$$:= T(T(2)) + T(6! / T(4)) + T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{2735} := -F(2) - 7! + 3!^5$$

$$:= T(T(2))! + (T(T(7)) - 3) \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{2747} := -2^{F(7)} + F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 7$$

$$:= T(T(2)) \times T(7) - T(4) - T(7)$$

$$\mathbf{2748} := -2^{F(7)} - F(4)! + F(F(8))$$

$$:= 2 \times T(T(7) + 4!) - 8$$

$$\mathbf{2753} := F(F(2) \times F(7)) + 5! \times F(F(3!))$$

$$:= T(2) + T(T(7)) \times 5 + T(3)!$$

$$\mathbf{2795} := (-F(2) + 7! / 9) \times 5$$

$$:= T(T(2))! + (T(T(7)) + 9) \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{2844} := (-F(2) - 8 + F(4)!) \times 4$$

$$:= T(T(2))! + T(8) \times (4 + T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{2846} := -F(F(2) + 8) + 4 \times 6!$$

$$:= 2 - T(8) + 4 \times 6!$$

$$\mathbf{2856} := (2^8 - 5!) \times F(F(6))$$

$$:= (2^8 - 5!) \times T(6)$$

$$\mathbf{2878} := -2 + 8! / (-7 + F(8))$$

$$:= T(28) \times 7 + T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{2946} := (2^9 - F(F(F(4)!))) \times 6$$

$$:= T(2 + 9) + 4 \times 6!$$

$$\mathbf{2964} := (F(-F(2) + 9) + 6!) \times 4$$

$$:= T(T(2)) \times (9! / 6! - T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{3024} := F(F(3!)) \times F((0! + 2) \times 4)$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(02)) \times 4!$$

$$\mathbf{3045} := F(F(3!)) \times (0! + 4! + 5!)$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times (0! + 4! + 5!)$$

$$\mathbf{3150} := F(F(3!)) \times 150$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times 150$$

$$\mathbf{3159} := (3! - 1)^5 + F(9)$$

$$:= T(31 - 5) \times 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3165 &:= (-T(T(3)) + 1 + T(T(6))) \times T(5) &:= T(3)!/T(3) \times T(6 + 0!) \\
 &:= F(F(F(3!)) - 1) - 6! \times 5 \\
 3240 &:= 3!!/2 \times (F(F(4)!) + 0!) &3374 &:= -F(F(3)) + (F(3) + F(7))^{F(4)} \\
 &:= T(T(3)/T(2) \times 40) &&:= 3 \times (T(3)! + T(T(7))) - 4 \\
 3249 &:= (3!! + 2)/F(F(4)) \times 9 &3375 &:= 3 \times (-F(3!) + F(F(7))) \times 5 \\
 &:= 3 \times (T(2) + 4! \times T(9)) &&:= T(3 \times 3) \times 75 \\
 3264 &:= (F(3! \times 2) - F(6)) \times 4! &3376 &:= F(3!)^{-3+7} - 6! \\
 &:= (T(3) - 2)! \times T(6 + T(4)) &&:= -T(3)! + (-3 + 7)^6 \\
 3276 &:= 3! \times 2 \times F(7) \times F(F(6)) &3384 &:= F(3!) - 3!! + 8^4 \\
 &:= T(3)^2 \times T(7 + 6) &&:= (T(T(3)) + (-3 + 8)!) \times 4! \\
 3303 &:= F(3 \times 3!) - 0! + 3!! &3396 &:= 3! \times (3!! - F(9)) - 6! \\
 &:= T(T(T(T(3))))/3 + T((0! + 3)!) &&:= T(3^3) \times 9 - 6 \\
 3304 &:= 3!! + F(3! \times F(04)) &3429 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(4)!!/2) \times 9 \\
 &:= T(T(T(T(3))))/3 + 0! + T(4!) &&:= (3 + T(4! + T(2))) \times 9 \\
 3312 &:= (F(3) + F(F(3!))) \times F(12) &3435 &:= -F(F(3!)) + 4! \times 3!!/5 \\
 &:= T(T(3 + 3)) + T(T(12)) &&:= T(3^4) - T(3) + 5! \\
 3325 &:= (3!! - F(F(3!) + 2)) \times 5 &3437 &:= -3!! - 4! + F(3! + F(7)) \\
 &:= (T(3)! - T(T(T(3) - 2))) \times 5 &&:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 3 - T(7) \\
 3333 &:= 3! \times 3!! - F(F(3) \times F(3!)) &3448 &:= F(3 \times 4) \times 4! - 8 \\
 &:= T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(3))) + T(T(T(3) + T(3))) &&:= T(3) \times 4! \times 4! - 8 \\
 3339 &:= (-3! + F(3! + F(3!))) \times 9 &3451 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(F(4)!)) \times (5! - 1) \\
 &:= 3^{T(3)} \times T(3) - T(T(9)) &&:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - 5! + 1 \\
 3344 &:= F(3) \times (F(3)!/4! - F(F(4)!)) &3452 &:= -F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(4)) + 5!^2 \\
 &:= T(3)! + T(3 \times 4!) - 4 &&:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - 5! + 2 \\
 3357 &:= (3!! - F(3)) \times 5 - F(F(7)) &3454 &:= -F(3) + (4! + 5!) \times 4! \\
 &:= -3 + T(3 \times 5) \times T(7) &&:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - 5! + 4 \\
 3360 &:= (F(3!))!/(F(3) \times 6) + 0 &3456 &:= 3 \times (4! + 5!) \times F(6) \\
 &&&:= T(3) \times (-4! + 5!) \times 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3457 &:= F(F(3)) + 4! \times F(5 + 7) \\
 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - 5! + 7 \\
 3463 &:= -3!! + F(F(4)) + F(F(F(6))) - F(3) \\
 &:= T(T(3 + T(4))) - 6! - 3 \\
 3464 &:= F(3!) + 4! \times 6 \times 4! \\
 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times 4! - T(64) \\
 3466 &:= F(3) + 4 \times F(F(F(6))) - F(6)! \\
 &:= T(T(3 + 4 + 6)) - 6! \\
 3474 &:= -3!! + F(4) \times F(F(7)) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(3^4) + T(-7 + 4!) \\
 3483 &:= 3 \times (F(4)!! + F(8)^{F(3)}) \\
 &:= T(T(3)) - 4! + T(83) \\
 3486 &:= F(3!)^4 - F(F(8)) - 6 \\
 &:= T(3^4 + 8 - 6) \\
 3487 &:= -F(3!) - (F(4)! - F(8)) \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= T(-3 \times (T(4) - T(8))) + T(T(7)) \\
 3492 &:= 3 \times (F(F(4)!) + F(9)^2) \\
 &:= T(3^4) + T(9 \times 2) \\
 3497 &:= F(3) + (4! - 9) \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= -3 - T(T(4) + T(9)) + 7! \\
 3498 &:= F(F(F(3!))) \times 4 + F(9) - 8! \\
 &:= T(T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times (T(9) + 8) \\
 3525 &:= (F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 25 \\
 &:= (T(T(3)) + 5!) \times 25 \\
 3534 &:= (F(3 \times 5) - F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= (-T(3) + 5!) \times (T(T(3)) + T(4)) \\
 3544 &:= F(3!) \times 5! + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \\
 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(5) + T(T(4)) + 4! \\
 3545 &:= (3!! - 5 - F(4)!) \times 5 \\
 &:= (T(3)! - T(5) + 4) \times 5 \\
 3549 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (5! + 49) \\
 &:= T(T(3)) \times (5! + 49) \\
 3567 &:= F(3) + 5 \times (6! - 7) \\
 &:= -3 + T(56 + T(7)) \\
 3568 &:= F(3!) + 5 \times (6! - 8) \\
 &:= (T(T(3)) - 5) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \\
 3573 &:= 3 + T(T(5 + 7) + T(3)) \\
 &:= F(3!) + 5 \times (-7 + 3!!) \\
 3594 &:= -3! + 5! \times (F(9) - 4) \\
 &:= T(T(3) \times (5 + 9)) + 4! \\
 3597 &:= 3!! \times 5 - F(-9 + F(7)) \\
 &:= T(3)! \times 5 - T(9 - 7) \\
 3602 &:= F(3) + 60^2 \\
 &:= T(3)! \times (6 - 0!) + 2 \\
 3603 &:= 3 + 60^{F(3)} \\
 &:= 3 - 6! \times (0! - T(3)) \\
 3605 &:= (F(3) + 6! - 0!) \times 5 \\
 &:= (T(3)! + (6 \times 0!)) \times 5 \\
 3624 &:= 3!! \times (6 - F(2)) + 4! \\
 &:= (3 + T(T(6) \times 2)) \times 4 \\
 3627 &:= (3!! - (F(F(6))))^2 \times F(7) \\
 &:= T(3)! + 6! + T(2)^7 \\
 3635 &:= (3^6 - F(3)) \times 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (T(3)! + T(6)/3) \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{3643} := (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/F(4) - 3$$

$$:= -3 + 6! + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(3))$$

$$\mathbf{3646} := (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6))))/(4!/F(6))$$

$$:= T(3)! + T(T(6) + T(4 + 6))$$

$$\mathbf{3647} := 3! \times F(F(F(6))) - F(4!) - F(7)$$

$$:= 3 \times T(-6 + T(T(4))) - T(7)$$

$$\mathbf{3648} := (-F(3) + F(F(6))) \times 4! \times 8$$

$$:= (-3 + T(T(6))) \times (4! - 8)$$

$$\mathbf{3658} := -F(3) + 6 \times F(5!/8)$$

$$:= 3 + T(-6 + T(5 + 8))$$

$$\mathbf{3672} := 3! \times (F(F(6) + 7)) + 2$$

$$:= 3 \times T(T(6) + T(7)) - T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{3675} := (F(3) + 6! + F(7)) \times 5$$

$$:= 3 \times T(6 + T(7) + T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{3705} := (3!! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 5$$

$$:= T(37 + 0!) \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{3720} := F(3!) \times (F(F(7)) \times 2 - 0!)$$

$$:= (3 + T(7)) \times (T(T(2)) - 0!)!$$

$$\mathbf{3732} := (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \times 2$$

$$:= T(3) \times (T(T(7)) + T(3)^{T(2)})$$

$$\mathbf{3734} := (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + 3) \times F(F(4))$$

$$:= T(T(T(3))) + 7! + 3 - T(T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{3744} := 3 \times F(7) \times 4 \times 4!$$

$$:= 3 \times (T(7) + 4!) \times 4!$$

$$\mathbf{3746} := 3!! \times (-7 - F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$:= T(3 \times T(7)) - T(T(4)) + T(T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{3835} := F(3)!/F(8) \times F(3) - 5$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(3)) - 8)) - T(T(T(3))) + 5$$

$$\mathbf{3842} := (F(3)!)/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 2$$

$$:= T(T(3)!/8) - T(4! - 2)$$

$$\mathbf{3844} := F(3)!/F(8) \times F(F(4)) + 4$$

$$:= T(3)! - T(8) + T(T(T(4))) + 4!$$

$$\mathbf{3856} := F(3)^8 + 5 \times 6!$$

$$:= -T(T(T(3))) - 8 + T(T(5) \times 6)$$

$$\mathbf{3882} := (F(F(3!)) + 8!/F(8)) \times 2$$

$$:= 3 \times (T(8) \times T(8) - 2)$$

$$\mathbf{3927} := (F(3!) + 9) \times (-2 + F(F(7)))$$

$$:= T(3 \times (9 + 2)) \times 7$$

$$\mathbf{3945} := F(F(3)) + F(9) \times (-4 + 5!)$$

$$:= (T(3)! + T(9) + 4!) \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{3954} := 3! \times (F(9) + 5^4)$$

$$:= -T(3) + (T(9) + 5!) \times 4!$$

$$\mathbf{3960} := -(F(F(3)) - F(9)) \times (6 - 0!)$$

$$:= ((T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 60)$$

$$\mathbf{3961} := (F(3!) + 9) \times F(F(6 + 1))$$

$$:= T(T(3)!/9) + 6! + 1$$

$$\mathbf{3967} := 3! + (9 + F(6)) \times F(F(7))$$

$$:= T(T(3)!/9) + 6! + 7$$

$$\mathbf{3968} := F(3!) \times (9!/6! - 8)$$

$$:= T(T(3)!/9) + 6! + 8$$

$$\mathbf{4032} := F(F(4)!)/(0! + 3^2)$$

$$:= 4! \times T(0! + T(3)) \times T(T(2))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4059 &:= -F(F(F(4)!)) \times 0! + 5! \times F(9) & := (T(4!) + T(T(2) \times T(3))) \times 9 \\
 &:= (T(4) - 0!)! / 5! + T(T(9)) \\
 4094 &:= -F(F(4)) + (0! - 9)^4 & := F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) + F(4) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= -(4 \times 0)! + T(9 \times T(4)) & := (T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 4! - T(T(T(4)))) \\
 4147 &:= -F(F(F(4)! + 1) + F(F(4)! + F(7))) & := (F(F(4)!))^2 + F(4! - 5) \\
 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 7 & := -T(4!) + (T(2) + T(4!)) \times T(5) \\
 4173 &:= -T(41) + 7! - T(3) & := (-F(4)^2 + 6!) \times 6 \\
 &:= F((4 - 1)! + F(7)) - F(3!) & := (4! - T(T(2))) \times (6 + T(T(6))) \\
 4175 &:= -F(4)! + F(1 + F(7) + 5) & := 4! \times 2 \times F(F(7) - 2) \\
 &:= -T(4) - 1 + T(T(T(7) - T(5))) & := (T(4!) + T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(2)) \\
 4190 &:= F(F(4)!) + F(19) + 0! & := F(F(4)^2) \times F(8) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= 4 + T(1 + 90) & := T(4!) \times T(T(T(2))) - T(8 + T(T(4))) \\
 4196 &:= -F(4)! + F(19) + F(F(6)) & := (F(4)!! \times 2 - 9) \times 3 \\
 &:= T(4) + T(T(19 - 6)) & := T(4! + 29) \times 3 \\
 4200 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times 200 & := (-F(4) + 3!) \times (0! + 2)! \\
 &:= T(4!) \times (T(T(T(2)) - 0!) - 0!) & := (-4 + T(3)! + 0!) \times T(T(2)) \\
 4223 &:= 42 + F(-2 + F(F(3!))) & := F(4)! \times (3!! - 0!) - F(6) \\
 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(T(2 + T(T(T(2)))) / 3) & := T(T(T(4) + 3)) + (-0! + 6)! \\
 4224 &:= F(F(4)!) \times 22 \times 4! & := F(4)! \times 3!! - 10 \\
 &:= T(42) + T(T(2)^4) & := -T(4) + T(3)! \times T(T(1 + 0!)) \\
 4232 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) / 3 - T(2) & := F(4)! \times 3!! - 1 \times F(4)! \\
 &:= F(F(4)!) \times 23^2 & := 4! \times (T(3)! - 1) / 4 \\
 4236 &:= F(F(F(4)!) + 2) + F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) & := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 0 \\
 &:= -T(4!) + T(T(2))^3 \times T(6) & := 4! \times T(3)! / (T(2) + 0!) \\
 4237 &:= F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) + F(3!) \times 7 & := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 1 \\
 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(T(2)) \times T(3)! - T(7) & := T(T(-4 + T(3))) \times T(T(2))! + 1 \\
 4239 &:= 4! + F(-2 + F(F(3!))) + F(9) & := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 2 \\
 & & := 4 + T(3)! \times T(T(2)) - 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4323 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 3 \\
 &:= (4 + T(3)!) \times T(T(2)) - T(T(3)) \\
 4324 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 + T(3) \times (2 + 4)! \\
 4325 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 5 \\
 &:= T(4) + T(3)! \times T(T(2)) - 5 \\
 4326 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 6 \\
 &:= 4! - T(3) \times (T(2) - 6!) \\
 4327 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 7 \\
 &:= 4^{T(3)} + T(T(2) \times 7) \\
 4328 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 8 \\
 &:= T(T(-4 + T(3))) \times T(T(2))! + 8 \\
 4329 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + F(2) \times 9 \\
 &:= T(T(-4 + T(3))) \times T(T(2))! + 9 \\
 4331 &:= (F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 3! - 1 \\
 &:= T(4) + T(3) \times T(3)! + 1 \\
 4332 &:= F(4)! \times (F(3) + (3 \times 2)!) \\
 &:= T(4) + T(3) \times T(3)! + 2 \\
 4333 &:= (F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 3! + F(F(3)) \\
 &:= T(4) + T(3) \times T(3)! + 3 \\
 4334 &:= (F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 3! + F(F(4)) \\
 &:= T(4) + T(3) \times T(3)! + 4 \\
 4335 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + 3 \times 5 \\
 &:= T(4) + T(3) \times T(3)! + 5 \\
 4336 &:= 4^{F(3)} + 3! \times 6! \\
 &:= T(4) + T(3) \times T(3)! + 6 \\
 4337 &:= (4 + 3)! - T(37) \\
 &:= 4^{3!} + F(3!) + F(F(7)) \\
 4338 &:= (F(4) + 3!!) \times (-F(3) + 8) \\
 &:= T(4) + T(3)! \times T(3) + 8 \\
 4343 &:= (4 + 3!!) \times F(4)! - F(F(3)) \\
 &:= -4 + (T(T(T(3))) - 4!) \times T(T(3)) \\
 4347 &:= -4! + T(3 \times (4! + 7)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times 3!! + F(4)^7 \\
 4348 &:= (F(4)! + 3!!) \times F(4)! - 8 \\
 &:= 4 \times (T(3) + T(T(4) + T(8))) \\
 4350 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 0 \\
 &:= T(4) \times T(T(3) \times 5 - 0!) \\
 4356 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 6 \\
 &:= -T(4!) + T(T(3) \times T(5) + 6) \\
 4357 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 7 \\
 &:= T(4! - T(3)) + T(T(-T(5) + T(7))) \\
 4362 &:= F(4)! \times (3^6 - 2) \\
 &:= 4! + T(3) \times (6! + T(2)) \\
 4365 &:= F(4)!! + 3^6 \times 5 \\
 &:= (T(4!) - 3 - 6) \times T(5) \\
 4366 &:= F(4)^{3!} \times 6 - F(6) \\
 &:= T(4) + (T(3) + 6!) \times 6 \\
 4374 &:= F(4)^{3!} \times (7 - 4)! \\
 &:= -T(T(4!/3)) + (T(7)/4)! \\
 4378 &:= -F(4)^{F(3!)} - 7 + F(F(8)) \\
 &:= 4!/T(3) + 7! - T(T(8)) \\
 4379 &:= -4 + (3!! - F(F(7))) \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= -T(4) + T(T(T(3))) \times (T(7) - 9)$$

$$4383 := F(4)! \times 3!! + F(8) \times 3$$

$$:= (-4! + T(T(3)! - T(T(8)))) \times 3$$

$$4384 := F(4)! \times 3!! + 8^{F(F(4))}$$

$$:= (4 + 3)! - T(T(8)) + T(4)$$

$$4385 := -F(4)^{F(3!)} + F(F(F((8 - 5)!)))$$

$$:= T(4) + T(3)! + T(85)$$

$$4395 := (-F(4)!! + F(3)!) / 9 - 5$$

$$:= T(4!) + T((-3 + 9) \times T(5))$$

$$4399 := (-F(4)!! + F(3)!) - 9 / 9$$

$$:= (T(T(4)) \times T(3)! - 9) / 9$$

$$4410 := F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} \times 10$$

$$:= T(4! - 4) \times T(T(T(1 + 0!)))$$

$$4416 := 4! \times (4! - 1) \times F(6)$$

$$:= (-4! + T(4!)) \times 16$$

$$4424 := F(4!) / F(F(F(4)!)) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$:= 4 + 4 \times T(T(2))! + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$4428 := (F(4!) - F(F(F(F(4)!)))) + 2 / 8$$

$$:= T(T(T(4))) + 4 \times T(T(2))! + 8$$

$$4432 := (F(F(4)!) + F(4!) / F(F(3!))) \times 2$$

$$:= T(T(T(4))) + 4 \times (T(3)! + T(2))$$

$$4434 := (F(4)!! - F(F(4)) + F(F(3!))) \times F(4)!$$

$$:= T(4! - 4) \times T(T(3)) + 4!$$

$$4440 := F(4)! \times F(4)!! + (4 + 0)!$$

$$:= (T(4!) - 4) \times T(4 + 0!)$$

$$4443 := (4! + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! - F(F(3!))$$

$$:= (T(T(T(4))) - 4 - T(T(4))) \times 3$$

$$4446 := F(4)! \times (F(4 + 4) + 6!)$$

$$:= T(4! \times 4) - T(4) \times T(6)$$

$$4448 := F(F(4)) + F(4)! \times (F(4)!! + F(8))$$

$$:= (T(4!) + 4^4) \times 8$$

$$4459 := -F(F(F(4)!)) + (F(4) + 5)! / 9$$

$$:= 4 + T(4!) \times T(5) - T(9)$$

$$4462 := F(4)! \times (4! + 6!) - 2$$

$$:= T(T(4) \times T(4) - 6) - T(2)$$

$$4463 := F(4)! \times (4! + 6!) - F(F(3))$$

$$:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)) + T(6)) - 3$$

$$4466 := F(F(4)) + (4! + 6!) \times 6$$

$$:= T(4! + 4) \times T(T(6)) / T(6)$$

$$4467 := F(4)! \times F(4)!! + F(F(6)) \times 7$$

$$:= T(T(4!) / 4) + T(T(6)) \times 7$$

$$4469 := -F(4) - F(F(4)!) + F(6)! / 9$$

$$:= 4 + T(T(T(4)) - 6 + T(9))$$

$$4473 := 4^{F(4)!} + F(7 \times F(3))$$

$$:= (4 \times T(T(4)) - 7) \times T(T(3))$$

$$4474 := -4! \times 4! + 7! + T(4)$$

$$:= F(F(4)!)! / (-4 + F(7)) - F(4)!$$

$$4475 := F(F(4)!)! / (-4 + F(7)) - 5$$

$$:= -T(4) \times T(T(4)) + 7! - T(5)$$

$$4476 := F(4)! \times (F(F(4)) \times F(7) + 6!)$$

$$:= T(4!) - T(4) + T(T(7 + 6))$$

$$4483 := (F(F(4)!)! / (F(F(F(4)))) + 8) + 3$$

$$:= T(4!) + T(T(T(4)) + T(8)) - 3$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4485 &:= (F(F(4)!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 5 & &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 99 \\
 &:= (T(T(4!/4)) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\
 4486 &:= (F(F(4)!))!/(F(F(F(4))) + 8) + 6 & &4634 := (F(-4 + F(F(6)))) + 3!! \times F(F(4)) \\
 &:= T(4!) + T(T(T(4) + T(8 - 6))) & &:= T(4)!/6! - T(T(3 + 4)) \\
 4496 &:= F(F(4)!) + (F(F(4)!))!/9 + F(6) & &4636 := (F(4!) - F(6))/(F(3) + F(6)) \\
 &:= -4 + T(4!) \times (9 + 6) & &:= T(T(4) + T(6 + T(3))) + 6! \\
 4498 &:= -F(4) + (F(F(4)!))!/9 + F(8) & &4637 := -F(F(4))^{F(6)} + F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= T(4) + T(4! + 9) \times 8 & &:= T(4)!/6! + 3 - T(T(7)) \\
 4536 &:= F(4)! \times (5! + 3!) \times 6 & &4644 := (F(4)!! + (F(F(6)))^{F(F(4))}) \times 4 \\
 &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 36 & &:= T(T(4)) \times T(6) \times 4 + 4! \\
 4560 &:= -4 \times 5! + (F(6) - 0)! & &4656 := F(4)! \times (6! + 56) \\
 &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 60 & &:= T(4 \times (6 \times 5 - 6)) \\
 4563 &:= F(4)^5 + 6! \times 3! & &4672 := -4! \times 6! + T(7)^{T(2)} \\
 &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 63 & &:= -F(F(4)!) + 6! \times F(7)/2 \\
 4567 &:= F(F(4)!) \times (-5! + 6!) - F(F(7)) & &4674 := -F(4)! + 6! \times F(7)/F(F(4)) \\
 &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 67 & &:= -T(-T(4) + T(6)) + 7! - T(4!) \\
 4569 &:= F(F(4)!) + 5 + (F(6))!/9 & &4687 := 4! - F(6 + 8) + 7! \\
 &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 69 & &:= 4 + T(6) + T(T(8)) \times 7 \\
 4574 &:= (F(F(4) + 5)! - F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)) & &4688 := -4! + F(-6 + F(8)) \times 8 \\
 &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 74 & &:= 4! \times (T(T(6)) - T(8)) + 8 \\
 4576 &:= 4 \times (5 \times F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) & &4689 := F(4)!! + F(F(6)) \times F(8) \times 9 \\
 &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 76 & &:= 4! \times (T(T(6)) - T(8)) + 9 \\
 4578 &:= (-F(4) \times 5 + F(F(7))) \times F(8) & &4697 := (-4 + 6! - T(9)) \times 7 \\
 &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 78 & &:= -F(F(4)!) + F(6) + F(9) + 7! \\
 4596 &:= (-F(4)! + 5!) \times F(9) + 6! & &4704 := 4! \times (F(7) + 0!)^{F(F(4))} \\
 &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 96 & &:= T(47 + 0!) \times 4 \\
 4599 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! + 99) & &4720 := (F(4) + F(F(7))) \times 20 \\
 & & &:= -T(4!) + 7! - 20
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4725 &:= (-F(F(4)!) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(F(2) + 5)) \\
 &:= T(4) + 7! - T(25) \\
 4727 &:= -4! \times F(7) - F(2) + 7! \\
 &:= -T(4!) - 7 - T(T(2)) + 7! \\
 4728 &:= -4! \times F(7) + (-F(2) + 8)! \\
 &:= T(4!) \times 7 + T(2 \times T(8)) \\
 4733 &:= F(F(4)!) + (F(F(7)) - F(3!)) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(7) \times T(3 \times T(3)) \\
 4735 &:= (-F(4)!) + F(F(7)) + 3!! \times 5 \\
 &:= T(T(4)) + 7! - 3 \times 5! \\
 4736 &:= (-F(F(4))⁷ + 3!!) \times F(6) \\
 &:= T(4) + T(T(7)) + T(3) \times 6! \\
 4740 &:= (4 + F(F(7))) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \\
 &:= -T(4!) + 7! \times (4 \times 0)! \\
 4743 &:= (-4! + F(F(7)) - F(4)!) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 &:= 4! + 7! - T(4!) - T(T(3)) \\
 4744 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times F(F(4))) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 + (T(7)/4)! - T(4!) \\
 4745 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) - 4) \times 5 \\
 &:= -T(4) + 7! - T(4!) + T(5) \\
 4749 &:= -4 + T(T(7) + 4!) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(F(7)) - F(F(4) + 9) \\
 4753 &:= -F(4)!! + F(F(F(7) - 5))/F(3) \\
 &:= T(-4 \times 7 + 5^3) \\
 4763 &:= -4 + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 &:= T(4) + T(T(7 + 6) + T(3)) \\
 4764 &:= (-F(4)!) + F(F(7)) \times F(F(6)) - F(4) \\
 &:= 4! + 7! - T(6 \times 4) \\
 4773 &:= -F(F(4) + F(7)) + 7! + 3!! \\
 &:= T(4) \times T(T(7)) - 7 + T(3)! \\
 4776 &:= 4! \times F(7) \times F(7) + 6! \\
 &:= -4! + 7! - 7!/T(6) \\
 4778 &:= -F(F(4)!) - F(F(7)) + 7! - F(8) \\
 &:= -T(4) + 7! - 7 \times T(8) \\
 4779 &:= F(4)! - F(F(7)) + 7! - F(9) \\
 &:= (T(4!) + T(-7 + T(7))) \times 9 \\
 4780 &:= (F(4)! + F(F(7))) \times (F(8) - 0!) \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(7) + T(80) \\
 4783 &:= -4! - F(F(7)) + (F(8)/3)! \\
 &:= T(4) + 7! - T(8) - T(T(T(3))) \\
 4784 &:= F(4!) \times F(7)/(F(8) \times F(4)!) \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(7) + T(80) \\
 4794 &:= 47 \times F(9) \times F(4) \\
 &:= (-T(4!) + T(T(7))) \times T(9) + 4! \\
 4796 &:= -F(4)!) + 7 \times (-F(9) + 6!) \\
 &:= -4 + 7! - 9 - T(T(6)) \\
 4797 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(7)) \times 9 + 7! \\
 &:= -F(4)⁷/9 + 7! \\
 4800 &:= F(4)! \times 800 \\
 &:= T(4!) \times 8 \times (0! + 0!) \\
 4827 &:= -4! + F(8) \times (-2 + F(F(7))) \\
 &:= -4! + T((8 + T(T(2))) \times 7) \\
 4837 &:= (F(4)!! - F(8) - F(3!)) \times 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (4 + T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times 7$$

$$4848 := F(4)!! + (8! + F(4!)) / F(8)$$

$$:= 4 \times (T(8) + T(48))$$

$$4857 := -F(4) \times F(8) - 5! + 7!$$

$$:= T(4!) + (T(T(8)) - T(5)) \times 7$$

$$4859 := F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(8 + 5) - F(9)$$

$$:= -T(T(4)) + (T(T(8)) - 5!) \times 9$$

$$4863 := -F(-F(4)! + F(8)) + F(F(F(6))) / F(3)$$

$$:= 4 + 8 + T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$4870 := -4! + F(8) \times F(F(7)) + 0!$$

$$:= -T((T(4) + 8)) + 7! + 0!$$

$$4874 := -F(F(4)!) \times F(8) + 7! + F(F(4))$$

$$:= -T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) + 7! + 4!$$

$$4882 := F(-F(4)! + F(8)) \times 8 + 2$$

$$:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - T(T(2))$$

$$4884 := 4 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!)$$

$$:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - 4$$

$$4886 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 6$$

$$:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) + 8 \times 6!$$

$$4887 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 7$$

$$:= -T(T(4! - 8) / 8) + 7!$$

$$4888 := F(-F(4)! + (F(8))) \times 8 + 8$$

$$:= T(4! - 8) \times T(8) - 8$$

$$4904 := -4 \times F(9) + (0! + F(4)!)$$

$$:= (T(49) + 0!) \times 4$$

$$4927 := -4! - F(9 + 2) + 7!$$

$$:= T(T(4)) + (9 + T(2)) \times T(T(7))$$

$$4937 := -F(4) \times F(9) - F(F(3)) + 7!$$

$$:= -T(4) - 93 + 7!$$

$$4944 := (F(4)! \times F(9) + F(F(4))) \times 4!$$

$$:= (4! \times 9 - T(4)) \times 4!$$

$$4947 := (F(4) - F(9)) \times F(4) + 7!$$

$$:= -4! - T(9) - 4! + 7!$$

$$4957 := F(4) + F(9) - 5! + 7!$$

$$:= T(4 + 95) + 7$$

$$4960 := -F(4)!! / 9 + (F(6) - 0)!)$$

$$:= T(4) \times T(9 + T(6) + 0!)$$

$$4967 := -F(F(F(4))) - 9 \times F(6) + 7!$$

$$:= -T(4) - (9 - 6!) \times 7$$

$$4968 := -F(F(4)!) \times 9 + (F(6))! / 8$$

$$:= 4! \times (-9 + 6 \times T(8))$$

$$4970 := (-F(F(4)) + 9)! - 70$$

$$:= -4! - T(9) + 7! - 0!$$

$$4971 := -4! - T(9) + 7! \times 1$$

$$:= -F(F(4)) \times F(9) + 7! - 1$$

$$4973 := -F(F(4)) \times F(9) + 7! + F(F(3))$$

$$:= -T(T(4)) - 9 + 7! - 3$$

$$4974 := (4! \times F(9) + F(7)) \times F(4)!$$

$$:= 4! + T(9 \times (7 + 4))$$

$$4975 := F(-4! + F(9)) + 7! - 5!$$

$$:= T(4) + T(9) + 7! - 5!$$

$$4976 := -4! - F(9) + 7! - 6$$

$$:= -T(T(4)) - 9 + 7 \times 6!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4977 &:= -F(4) \times (F(9) - F(7)) + 7! & & := -T(5!/T(3)) + T(T(T(3))) \times 4! \\ &:= T(4) - T(9) + 7! - T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5027 &:= (5 + 02)! - F(7) & & 5337 := (5! - F(F(3!))) \times 3 + 7! \\ &:= -T(5) + 02 + 7! & & := (5! - T(T(3))) \times 3 + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5032 &:= -F(5 + 0!) + (3! + F(2))! & & 5376 := (5! + F(3!)) \times 7 \times 6 \\ &:= -5 + (0! + T(3))! - T(2) & & := T(5) \times T(T(3)) + 7! + T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5035 &:= -5 + (F(03) + 5)! & & 5409 := (-5! + F(4)!! + 0!) \times 9 \\ &:= ((5 \times 0)! + T(3))! - 5 & & := 5! \times T(T(4) - 0!) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5045 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 5 & & 5433 := -5!/F(4) + F(F(F(3!)))/F(3) \\ &:= 5 + (0! + T(T(T(4)/5)))! & & := 5! + (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5046 &:= (5 - 0! + F(4))! + 6 & & 5434 := (-5! + F(F(F(F(4)!))))/F(3) + F(F(F(4)!)) \\ &:= 5 + 0! + T(4)!/6! & & := -5! + 4! \times T(T(T(3))) + T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5061 &:= F(F(5 + 0!)) + (6 + 1)! & & 5443 := (-5!/F(F(4)) + F(F(F(F(4)!))))/F(3) \\ &:= T(5 + 0!) + (6 + 1)! & & := -5 + 4! \times (-4 + T(T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5066 &:= 5 + (0! + 6)! + F(F(6)) & & 5448 := 5! - F(4)!! + F(4!) - 8! \\ &:= 5 + (0! + 6)! + T(6) & & := (T(5) + T(T(4 + 4))) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5067 &:= 5 + 0! + F(F(6)) + 7! & & 5472 := -5! + 4! \times F(F(7) \times F(2)) \\ &:= 5 + 0! + T(6) + 7! & & := T(5 + 4!) + 7! - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5079 &:= 5 + 07! + F(9) & & 5473 := F(F(5 - 4 + 7))/F(3) \\ &:= -5 - 0! + 7! + T(9) & & := T(-T(5) + 4 \times T(7)) + T(3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5082 &:= (5! + 0!) \times (T(8) + T(T(2))) & & 5487 := (-5 + F(4)!!) \times 8 - F(F(7)) \\ &:= (5! + 0!) \times F(8) \times 2 & & := T(5) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(8)) \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5272 &:= F(F(5 + 2)) + 7! - F(2) & & 5488 := (5! + 4 \times F(F(8)))/8 \\ &:= (T(5) - 2) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(2)) & & := (5 \times 4 + T(T(8))) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5273 &:= (5 + 2)! + F(7 + 3!) & & 5535 := (5! + F(-5 + F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 - T(2) + 7! + T(T(T(3))) & & := (5! \times 5 - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5334 &:= (F(F(5 + F(3))) + F(F(3!))) \times F(F(F(4)!)) & & 5544 := (5! + 5! + 4!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\ & & & := T(5 \times 5 - 4) \times 4! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5597 &:= 5 + (-5 + 9)! \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= (5! + 5) \times T(9) - T(7) \\
 5634 &:= -5! + (F(6) \times 3!! - F(4)!) \\
 &:= -T(T(5) + T(6)) + T(T(3)) \times T(4!) \\
 5640 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 0 \\
 &:= (5! + T(6)) \times 40 \\
 5643 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 3 \\
 &:= (5 + T(T(6))) \times 4! - T(T(3)) \\
 5646 &:= -5! + F(6) \times F(4)!! + 6 \\
 &:= T(5! - T(6)) - 4! + 6! \\
 5664 &:= -5! + F(6) \times 6! + 4! \\
 &:= (5 + T(T(6))) \times 6 \times 4 \\
 5697 &:= 5 \times 6! + 9 \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= T(T(5) + T(6)) - 9 + 7! \\
 5733 &:= 5! + F(F(7)) \times F(F((3)!)) + 3!! \\
 &:= (-T(5) + T(7)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(3)) \\
 5736 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times (-3 + 6!) \\
 &:= (T(5) - 7) \times (-3 + 6!) \\
 5738 &:= 5 + F(7) \times F(F(3!)) \times F(8) \\
 &:= -T(5) - 7 + T(3)! \times 8 \\
 5747 &:= (-5 + F(7)) \times F(4)!! - F(7) \\
 &:= T(5) \times 7 \times T(T(4)) - T(7) \\
 5748 &:= -5 - 7 + F(4)!! \times 8 \\
 &:= T(57) + T(T(4)!/8!) \\
 5773 &:= -5! - F(7) - 7! + F(F(F(3!))) \\
 &:= -T(5) + 7! + T(7) + T(3)! \\
 5783 &:= -5! - 7! + F(F(8)) - 3 \\
 &:= T(5) + 7! + 8 + T(3)! \\
 5784 &:= -5! + 7! + T(8) \times 4! \\
 &:= -5! - 7! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4)) \\
 5894 &:= -5! - 8! - F(9) + F(4!) \\
 &:= (-5 + T(T(8))) \times 9 - T(T(4)) \\
 6027 &:= F(F(6) \times 02) + 7! \\
 &:= T(T(6) - 0! + T(T(T(2)))) \times 7 \\
 6048 &:= F(6 \times 04) - 8! \\
 &:= (6 + 0!) \times 4! \times T(8) \\
 6174 &:= F(F(6)) \times (1 + F(7)) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= T(6) \times (1 - 7 + T(4!)) \\
 6237 &:= F(F(6)) \times (2^{3!} + F(F(7))) \\
 &:= T(T(6)) \times (2 - 3 + T(7)) \\
 6264 &:= (F(6) + F(2)) \times (6! - 4!) \\
 &:= (6!/T(2) + T(6)) \times 4! \\
 6324 &:= -F(F(6))^{F(3)} + F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(6))/3) + T(T(2)^4) \\
 6336 &:= 6^{3!} - (F(3) + 6)! \\
 &:= T(63) + T(3) \times 6! \\
 6384 &:= F(F(6)) \times 38 \times F(F(4)!) \\
 &:= T(6) \times (T(3 \times 8) + 4) \\
 6426 &:= (6! - F(4)!) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \\
 &:= T(T(6) - 4) \times 2 \times T(6) \\
 6432 &:= (6! + 4!!/(F(F(3!))))/2 \\
 &:= (6 + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) + T(T(2)) \\
 6435 &:= F(6 + 4) \times (-3 + 5!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(6 + 4) \times (-3 + 5!)$$

$$\mathbf{6444} := (6! - 4) \times F(4) \times F(4)$$

$$:= T(T(6)) \times (4! + 4) - 4!$$

$$\mathbf{6447} := (F(6))!/F(4)! - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(7)$$

$$:= T(T(6)) + T(4! + 4!) + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{6459} := -F(F(6)) + F(4)! \times 5! \times 9$$

$$:= -T(6) + (4! + 5!) \times T(9)$$

$$\mathbf{6469} := -F(6) - F(4) + 6! \times 9$$

$$:= -T(6) + T(4) + 6! \times 9$$

$$\mathbf{6472} := F(6) \times (F(4)!! + F(F(7) - 2))$$

$$:= -6 + T(4) + T(7) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{6473} := F(6) \times F(4)!! - 7 + 3!!$$

$$:= 6! \times T(4) - 7 - T(3)!$$

$$\mathbf{6490} := (6! + F(F(F(4)))) \times 9 + 0!$$

$$:= T(6) \times (T(4!) + 9) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{6496} := -F(6) + 4! + 9 \times 6!$$

$$:= 6 + T(4) + 9 \times 6!$$

$$\mathbf{6497} := (6! - 4!) \times 9 + F(F(7))$$

$$:= 6! \times T(4) - T(9 + T(7))$$

$$\mathbf{6498} := (6! + F(F(4))) \times 9!/8!$$

$$:= T(6) \times 4! + 9 \times T(T(8))$$

$$\mathbf{6594} := -6 + 5! \times F(F(9) - 4!)$$

$$:= -6 + 5! \times (T(9) + T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{6624} := -6! \times 6 - 2 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))$$

$$:= T(T(6) + 6/T(2)) \times 4!$$

$$\mathbf{6644} := F(F(F(6))) + (-6! + F(4)) \times F(4)!$$

$$:= -6 + (6! - T(T(4))) \times T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{6648} := 6! + (F(F(6)) + F(4)!) \times 8$$

$$:= -6 - 6 + T(4) \times T(T(8))$$

$$\mathbf{6660} := (F(6))!/6 - 60$$

$$:= 6 \times (-6! + T(60))$$

$$\mathbf{6744} := (6 + 7!/F(4)) \times 4$$

$$:= T(T(6)) \times T(7) + T(4!) - 4!$$

$$\mathbf{6834} := (6! + 8!)/3! - F(4)!$$

$$:= -6 + (-T(8) + T(3)!) \times T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{6867} := (-6 + F(8 + F(6))) \times 7$$

$$:= T(T(6)) \times 8 - T(6) + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{6930} := 6 \times (F(9)^{F(3)} - 0!)$$

$$:= 6 \times T(T(9)) + T(3 + 0)!$$

$$\mathbf{7203} := 7^{2+0!} \times F(F(3!))$$

$$:= 7^{T(2)+0!} \times 3$$

$$\mathbf{7227} := 7! + F(2 + 2)^7$$

$$:= 7! + (T(T(2))/2)^7$$

$$\mathbf{7237} := (F(7) \times F(2))^3 + 7!$$

$$:= (7 + T(T(2)))^3 + 7!$$

$$\mathbf{7246} := 7! - 2 + F(4!)/F(F(6))$$

$$:= (7! - T(T(2))!) + T(T(T(4)) + T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{7344} := -T(T(7)) + (T(3)! + T(T(4))) \times T(4)$$

$$:= 7! + (F(3) \times 4!)^{F(F(4))}$$

$$\mathbf{7353} := 7 + F(F(F(3!))) - 5 \times 3!!$$

$$:= (T(T(7)) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times 3$$

$$\mathbf{7365} := -F(F(7)) \times 3 + (F(6))!/5$$

$$:= 7 \times T(T(3 + 6)) + 5!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7413 &:= (F(F(7)) + (4 + 1)!) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 &:= (T(7) + T(4! + 1)) \times T(T(3)) \\
 7434 &:= (7!/4 - F(F(3!))) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(3)) \times T(4!) \\
 7441 &:= 7^4 + (F(4)! + 1)! \\
 &:= 7! + T(T(T(4))) + T(41) \\
 7443 &:= -(F(7) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))) \times F(4) + F(3)! \\
 &:= (T(7 \times T(4)) - 4) \times 3 \\
 7455 &:= 7! + F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! - 5) \\
 &:= 7! + T(T(45)/T(5)) \\
 7456 &:= F(F(7)) \times (-4! + 56) \\
 &:= T(T(7)) - T(4) \times (T(5) - 6!) \\
 7476 &:= (7^{F(4)} + F(7)) \times F(F(6)) \\
 &:= 7! + T(4 \times 7) \times 6 \\
 7495 &:= -F(F(7)) + F(4!)/(F(9 - 5))! \\
 &:= 7! + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9)) - 5! \\
 7584 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(8) + 4! \\
 &:= 7! - 5! + T(T(8)) \times 4 \\
 7637 &:= F(7) + F(6 \times 3) + 7! \\
 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(T(T(6)))/3 + 7! \\
 7644 &:= F(7) \times F(F(6)) \times (4! + 4) \\
 &:= T(7) \times T(T(6)) + T(4! + 4!) \\
 7689 &:= F(F(7)) \times (-F(6)/8 + F(9)) \\
 &:= 7! + T(6) + T(8 \times 9) \\
 7694 &:= (F(F(7)) - 6) \times F(9) - 4! \\
 &:= -T(T(7)) + 6! \times T(9)/4 \\
 7874 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(8)) \times (7 + 4!) \\
 &:= 7! - T(T(8)) + 7! - T(T(T(4))) \\
 7920 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 0 \\
 &:= -7! + (9!/T(T(T(2)) + 0!)) \\
 7923 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 3 \\
 &:= 7 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) + T(3)! \\
 7926 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 6 \\
 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(2)) - 6! \\
 7937 &:= 7 \times T(T(9)) + T(3)! - T(7) \\
 &:= F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 7 \\
 7942 &:= (T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times (4! - 2) \\
 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2) \\
 8043 &:= 8!/(0! + 4) - F(F(3!)) \\
 &:= 8!/(0! + 4) - T(T(3)) \\
 8085 &:= F(8) + 08!/5 \\
 &:= (T(8) - 0!) \times T(T(8) - T(5)) \\
 8317 &:= 8!/3! + F(17) \\
 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 1^7 \\
 8344 &:= 8 \times 3!! + F(F(4) \times F(4)!) \\
 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 4! + 4 \\
 8445 &:= 8!/4! + F(4 \times 5) \\
 &:= T(T(8)) \times T(4!)/4! + 5! \\
 8642 &:= F(F(8)) - (F(6) \times F(4)!)^2 \\
 &:= (8 + T(6)) \times (T(4!) - 2) \\
 8694 &:= F(8) \times 69 \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(8) \times T(69)/T(4) \\
 8784 &:= 8!/(F(7) - 8) + F(4)!!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= -T(8) + (-7! + 8!)/4$$

$$:= (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(3)) \times 3$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8856 &:= (F(8 + 8) + 5!) \times F(6) \\ &:= T(8) \times (T(8) + 5) \times 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9360 &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 0 \\ &:= T(9 + 3) \times (6 - 0)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8972 &:= F(F(8)) - F(9 + 7) \times 2 \\ &:= 8 \times T(T(9)) - T(7) + (T(T(2)))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9407 &:= F(9) + (F(4)!! + 0!) \times F(7) \\ &:= T(T(9)) + (T(4!) - 0!) \times T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9243 &:= -9 \times 2 + F(F(F(4)!))!^3 \\ &:= 9 \times (2^{T(4)} + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9454 &:= F(9) \times (F(4)!! - 5!) - F(F(F(F(4)!))) \\ &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9244 &:= F(9)^2 \times F(F(4)!) - 4 \\ &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9477 &:= 9^{-4+7} \times F(7) \\ &:= T(94) - T(7) + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$9333 := 9 \times F(3!) + F(F(3!))^3$$

2.2.2 Reverse Order of Digits

• Symmetric

$$720 := 0 + (-F(2) + 7)! = 0 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7!$$

$$721 := 1 + (-F(2) + 7)! = 1 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7!$$

$$722 := 2 + (-F(2) + 7)! = 2 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7!$$

$$723 := 3 + (-F(2) + 7)! = 3 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7!$$

$$724 := 4 + (-F(2) + 7)! = 4 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7!$$

$$725 := 5 + (-F(2) + 7)! = 5 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7!$$

$$726 := 6 + (-F(2) + 7)! = 6 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7!$$

$$727 := 7 + (-F(2) + 7)! = 7 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7!$$

$$728 := 8 + (-F(2) + 7)! = 8 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7!$$

$$729 := 9 + (-F(2) + 7)! = 9 + T(T(T(T(2))))/7!$$

$$4320 := 0 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4) = 0 - T(T(2))! + (3 + 4)!$$

$$4321 := 1 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4) = 1 - T(T(2))! + (3 + 4)!$$

$$4322 := 2 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4) = 2 - T(T(2))! + (3 + 4)!$$

$$4323 := 3 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4) = 3 - T(T(2))! + (3 + 4)!$$

$$4324 := 4 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4) = 4 - T(T(2))! + (3 + 4)!$$

$$4325 := 5 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4) = 5 - T(T(2))! + (3 + 4)!$$

$$4326 := 6 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4) = 6 - T(T(2))! + (3 + 4)!$$

$$4327 := 7 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4) = 7 - T(T(2))! + (3 + 4)!$$

$$4328 := 8 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4) = 8 - T(T(2))! + (3 + 4)!$$

$$4329 := 9 + 2 \times 3!! \times F(4) = 9 - T(T(2))! + (3 + 4)!$$

$$\begin{aligned}5040 &:= 0 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! = 1 + T(4)! / (0! + 5)! \\5041 &:= 1 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! = 1 + T(4)! / (0! + 5)! \\5042 &:= 2 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! = 2 + T(4)! / (0! + 5)! \\5043 &:= 3 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! = 3 + T(4)! / (0! + 5)! \\5044 &:= 4 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! = 4 + T(4)! / (0! + 5)! \\5045 &:= 5 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! = 5 + T(4)! / (0! + 5)! \\5046 &:= 6 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! = 6 + T(4)! / (0! + 5)! \\5047 &:= 7 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! = 7 + T(4)! / (0! + 5)! \\5048 &:= 8 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! = 8 + T(4)! / (0! + 5)! \\5049 &:= 9 + (F(4) - 0! + 5)! = 9 + T(4)! / (0! + 5)!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5760 &:= 0 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) = 0 + 6! \times (-7 + T(5)) \\5761 &:= 1 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) = 1 + 6! \times (-7 + T(5)) \\5762 &:= 2 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) = 2 + 6! \times (-7 + T(5)) \\5763 &:= 3 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) = 3 + 6! \times (-7 + T(5)) \\5764 &:= 4 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) = 4 + 6! \times (-7 + T(5)) \\5765 &:= 5 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) = 5 + 6! \times (-7 + T(5)) \\5766 &:= 6 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) = 6 + 6! \times (-7 + T(5)) \\5767 &:= 7 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) = 7 + 6! \times (-7 + T(5)) \\5768 &:= 8 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) = 8 + 6! \times (-7 + T(5)) \\5769 &:= 9 + 6! \times (F(7) - 5) = 9 + 6! \times (-7 + T(5))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6480 &:= 0 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 1 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\6481 &:= 1 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 1 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\6482 &:= 2 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 2 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\6483 &:= 3 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 3 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\6484 &:= 4 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 4 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\6485 &:= 5 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 5 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\6486 &:= 6 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 6 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\6487 &:= 7 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 7 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\6488 &:= 8 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 8 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\6489 &:= 9 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 9 + T(8)/4 \times 6!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6840 &:= 0 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6 = 0 - T(4) \times (T(8) - 6!) \\6841 &:= 1 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6 = 1 - T(4) \times (T(8) - 6!) \\6842 &:= 2 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6 = 2 - T(4) \times (T(8) - 6!) \\6843 &:= 3 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6 = 3 - T(4) \times (T(8) - 6!) \\6844 &:= 4 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6 = 4 - T(4) \times (T(8) - 6!) \\6845 &:= 5 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6 = 5 - T(4) \times (T(8) - 6!) \\6846 &:= 6 + (F(4)!! + 8!) / 6 = 6 - T(4) \times (T(8) - 6)!\end{aligned}$$

$$6847 := 7 + (F(4)!! + 8!)/6 = 7 - T(4) \times (T(8) - 6!)$$

$$6848 := 8 + (F(4)!! + 8!)/6 = 8 - T(4) \times (T(8) - 6!)$$

$$6849 := 9 + (F(4)!! + 8!)/6 = 9 - T(4) \times (T(8) - 6!)$$

$$7560 := 0 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7! = 0 + T(6) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7561 := 1 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7! = 1 + T(6) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7562 := 2 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7! = 2 + T(6) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7563 := 3 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7! = 3 + T(6) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7564 := 4 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7! = 4 + T(6) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7565 := 5 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7! = 5 + T(6) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7566 := 6 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7! = 6 + T(6) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7567 := 7 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7! = 7 + T(6) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7568 := 8 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7! = 8 + T(6) \times 5! + 7!$$

$$7569 := 9 + F(F(6)) \times 5! + 7! = 9 + T(6) \times 5! + 7!$$

• **Nonsymmetric**

$$21 := F(F((1 + 2)!)) \\ := T(T(1 + 2))$$

$$23 := F(F(3!)) + 2 \\ := T(T(3)) + 2$$

$$143 := T(3) \times 4! - 1 \\ := F(3 \times 4) - 1$$

$$144 := 4! \times T(4 - 1) \\ := F(4 \times (4 - 1))$$

$$147 := 7 \times F(F((4 - 1)!)) \\ := 7 \times T(T(4 - 1))$$

$$227 := F(F(7)) - F(2 + 2)! \\ := -7 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2)$$

$$232 := -F(2) + F(F(3! + F(2))) \\ := T(2) + T(T(T(3))) - 2$$

$$235 := F(F(5 + F(3))) + 2 \\ := (-T(5) + T(3)!)/T(2)$$

$$247 := F(7) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \\ := T(T(7) + T(4))/T(2)$$

$$254 := F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(5 + 2)) \\ := T(T(4)) \times 5 - T(T(T(2)))$$

$$273 := F(F(3!)) \times F(7) \times F(2) \\ := T(T(3) + 7) \times T(2)$$

$$274 := F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(7) + F(2) \\ := T(4!) - T(7) + 2$$

$$336 := F(6)!/(F(3) + 3)! \\ := T(63)/T(3)$$

$$354 := F(4) \times (5!) - 3! \\ := 4! \times T(5) - T(3)$$

$$364 := 4 + 6!/F(3) \\ := T(T(T(4)) - T(6)) - T(T(T(3)))$$

$$369 := 9 + 6!/F(3)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= T(T(9)) - T(6 \times T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{384} &:= 4! \times 8 \times F(3) \\
 &:= -T(4!) - T(8) + T(3)! \\
 \mathbf{432} &:= 2 \times 3!^{F(4)} \\
 &:= T(2) \times T(3) \times 4! \\
 \mathbf{433} &:= F(F(3!))^{F(3)} - F(F(4)!) \\
 &:= T(3^3) + T(T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{445} &:= 5 \times F(F(4) + F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= T(5 + 4!) + T(4) \\
 \mathbf{462} &:= (F(2) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= -T(2) + T(6!/4!) \\
 \mathbf{472} &:= 2 \times F(F(7)) + F(4)! \\
 &:= T(T(2) + T(7)) - 4! \\
 \mathbf{497} &:= (-7! + 9!)/F(4)!! \\
 &:= T(T(7)) + T(9 + 4) \\
 \mathbf{504} &:= 4! \times F(F(0! + 5)) \\
 &:= 4! \times T(0! + 5) \\
 \mathbf{546} &:= F(F(6)) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + 5) \\
 &:= T(T(6)) + T(4!) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{564} &:= 4 \times (F(F(6)) + 5!) \\
 &:= 4 \times (T(6) + 5!) \\
 \mathbf{576} &:= 6! - F(7 + 5) \\
 &:= T(T(T(6))/7) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{733} &:= (3 + 3)! + F(7) \\
 &:= T(3)! + T(3) + 7 \\
 \mathbf{735} &:= 5 \times F(F(3!)) \times 7 \\
 &:= 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 7 \\
 \mathbf{748} &:= F(8) + F(4)!! + 7 \\
 &:= T(T(8/4))! + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{846} &:= 6!/4 + T(T(8)) \\
 &:= 6! + F(4)! \times F(8) \\
 \mathbf{0133} &:= 3! \times (F(F(3!)) + 1) + 0! \\
 &:= -3 + T(T(3) + 10) \\
 \mathbf{0134} &:= 4! \times T(3) - 10 \\
 &:= F(4 \times 3) - 10 \\
 \mathbf{0142} &:= -2 + F(4!/(1 + 0!)) \\
 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(4 + 1) + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0147} &:= 7 \times F(4 \times (1 + 0!)) \\
 &:= T(7) + (4 + 1)! - 0! \\
 \mathbf{0155} &:= -5! + 5 \times F(10) \\
 &:= 5 + T(5) \times 10 \\
 \mathbf{0157} &:= F(7) + F(5!/10) \\
 &:= 7 + T(5) \times 10 \\
 \mathbf{0169} &:= F(9) \times (6 - 1) - 0! \\
 &:= (T(T(9)) - T(6))/T(T(1 + 0!)) \\
 \mathbf{0176} &:= F(6) \times (F(7 + 1) + 0!) \\
 &:= -T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) \times 1 + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0179} &:= F(9) + F(F(7) - 1) + 0! \\
 &:= -T(9) - 7 + T(T(T(T(1 + 0!)))) \\
 \mathbf{0184} &:= F(F(4!)) \times (F(8) + 1 + 0!) \\
 &:= (4 \times (T(8) + 10)) \\
 \mathbf{0194} &:= F(4)! \times F(9) - 10 \\
 &:= 4 + T(9 + 10)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{0197} &:= F(F(7)) - F(9) - 1 - 0! & &:= 4! \times (T(6 - 2) + 0!) \\
 &:= 7 + T(9 + 10) \\
 \mathbf{0204} &:= F(4)! \times F(0! + F((2 + 0)!)) & &:= 5! + F(6 \times 2) + 0! \\
 &:= -T(4 - 0!) + T(20) & &:= T(56)/T(T(2)) - 0! \\
 \mathbf{0213} &:= F(F(3! + 1)) - 20 & &:= -6! + F(F(6) \times 2) - 0! \\
 &:= 3 + T(1 \times 20) & &:= T(T(6)) + 6^2 - 0! \\
 \mathbf{0233} &:= F(33 - 20) & &:= F(F(7)) + F(F(6) + (2 \times 0)!) \\
 &:= (T(3)! - T(T(3)))/T(2 + 0) & &:= T(7) + 6!/T(2) - 0! \\
 \mathbf{0234} &:= F(4 + 3^2) + 0! & &:= F(9) \times F(6) - 2 - 0! \\
 &:= 4 \times T(3) + T(20) & &:= T(9) \times 6 - (2 \times 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0237} &:= 7 \times F(3^2) - 0! & &:= F(3!) \times F(7 + 2) + 0! \\
 &:= 7!/T(T(3)) - T(2 + 0) & &:= 3 \times T(-7 + 20) \\
 \mathbf{0239} &:= F(9) \times (3! + F(2)) + 0! & &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(7)) + 20 \\
 &:= (9 - 3)!/T(2) - 0! & &:= T(4!) - T(7) + 2 + 0 \\
 \mathbf{0244} &:= F(4)^{F(4)+2} + 0! & &:= (5! - T(7)) \times T(2) - 0! \\
 &:= 4! + T(4) + T(20) & &:= (5 \times F(((7 + 2) + (0)!))) \\
 \mathbf{0247} &:= F(F(7)) - F(4)! + 20 & &:= (F(F(6)) \times F(7)) + 2 + 0! \\
 &:= (T(T(7) + T(4)))/T(2 + 0) & &:= 6 \times (T(7 + 2) + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0248} &:= 8 + F(4)!!/(2 + 0!) & &:= 7 \times (F(8) \times 2 - 0!) \\
 &:= 8 \times (T(4) \times T(2) + 0!) & &:= T(T(7)) - (8 - T(2))! + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0249} &:= 9 + F(4)!!/(2 + 0!) & &:= F(F(3!)) + F(9) \times F((2 + 0)!) \\
 &:= -T(9) + T(4!) - T(T(2 + 0)) & &:= -T(3)! + T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2))) - 0! \\
 \mathbf{0254} &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(5 + 2 + 0)) & &:= F(6) \times (F(9) + 2 + 0!) \\
 &:= T(4 \times 5 + 2) + 0! & &:= T(T(6)) + T(9) + 20 \\
 \mathbf{0257} &:= F(F(7)) + 5^2 - 0! & &:= F(F(6) + 0!) \times (F(3!) + 0!) \\
 &:= T(7 + T(5)) + T(2) + 0! & &:= T(60)/T(3) + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0264} &:= 4! \times (F(6) + 2 + 0!) & &:= F(4)!^2 \times (F(3!) + 0!) \\
 & & &:= 4 \times T(2)^{3+0!}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}0326 &:= 6!/2 - F(F(3!)) + 0! \\ &:= T(T(6) - 2 + T(3)) + 0! \\0329 &:= F(9 + F(2)) \times 3! - 0! \\ &:= (T(9) + 2) \times (T(3) + 0!) \\0342 &:= (F(2) + F(4)!)^3 - 0! \\ &:= (T(2) + 4)^3 - 0! \\0344 &:= (F(4) + 4)^3 + 0! \\ &:= T(4!) + 43 + 0! \\0345 &:= 5! - F(F(4)!) + F(F(3! + 0!)) \\ &:= -5 \times 4! + T(30) \\0347 &:= 7^{F(4)} + 3 + 0! \\ &:= T(T(7)) - T(4) \times T(3) + 0! \\0349 &:= (F(9) + 4!) \times 3! + 0! \\ &:= T(9) + T(4!) + 3 + 0! \\0352 &:= -F(2) + 5! + F(F(3! + 0!)) \\ &:= (-T(2) + 5!) \times 3 + 0! \\0354 &:= F(4) \times 5! - (3 + 0)! \\ &:= 4! \times T(5) - T(3 + 0) \\0356 &:= F(6 + 5) \times (3 + 0!) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + 5^3 + 0 \\0357 &:= F(F(7)) + 5! + 3 + 0! \\ &:= 7!/T(5) + T(T(3 + 0)) \\0358 &:= 8!/5! + F(F(3!)) + 0! \\ &:= 8!/5! + T(T(3)) + 0! \\0368 &:= 8 + 6!/F(3 + 0) \\ &:= 8 \times (T(6 + 3) + 0!) \\0369 &:= 9 + 6!/F(3 + 0) \\ &:= -96 + T(30) \\0371 &:= F(1 + F(7)) - (3 + 0)! \\ &:= T(-1 + T(7)) - T(3) - 0! \\0374 &:= -F(4) + F(F(7)) + (3 \times 0!) \\ &:= T(4!) + 73 + 0! \\0375 &:= 5! + F(F(7)) + F(F(3!)) + 0! \\ &:= 5! \times 7 - T(30) \\0377 &:= F(7 + 7) + 3 \times 0 \\ &:= T(T(7)) - T(7) - (3 \times 0)! \\0384 &:= 4! \times 8 \times F(3 + 0) \\ &:= 4! \times (T(8 - 3) + 0!) \\0386 &:= F(6) + F(8 + 3!) + 0! \\ &:= -6!/T(8) + T(T(T(3) + 0!)) \\0397 &:= (F(F(7)) - F(9)) \times F(3) - 0! \\ &:= T(T(7)) - 9 + 3 \times 0 \\0398 &:= F(8) + F(9 + 3! - 0!) \\ &:= -8 + T(9 \times 3 + 0!) \\0428 &:= F(8)^2 - F(F(4)!) + 0! \\ &:= -T(8) + T(T(2) \times T(4)) - 0! \\0429 &:= (F(9) - F(2)) \times F(F(4)!) + 0! \\ &:= (T(9) - 2) \times T(4) - 0! \\0433 &:= 3 \times F(3 \times 4) + 0! \\ &:= 3 \times T(3) \times 4! + 0! \\0435 &:= (-5 + F(F(3!))^{F(F(4))}) - 0! \\ &:= T(5) \times (T(3 + 4) + 0!) \\0436 &:= F(F(6))^{F(3)} - 4 - 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(6) \times T(T(3)) - 4 - 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0439} := F(9 + F(F(3))) \times F(F(4)!) - 0!$$

$$:= T(T(9)) - T(34) - 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0457} := (F(F(7)) - 5) \times F(F(4)) + 0!$$

$$:= T(T(7)) + 5 \times T(4) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0458} := -F(8) + 5! \times 4 - 0!$$

$$:= -8 + T(5!/4) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0461} := (1 + F(F(6))) \times F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!$$

$$:= T(16) + T(4! + 0!)$$

$$\mathbf{0462} := (F(2) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(F(4 + 0)!))$$

$$:= 2 \times T(6) \times (T(4) + 0!)$$

$$\mathbf{0463} := F(F(3!)) + F(F(6))^{F(F(4))} + 0!$$

$$:= -3 + T(6!/4!) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0466} := F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)) + 4! + 0!$$

$$:= T(6 + 6 \times 4) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0469} := -F(9) + F(F(6)) \times 4! - 0!$$

$$:= T(9 + T(6)) + 4 + 0$$

$$\mathbf{0472} := 2 \times F(F(7)) + F(4 + 0)!$$

$$:= T(T(2) + T(7)) - (4 + 0)!$$

$$\mathbf{0473} := (3 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)) + 0!$$

$$:= T(3 + T(7)) - 4! + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0476} := (F(F(6)) - 7) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + 0!$$

$$:= -T(6) + T(7 + 4!) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0483} := F(F(3)) \times F(8) \times (4! - 0!)$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times ((8 - 4)! - 0!)$$

$$\mathbf{0486} := 6! - F(F(F(8)/F(4))) - 0!$$

$$:= 6 \times (8 \times T(4) + 0!)$$

$$\mathbf{0487} := -F(F(7)) + (8 - F(4) + 0)!!$$

$$:= T(T(7)) + 8 \times T(4) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0488} := 8 \times (T(8) + 4! + 0!)$$

$$:= 8 \times (F(8) + 40)$$

$$\mathbf{0492} := 2^9 - F(F(F(4)!)) + 0!$$

$$:= -T(2) + T(9) \times (T(4) + 0!)$$

$$\mathbf{0496} := -F(6) + 9!/F(4 + 0)!!$$

$$:= T(T(6) + 9 + (4 \times 0)!)$$

$$\mathbf{0503} := F(F(3!)) \times (-0! + 5)! - 0!$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times (-0! + 5)! - 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0504} := 4! \times F(F(0! + 5 + 0))$$

$$:= 4! \times T(0! + 5 + 0)$$

$$\mathbf{0512} := 2^{F(1+5)+0!}$$

$$:= 2^{-1+T(5-0!)}$$

$$\mathbf{0524} := F(F(F(4)!)) \times 25 - 0!$$

$$:= -4 + T(2^5 + 0)$$

$$\mathbf{0526} := F(F(6)) \times 25 + 0!$$

$$:= T(6) \times 25 + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0528} := (F(8) + F(2)) \times (5 - 0)!!$$

$$:= T(82 - 50)$$

$$\mathbf{0534} := F(4)! \times F(3! + 5 + 0)$$

$$:= T(4!) + 3 + T(T(5 + 0!))$$

$$\mathbf{0546} := F(F(6)) \times (-4! + 50)$$

$$:= T(6) \times (T(4) + T(5) + 0!)$$

$$\mathbf{0564} := 4 \times (F(F(6)) + (5 + 0)!)$$

$$:= 4 \times (T(6) + 5!) + 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0573 &:= -F(F(3!)) \times 7 + (5 + 0!)! \\ &:= T(3)! - T(7) - 5! + 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 5^4 + T(6) - 0!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0576 &:= 6! - F(7 + 5 + 0) \\ &:= (6! + 7!)/T(5 - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0648 &:= 8 \times (F(F(F(4)!)) + 60) \\ &:= T(8) \times (4! - 6 + 0) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0586 &:= F(-6 + F(8)) - (5 - 0!)! \\ &:= T(-6 + T(8)) + 5! + 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0672 &:= (F(2) + 7)!/60 \\ &:= 2 \times 7!/T(6 - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0593 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(9) - 5! - 0! \\ &:= T(3)! + 9 - T(T(5) + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0673 &:= 3!! + F(7) - 60 \\ &:= T(T(3) \times 7) - T(T(6)) + 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0594 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9) - (5 + 0)! \\ &:= T(4! + T(9 - 5)) - 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0684 &:= (F(4)!! + 8!)/60 \\ &:= 4! + T(T(8)) - 6 + 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0615 &:= 5 + F(16 - 0!) \\ &:= -T(T(5) - 1) + 6! \times 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0687 &:= -F(7) - F(8) + 6! + 0! \\ &:= -7 + T(T(8)) + T(6 + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0617 &:= 7 + F(16 - 0!) \\ &:= T(7) \times (1 + T(6)) + 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0689 &:= -9 - F(8) + 6! - 0! \\ &:= T(9) + T(T(8)) - T(6) - 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0631 &:= (1 + 3!)!/F(6) + 0! \\ &:= 1 + T(36 - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0694 &:= -F(4) \times 9 + 6! + 0! \\ &:= (4! + 9) \times T(6) + 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0634 &:= 4! + F(3! + F(6) + 0!) \\ &:= 4 + T(36 - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0697 &:= -F(7) - 9 + 6! - 0! \\ &:= T(T(7) + 9) - 6 + 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0635 &:= 5 \times (3! \times F(F(6)) + 0!) \\ &:= 5 \times (T(3) \times T(6) + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0698 &:= -F(8) + (9 - 6)!! - 0! \\ &:= T(-8 + T(9)) - 6 + 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0637 &:= F(7) \times (3! \times F(6) + 0!) \\ &:= -T(7) \times 3 + 6! + 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0702 &:= (2 + 0!) \times (F(F(7)) + 0!) \\ &:= 2 \times T(-0! + T(7) - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0639 &:= -9^{F(3)} + (6 + 0)! \\ &:= 9 + T(36 - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0703 &:= 3 \times (0! + F(F(7))) + 0! \\ &:= T(30 + 7 + 0) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0644 &:= F(4!)/(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(6) + 0!) \\ &:= T(T(4 + 4)) - T(6) - 0! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0732 &:= (2 \times 3)! + F(7) - 0! \\ &:= T(2) + 3^{7-0!} \end{aligned}$$

$$0645 := 5^4 + F(F(6)) - 0!$$

$$\begin{aligned} 0736 &:= 6! + 3 + F(7 + 0) \\ &:= T(6 \times T(3)) + 70 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 0738 &:= F(8) - 3 + (7 - 0!)! \\
 &:= T(8) + T(37) - 0! \\
 0741 &:= F(1 \times 4)!! + F(7 + 0!) \\
 &:= T(T(1 \times 4) + T(7 + 0)) \\
 0745 &:= 5^{F(F(4))} + (7 - 0!)! \\
 &:= T(5) + T(4) + (7 - 0!)! \\
 0746 &:= F(6)^{F(4)} + F(F(7)) + 0! \\
 &:= 6! + T(T(4)) - T(7) - 0! \\
 0748 &:= F(8) + F(4)!! + 7 + 0 \\
 &:= T(T(8)) + T(T(4)) + T(7) - 0! \\
 0753 &:= F(F(F(3!)) - 5) - F(F(7)) - 0! \\
 &:= T(3)! + 5 + T(7 + 0) \\
 0754 &:= (-F(4) + 5) \times F(F(7) + 0!) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) - 5! - T(T(7 + 0!)) \\
 0762 &:= 2 \times F(F(6)) + (7 - 0!)! \\
 &:= 2 \times T(6) + (7 - 0!)! \\
 0782 &:= (2 + F(F(8)))/(F(7) + 0!) \\
 &:= T(T(2))! - 8 + 70 \\
 0783 &:= 3 \times F(8) + (7 - 0!)! \\
 &:= T(3)! + T(8) + T(7) - 0! \\
 0784 &:= F(4)!! + 8 \times (7 + 0!) \\
 &:= T(4 + T(8)) - T(7 + 0!) \\
 0834 &:= -F(F(4)!) + (F(F(F(3!)))/F(8 - 0!)) \\
 &:= T(T(4)) + T(3 + T(8)) - 0! \\
 0835 &:= 5 \times (F(3!) \times F(8) + 0!) \\
 &:= T(5) + T(3 + T(8) + 0!) \\
 0836 &:= -6 + F(F(F(3!)))/F(8 - 0!) \\
 &:= T(6 \times 3) + T(T(8)) - 0! \\
 0839 &:= ((F(9) + 3!) \times F(8)) - 0! \\
 &:= T(T(9)) - T(T(T(3))) + T(8) - 0! \\
 0841 &:= (-1 + F(F(F(F(4)!)))/F(8 - 0!)) \\
 &:= 1 + 4! \times (T(8) - 0!) \\
 0842 &:= F(F(2 \times 4))/F(8 - 0!) \\
 &:= 2 + 4! \times (T(8) - 0!) \\
 0843 &:= F(F(F(3!)) - F(4)!) + F(F(8 - 0!)) \\
 &:= 3 + 4! \times (T(8) - 0!) \\
 0844 &:= F(F(4) + F(F(F(F(4)!)))/F(8 - 0!)) \\
 &:= 4 + 4! \times (T(8) - 0!) \\
 0845 &:= 5 \times (F(F(4)!) \times F(8) + 0!) \\
 &:= 5 + 4! \times (T(8) - 0!) \\
 0846 &:= 6! + F(4)! \times F(8 + 0) \\
 &:= 6 + 4! \times (T(8) - 0!) \\
 0847 &:= 7!/F(4)! + 8 - 0! \\
 &:= 7 + 4! \times (T(8) - 0!) \\
 0849 &:= F(9) \times (4 + F(8)) - 0! \\
 &:= 9 + 4! \times (T(8) - 0!) \\
 0856 &:= F(6) \times (5! - F(8 - 0!)) \\
 &:= 6! + T(T(5)) + (8 \times 0!) \\
 0863 &:= F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(6)))/F(8 - 0!) \\
 &:= (3 + T(6)) \times T(8) - 0! \\
 0864 &:= 4! \times 6!/(F(8) - 0!) \\
 &:= 4 \times 6 \times T(8 + 0) \\
 0873 &:= 3!! + F(F(7)) - 80
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(T(3+7)) - T(T(8)) - 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0874} := F(4)!! + 7 \times (F(8) + 0!) \\ := T(T(4)) \times T(7) - T(T(8+0))$$

$$\mathbf{0876} := 6 \times (7 \times F(8) - 0!) \\ := -6! + T(7 \times 8 + 0)$$

$$\mathbf{0932} := F(2 \times F(3!)) - F(9 + 0!) \\ := 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + 9) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0937} := F(7) \times F(3!) \times 9 + 0! \\ := -7 + T(T(3)) \times T(9) - 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0947} := F(F(7)) + F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(9 + 0) \\ := T(7 + 4 \times 9) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0952} := (-F(2) + 5!) \times (9 - 0!) \\ := T(T(2))! + T(T(T(5) - 9)) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0966} := F(F(6) + F(6)) - F(9 - 0!) \\ := T(6) + T(6) \times T(9 + 0)$$

$$\mathbf{0974} := F(4)!! + F(F(7)) + F(9 - 0!) \\ := -T(T(4)) - 7 + T(T(9)) + 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0978} := -8 + F(7 + 9) - 0! \\ := -8 \times 7 + T(T(9)) - 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0984} := 4! \times (8 + F(9) - 0!) \\ := -T(4!/8) + T(T(9)) - 0!$$

$$\mathbf{0986} := -6 \times 8 + T(T(9)) - 0! \\ := (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9 + 0)$$

$$\mathbf{1323} := F(F(3!)) \times (2^{3!} - 1) \\ := T(T(3)) \times (2^{T(3)} - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1324} := F(F(F(4)!))^2 \times 3 + 1 \\ := T(4!) + 2^{T(3+1)}$$

$$\mathbf{1343} := F(3)!/(4! + 3!) - 1 \\ := T(T(3)) \times 4^3 - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1344} := 4! \times (F(4 + 3!) + 1) \\ := (4! + 4!) \times T(T(3) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1364} := (F(4!) + F(6))/F(F(3!) + 1) \\ := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6)) + T(T(3 + 1))$$

$$\mathbf{1365} := 5 \times F(F(6)) \times F(3! + 1) \\ := T(5) \times T(6 + T(3) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1368} := (F(F(8)) + 6)/F(3!) - 1 \\ := 8 \times T(6 \times 3 \times 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1374} := (-4 + F(F(7))) \times 3! \times 1 \\ := -4 + T(T(7) + (3 + 1)!)$$

$$\mathbf{1378} := -F(8) + F(F(7)) \times 3! + 1 \\ := T(8 \times 7 - 3 - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1404} := F(4)! \times (0! + F(F(F(4)! + 1))) \\ := 4 \times T(0! + 4! + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1427} := -F(7) + 2 \times (4 - 1)!! \\ := T(T(7)) + T(T(2))! + T(4!) + 1$$

$$\mathbf{1429} := -9 + 2 \times (F(4)!! - 1) \\ := T(T(9) + 2) + T(4!) + 1$$

$$\mathbf{1432} := 2 \times 3!! - F((4 - 1)!) \\ := 2 \times (T(3)! - 4 \times 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1434} := (-F(4) + 3!!) \times F(4 - 1) \\ := T(4!) + T(T(3)) \times (T(T(4)) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1436} := 6! \times F(3) - 4 \times 1 \\ := 6! + T(3)! - 4 \times 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1444 &:= 3 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! &:= T(T(T(T(7 - 5)))) + T(51) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) - 4! \times 4 \times 1 \\
 1445 &:= 5 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! &:= T(1 \times 6) + T(T(T(5 - 1))) \\
 &:= 5 \times T(4!) - T(T(4 \times 1)) \\
 1446 &:= 6 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! &:= T(2 \times T(7)) - (5 - 1)! \\
 &:= 6 \times (4! \times T(4) + 1) \\
 1449 &:= 9 + F(F(4)) \times (4 - 1)!! &:= T(T(8)/3) \times T(6 \times 1) \\
 &:= (T(9) + 4!) \times T(T(4 - 1)) \\
 1456 &:= (-F(6) + 5!) \times F(F(4)! + 1) &:= T(T(T(4)) + 2) + 71 \\
 &:= T(T(6)) + T(5 \times T(4) - 1) \\
 1457 &:= F(7) \times (5! - F(F(4)!)) + 1 &:= (5 + (4 \times T((T(7) + 1)))) \\
 &:= -T(7) + T(54) \times 1 \\
 1462 &:= 2 \times 6! + F(F(F(4)!)) + 1 &:= F(4)!^{F(4)} \times 9 \times 1 \\
 &:= 2 \times (6! + T(4) + 1) &:= -4! \times (T(4) - 91) \\
 1463 &:= F(3) \times 6! + 4! - 1 &:= T(6)! / (10 \times 2) \\
 &:= T(3)! + 6! + 4! - 1 &:= T(61 + 02) \\
 1464 &:= 4! + 6! \times F(4 - 1) &:= T(7 + T(9)) - 0! + T(T(2))! \\
 &:= 4! \times (6 \times T(4) + 1) &:= F(F(7)) \times (9 + 0 \times 2) \\
 1483 &:= (3!! + F(8)) \times F(F(4)) + 1 &:= (6! - F(3!)) \times (1 + 2) \\
 &:= -T(3)! - 8 + T(T(T(4) + 1)) &:= 6! \times 3 - (1 + T(2))! \\
 1484 &:= F(F(4)) \times (F(8) + F(4)!! + 1) &:= (-5 + F(4)!!) \times (1 + 2) \\
 &:= T(T(4 + 8) - 4!) - 1 &:= T(5! - T((4 + 1) \times 2)) \\
 1542 &:= 2 \times (F(4)!! + 51) &:= -F(7) + F(4) \times ((1 + 2))! \\
 &:= 2 + T(4 + 51) &:= T(T(7 + 4) - 1) + 2 \\
 1547 &:= F(7) \times (4! \times 5 - 1) &:= F(4) \times ((5 + 1)! - 2) \\
 &:= 7 + T(4 + 51) &:= (4! \times T(5) - 1) \times T(T(2)) \\
 1557 &:= F(7) \times 5! - F(5 - 1) &:= F(4) \times (8 + (1 + 2)!!) \\
 & &:= (T(T(4)) + T(8)) \times (1 + T(2))!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2205 &:= 5 \times F(F((0! + 2)!))^2 \\
 &:= (T(T(5) - 0!)) \times T(2 \times T(2)) \\
 2274 &:= F(4)! \times (F(7 \times 2) + 2) \\
 &:= (-4! + T(T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(T(2)) \\
 2312 &:= 2 \times (F(1 + F(3!)))^2 \\
 &:= T(T(2) + 1) \times T(T(T(3))) + 2 \\
 2354 &:= (-F(F(4)!) + 5!) \times F(F(3!)) + 2 \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(5!/3) - T(T(2)) \\
 2373 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (-7 + (3 + 2)!) \\
 &:= T(3)! + T(T(7 + 3) + 2) \\
 2375 &:= (5! - 7) \times F(F(3!)) + 2 \\
 &:= (5! - 7) \times T(T(3)) + 2 \\
 2376 &:= F(6) \times (F(F(7)) + F(3!)^2) \\
 &:= 6 \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(3) - 2)) \\
 2401 &:= (F(10) - F(4)!)^2 \\
 &:= (-T(T(1 + 0!)) + T(T(4)))^2 \\
 2435 &:= 5 \times (3!! - F(F(F(4)!) + F(2))) \\
 &:= -T(5) + T(-T(3) + T(T(4))) \times 2 \\
 2439 &:= F(9 + 3!) \times 4 - F(2) \\
 &:= T(T(9)) \times 3 - T(T(4 \times 2)) \\
 2444 &:= 4 \times (F(F(F(F(4)!) - F(4)!) + F(2)) \\
 &:= (T(4!) - T(T(4))) \times T(4) - T(T(2)) \\
 2447 &:= (7! + F(4!))/F(F(F(4)!) - F(2) \\
 &:= 7 + T(T(T(4))) + T(4!) \times T(2) \\
 2448 &:= (F(8) - 4) \times F(4!/2) \\
 &:= (8 + T(4)) \times T(4^2) \\
 2449 &:= F(9) \times 4! \times F(4) + F(2) \\
 &:= T(9) \times T(T(4)) - 4! - 2 \\
 2456 &:= F(F(6)) \times (5! - F(4)) - F(2) \\
 &:= T(6) \times 5! - 4^{T(2)} \\
 2457 &:= (7! - 5! - F(4)!)/2 \\
 &:= T(7) \times 5! - T(42) \\
 2464 &:= F(4! - 6) - (F(4) + 2)! \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(6) + T(42) \\
 2465 &:= -5! + F(-6 + 4!) + F(2) \\
 &:= T(5) \times T(T(6)) - T(4)^{T(2)} \\
 2484 &:= -4 \times T(8) + T(4! \times T(2)) \\
 &:= F(4)!! + (F(8) \times F(F(4)))^2 \\
 2518 &:= F(8) \times 1 \times 5! - 2 \\
 &:= 8!/(1 + T(5)) - 2 \\
 2519 &:= F(9 - 1) \times 5! - F(2) \\
 &:= -T(T(9) + 1) + 5 \times T(T(2))! \\
 2541 &:= 1 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! + F(2)) \\
 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5 - 2))) \\
 2542 &:= F(2) + F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! + F(2)) \\
 &:= -2 + 4! + 5! \times T(T(T(2))) \\
 2544 &:= 4! + (F(F(4)) + 5)!/2 \\
 &:= (T(4!) + 4 + 5!) \times T(T(2)) \\
 2545 &:= 5! \times F(F(F(4)!)) + 5^2 \\
 &:= -5 + T(T(4) \times 5) \times 2 \\
 2561 &:= -1 + F(F(6)) \times (5! + 2) \\
 &:= -1 + T(6) \times (5! + 2) \\
 2562 &:= F(2 + 6) \times (5! + 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= T(T(2) \times 6) \times T(5) - T(2) \\
 \mathbf{2597} &:= (7! + F(9) + 5!)/2 \\
 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(-T(9) + 5! + 2) \\
 \mathbf{2634} &:= F(4)! \times (-F(3) + F(F(6)))^2 \\
 &:= T(4! \times 3) + T(6/2) \\
 \mathbf{2637} &:= 7 \times F(3! + F(6)) - 2 \\
 &:= (7! + 3 + T(T(6)))/2 \\
 \mathbf{2638} &:= -8 + 3! \times F(F(6))^2 \\
 &:= -8 + T(3) \times T(6)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2643} &:= -3 + F(4)! \times F(F(6))^2 \\
 &:= T(3 \times 4!) + T(6) - T(T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{2645} &:= (5! + F(4)!) \times F(F(6)) - F(2) \\
 &:= 5 \times (T(4!) + T(T(6)) - 2) \\
 \mathbf{2664} &:= (F(4!) - 6! - F(6)!)/2 \\
 &:= 4!/6 \times T(6^2) \\
 \mathbf{2704} &:= (4 \times F(07))^2 \\
 &:= (4! + T(07))^2 \\
 \mathbf{2753} &:= F(F(F(3) + 5)) + 7!/2 \\
 &:= T(3)! + 5 \times T(T(7)) + T(2) \\
 \mathbf{2754} &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times 5! + F(F(7)) + F(2) \\
 &:= T(4) \times T(-5 + T(7)) - T(T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{2844} &:= 4 \times (F(4)!! - 8 - F(2)) \\
 &:= T(T(4!)/4) - 8 + 2 \\
 \mathbf{2846} &:= 6! \times 4 - F(8 + F(2)) \\
 &:= 6! \times 4 - T(8) + 2 \\
 \mathbf{2848} &:= (-8 + F(4)!!) \times 8/2 \\
 &:= -8 + T(4! - 8) \times T(T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2856} &:= F(F(6)) \times (5! + 8 \times 2) \\
 &:= (6 + T(5)) \times T(8 \times 2) \\
 \mathbf{2878} &:= 8!/(-7 + F(8)) - 2 \\
 &:= (8! - T(7))/(8 + T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2905} &:= -5! + F(0! + 9)^2 \\
 &:= -5! + T(0! + 9)^2 \\
 \mathbf{3024} &:= (F(4)^2)!/(-0! + 3)! \\
 &:= 4! \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(03)) \\
 \mathbf{3045} &:= (5! + 4! + 0!) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 &:= T(5 + 4!) \times (0! + T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3165} &:= -5 \times 6! + F(-1 + F(F(3!))) \\
 &:= T(5) \times T(T(6)) - T((1 + 3)!) \\
 \mathbf{3196} &:= (F(F(6) + 9) + 1) \times F(3) \\
 &:= -6! + T(91 - 3) \\
 \mathbf{3249} &:= (F(9) + 4! - F(2))^{F(3)} \\
 &:= (T(9) \times 4! + T(2)) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{3264} &:= 4! \times (-F(6) + F(2 \times 3!)) \\
 &:= 4! \times T(T(6) - 2 - 3) \\
 \mathbf{3276} &:= F(F(6)) \times (F(7) \times 2) \times 3! \\
 &:= T(6 + 7) \times T(2^3) \\
 \mathbf{3297} &:= -7 + F(9 \times 2) + 3!! \\
 &:= (T(7 + 9) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3303} &:= 3!! - 0! + F(3 \times 3!) \\
 &:= T((3 + 0)!) + T(T(T(T(3))))/3 \\
 \mathbf{3304} &:= F(4! - 03!) + 3!! \\
 &:= T(4!) + 0! + T(T(T(T(3))))/3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3325 &:= 5 \times (-F(2 + F(3!)) + 3!!) & := 2 - 5! + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\
 &:= 5 \times (-T(T(-2 + T(3))) + T(3)!) \\
 3327 &:= F(7) \times 2^{F(3!)} - F(F(3)) & := 4 - 5! + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\
 &:= T(T(7) \times T(2)) - 3 + T(3) \\
 3339 &:= 9 \times (-3! + F(3! + F(3!))) & := 6 - 5! + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\
 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(T(3) + T(3))) \times 3 \\
 3344 &:= (F(F(4)!)/4! - F(3!)) \times F(3) & := 7 - 5! + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\
 &:= -4 + T(4! \times 3) + T(3)! \\
 3345 &:= -5! + T(T(4)) \times T(T(3)) \times 3 & := 9!/(5 \times F(F(F(4)!))) + 3 \\
 &:= 5^{F(4)} \times F(F(3!)) + 3!! \\
 3348 &:= (8!/4! - 3!) \times F(3) & := 9 - 5! + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\
 &:= T(8 + 4^3) + T(3)! \\
 3357 &:= -F(F(7)) + 5 \times (-F(3) + 3!!) & := F(2 \times 6) \times 4! + 3! \\
 &:= T(7) \times 5! - T(3) + 3 \\
 &:= T(2) \times T(6) \times T(T(4)) - 3 \\
 3376 &:= (F(6) + 7!/3) \times F(3) & := F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) + F(F(4)) - 3!! \\
 &:= -6! + (7 - 3)^{T(3)} & := -3 - 6! + T(T(T(4) + 3)) \\
 3384 &:= 4! + 8!/(F(3) \times 3!) & := F(4!) - F(6)! - F(4! - 3!) \\
 &:= 4! + 8!/(T(3) + T(3)) & := 4! \times T(T(6)) - T(4^3) \\
 3427 &:= F(F(7)) + 2 \times F(-4 + F(F(3!))) & := -F(6)! + F(F(F(6))) \times 4 + F(3) \\
 &:= 7^{T(2)} \times T(4) - 3 & := -6! + T(T(6 + 4 + 3)) \\
 3437 &:= F(F(7) + 3!) - 4! - 3!! & := F(4) \times F(F(7)) \times F(4)! - 3!! \\
 &:= -T(7) + T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 3 & := T(T(T(4)) + T(7)) - 4 \times 3 \\
 3448 &:= -8 + 4! \times F(4 \times 3) & := -F(F(8))/F(7) + F(4)! \times 3!! \\
 &:= -8 + 4! \times 4! \times T(3) & := -8 + T(T(7) + T(4 + T(3))) \\
 3451 &:= (-1 + 5!) \times (F(F(4)!) + F(F(3!))) & := -F(-6 + F(8)) + 4^{3!} \\
 &:= 1 - 5! + T(4 \times T(T(3))) & := T(6!/8 - 4 - 3) \\
 3452 &:= -2 + 5!^{F(F(4))} - F(F(F(3!))) & := F(F(7)) \times (-9 + 4!) + F(3) \\
 & & := 7! - T(T(9) + T(4)) - 3 \\
 & & := -8! + F(9) + 4 \times F(F(F(3!))) \\
 & & := (8 + T(9)) \times T(-T(4) + T(T(3)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3525 &:= 5^2 \times (5! + F(F(3!))) \\
 &:= 5 \times (-T(2) \times 5 + T(3)!) \\
 3534 &:= F(4)! \times (F(3 \times 5) - F(F(3!))) \\
 &:= (T(4) + T(T(3))) \times (5! - T(3)) \\
 3544 &:= F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 5! \times F(3!) \\
 &:= T(T(4)) + 4! + T(5) \times T(T(T(3))) \\
 3545 &:= 5 \times (-F(4)! - 5 + 3!!) \\
 &:= 5 \times (4 - T(5) + T(3)!) \\
 3549 &:= (-9 + F(4)!!) \times 5 - 3! \\
 &:= (T(9) + 4 + 5!) \times T(T(3)) \\
 3564 &:= F(4)! \times (6! - 5! - 3!) \\
 &:= T(4 \times T(6)) - T(T(5 - 3)) \\
 3565 &:= 5 \times (6! - 5 - F(3)) \\
 &:= -5 + T(6 \times T(5) - T(3)) \\
 3568 &:= (F(8) \times F(F(6)) + 5) \times F(3!) \\
 &:= (-8 + T(T(6))) \times (-5 + T(T(3))) \\
 3573 &:= (3!! - 7) \times 5 + F(3!) \\
 &:= 3 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\
 3584 &:= 4 \times (-8 + 5!) \times F(3!) \\
 &:= 4 \times 8! / (T(5) \times 3) \\
 3594 &:= (-4 + F(9)) \times 5! - 3! \\
 &:= 4! + T((9 + 5) \times T(3)) \\
 3597 &:= -F(F(7) - 9) + 5 \times 3!! \\
 &:= -T(-7 + 9) + 5 \times T(3)! \\
 3605 &:= 5 \times (-0! + 6! + F(3)) \\
 &:= T(5) \times (0! + 6!) / 3 \\
 3624 &:= 4! + (-F(2) + 6) \times 3!! \\
 &:= (T(4!) + 2) \times (6 + T(3)) \\
 3635 &:= 5 \times (3^6 + F(3)) \\
 &:= 5 \times (T(3)! + T(6) / 3) \\
 3642 &:= (F(2) - F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(F(6)))) / 3 \\
 &:= 2 \times (T(4!) \times 6 + T(T(3))) \\
 3643 &:= (-F(F(3!)) + 4 + F(F(F(6)))) / 3 \\
 &:= T(T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) + 6! - 3 \\
 3644 &:= (-F(4)! - F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))) / 3 \\
 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + 4! \times 6^3 \\
 3645 &:= 5 \times F(4)^{(6-3)!} \\
 &:= 5 \times (4! - T(6))^{T(3)} \\
 3646 &:= (F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4)!)) / (6 - 3) \\
 &:= T(T(6) + T(4 + 6)) + T(3)! \\
 3667 &:= 7 + 6 \times F(F(F(6)) - 3!) \\
 &:= T(76) + T(6) + T(3)! \\
 3672 &:= (2 + F(7 + F(6))) \times 3! \\
 &:= (2 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 3) \\
 3675 &:= 5 \times (F(7) + 6! + F(3)) \\
 &:= T(T(5) + T(7) + 6) \times 3 \\
 3699 &:= 9 \times (F(9) + F(F(6) + 3!)) \\
 &:= T(9 \times 9) + T(T(6) + T(3)) \\
 3705 &:= 5 \times ((-0! + 7)! + T(T(3))) \\
 &:= 5 \times (F(0! + 7) + 3!!) \\
 3732 &:= 2 \times (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) + F(3)) \\
 &:= (T(T(2)))^3 + T(T(7)) \times T(3) \\
 3734 &:= 4^{F(3)} \times F(F(7)) + 3!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))) + 7! + 3$$

$$\mathbf{3744} := (4! + 4!) \times F(7) \times 3!$$

$$:= 4! \times (4! + T(7)) \times 3$$

$$\mathbf{3746} := -6^4 + 7! + F(3)$$

$$:= T(T(6)) - T(T(4)) + T(T(7) \times 3)$$

$$\mathbf{3755} := 5^5 + 7!/F(3!)$$

$$:= T(5) + 5 \times (T(7) + T(3)!)$$

$$\mathbf{3765} := (-5! + 6 \times 7!)/F(3!)$$

$$:= T(5) \times T(T(6)) + T((7 - 3)!)$$

$$\mathbf{3774} := F(4)! \times (-7 \times F(7) + 3!)$$

$$:= T(4) \times (-T(7) + T(T(7))) - T(3)$$

$$\mathbf{3784} := F(F(4)!)/F(8) + F(F(7)) \times F(3!)$$

$$:= 4! \times T(T(8) + (7))/T(3)$$

$$\mathbf{3794} := F(F(F(4)!) + 9) + F(7)^3$$

$$:= -T(49) + 7! - T(T(3))$$

$$\mathbf{3834} := F(F(4)) \times F(3)!/F(8) - 3!$$

$$:= (-4! - 3 + T(T(8))) \times T(3)$$

$$\mathbf{3835} := -5 + F(3)!/F(8) \times F(3)$$

$$:= -5! - T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-8 + T(T(3))))$$

$$\mathbf{3844} := 4 + F(F(4)) \times 8!/F(F(3!))$$

$$:= T(T(T(4)) + 4!) - T(8) + T(3)!$$

$$\mathbf{3864} := F(4)!/((-6 + 8) \times 3!)$$

$$:= T(4)!/6! - T(8 \times T(3))$$

$$\mathbf{3882} := 2 \times (8!/F(8) + F(F(3!)))$$

$$:= T(2) \times T(8) \times T(8) - T(3)$$

$$\mathbf{3886} := (6! - 8 + F(F(8)))/3$$

$$:= T(T(6)) + T(88 - 3)$$

$$\mathbf{3944} := F(F(4)!) \times 493$$

$$:= 4 \times (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + T(3))$$

$$\mathbf{3945} := (5! - 4) \times F(9) + F(F(3))$$

$$:= T(5! - 4!) + 9 - T(3)!$$

$$\mathbf{3954} := -F(4)! + 5! \times (F(9) - F(F(3)))$$

$$:= 4! \times (5! + T(9)) - T(3)$$

$$\mathbf{3961} := F(F(1 + 6)) \times F(9)/F(3)$$

$$:= 1 + T(6!/9) + T(3)!$$

$$\mathbf{3963} := 3 + T(6!/9) + T(3)!$$

$$:= F(F(3!)) \times F(F(6)) \times 9 - 3!$$

$$\mathbf{3967} := 7 + T(6!/9) + T(3)!$$

$$:= F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + 9) + 3!$$

$$\mathbf{4032} := 2 \times F(3)!/(-0! + F(F(F(4)!)))$$

$$:= (2^3)!/T(04)$$

$$\mathbf{4059} := F(9) \times 5! - F(F(F(04)!))$$

$$:= 9!/5! + T(T(-0! + T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4072} := 2^{F(7)-0!} - 4!$$

$$:= 2 + (T(T(7)) + 0!) \times T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{4094} := -F(F(4)) + (9 - 0!)^4$$

$$:= T(T(4) \times 9) - (0 \times 4)!$$

$$\mathbf{4204} := 4! - 0! + F(-2 + F(F(F(4)!)))$$

$$:= (T(40) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times 4$$

$$\mathbf{4223} := F(F(F(3!)) - 2) + 2 \times F(F(F(4)!))$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(3)) + 2)/T(2)) - T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4224} := F(F(4)!) \times 22 \times 4!$$

$$:= T(42) + T(T(2)^4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4232 &:= 23^2 \times F(F(4)!) & &:= 7! + 1 - T(3)! - 4 \\
 &:= -T(2) + T(T(T(3)))/T(2) \times T(T(4)) \\
 4236 &:= (F(F(F(6)) - F(3)) + F(2 + F(F(4)!))) & &4331 := (-1 + F(3) + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(6) \times T(3)^{T(2)} - T(4!) & &:= 1 + T(3) \times T(3)! + T(4) \\
 4237 &:= 7 \times F(3!) + F(-2 + F(F(F(4)!))) & &4332 := (2 + 3!!) \times (3 + F(4)) \\
 &:= -T(7) + T(3)! \times T(T(2)) - T(T(4)) & &:= 2 + T(3) \times T(3)! + T(4) \\
 4244 &:= F(4) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + F(-2 + F(F(F(4)!))) & &4333 := 3! \times 3!! + F(3 + 4) \\
 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + (T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 4! & &:= 3 + T(3) \times T(3)! + T(4) \\
 4245 &:= F(-5 + 4!) + 2^{F(4)!} & &4334 := (F(F(4)) + 3!!) \times 3! + F(F(4)) \\
 &:= T(5) \times (T(4!) + T(2)) - T(4!) & &:= 4 + T(3) \times T(3)! + T(4) \\
 4248 &:= 8 \times F(F(F(4)!))^2 + F(4)!! & &4335 := (5 + 3!! + 3!!) \times F(4) \\
 &:= (T(8 + T(4)) + T(T(2))) \times 4! & &:= 5 + T(3) \times T(3)! + T(4) \\
 4266 &:= (6! - F(6) - F(2)) \times F(4)! & &4336 := (6! + F(3)) \times 3! + 4 \\
 &:= (-6 - T(T(6))) \times (T(T(2)) - 4!) & &:= 6 + T(3) \times T(3)! + T(4) \\
 4272 &:= F(-2 + F(7)) \times 2 \times 4! & &4337 := F(7) + 3!! \times 3! + 4 \\
 &:= 2 \times T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)) - T(4!) & &:= 7 + T(3) \times T(3)! + T(4) \\
 4284 &:= F(4)! \times ((8 - 2)! - F(4)!) & &4338 := (F(8/F(3)) + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= (T(-T(4)) + T(8)) + T(T(2)!) \times 4 & &:= 8 + T(3) \times T(3)! + T(4) \\
 4293 &:= 3 \times (-9 + 2 \times (F(4)!))! & &4343 := 3!! \times F(4)! - F(F(3)) + 4! \\
 &:= 3 \times T(T(9)) + 2 \times 4 & &:= (T(T(T(3))) - 4!) \times T(T(3)) - 4 \\
 4302 &:= (-2 - 0! + 3!!) \times F(4)! & &4344 := (4 + (F(4) \times F(3))!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times (0! + T(3)! - 4) & &:= (T(4) + T(4! - T(3))) \times 4! \\
 4306 &:= -F(6) + (-0! + 3!!) \times F(4)! & &4347 := 7! + F(4) - 3!! + 4! \\
 &:= (6 - 0!)! + T(T(3 + T(4))) & &:= T((7 + 4!) \times 3) - 4! \\
 4314 &:= F(4)! \times 1 \times 3!! - F(4)! & &4348 := (-8 + F(4)! + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= 4! \times (-1 + T(3)!)/4 & &:= (T(T(8) + T(4)) + T(3)) \times 4 \\
 4317 &:= (7 - 1)! \times 3! - F(4) & &4352 := 2 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 & & &:= 2^5 \times T(T(3) + T(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4355 &:= 5 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(5 + T(5)) \times T(T(3)) - T(T(4)) \\
 4357 &:= 7 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(T(T(7) - T(5))) + T(-T(3) + 4!) \\
 4362 &:= (F(2) + 6! + 3!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= (T(2) + 6!) \times T(3) + 4! \\
 4366 &:= (6! + 6) \times T(3) + T(4) \\
 &:= (F(6) + 6!) \times 3! - F(F(4)) \\
 4367 &:= -7 + 6 \times 3^{F(4)!} \\
 &:= -T(T(7) - 6) + 3 \times T(T(T(4))) \\
 4368 &:= (8 + 6!) \times F(3) \times F(4) \\
 &:= 8!/6! \times T(3 \times 4) \\
 4379 &:= 9 \times (-F(F(7)) + 3!!) - 4 \\
 &:= (-9 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(4) \\
 4383 &:= (3!! + F(8) + 3!!) \times F(4) \\
 &:= (T(T(T(3))) - 8) \times T(T(3)) - T(4!) \\
 4384 &:= F(F(4)!) \times 8 + 3!! \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(4) - T(T(8)) + (3 + 4)! \\
 4386 &:= (6! + 8 + 3) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(6!/T(8)) \times T(T(3)) - 4! \\
 4396 &:= F(6)!/9 - F(F(3!)) \times 4 \\
 &:= T(6) + T(93) + 4 \\
 4416 &:= F(6) \times (-1 + 4!) \times 4! \\
 &:= (6! - 1) \times 4 + T(T(T(4))) \\
 4424 &:= F(4!) \times 2/F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(4)!) \\
 &:= 4 \times T(T(2))! + 4 + T(T(T(4))) \\
 4432 &:= 2 \times (F(3!) + F(4!)/F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 &:= (T(2) + T(3)!) \times 4 + T(T(T(4))) \\
 4434 &:= (-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!)) + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= 4! + T(T(3)) \times T(4! - 4) \\
 4437 &:= F(F(7) + 3!) + 4^4 \\
 &:= 7! - 3 - T(4!) - T(4!) \\
 4443 &:= (F(F(3!)) + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! - F(4) \\
 &:= 3 \times (T(T(T(4)))) - 4 - T(T(4)) \\
 4445 &:= 5^{F(4)} + F(4)! \times F(4)!! \\
 &:= (5 + T(4)) \times T(4!) - T(T(4)) \\
 4446 &:= (6! + F(4 + 4)) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= 6 \times T(4! - T(4) + 4!) \\
 4448 &:= (F(8) + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! + F(F(4)) \\
 &:= 8 \times (T(4!) + 4^4) \\
 4462 &:= -2 + (6! + 4!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= -T(2) + T(T(6) \times 4 + T(4)) \\
 4466 &:= 6 \times (6! + 4!) + F(F(4)) \\
 &:= T(T(6))/T(6) \times T(4! + 4) \\
 4467 &:= -F(7) + F(6)!/(F(4) \times F(4)) \\
 &:= 7 \times T(T(6)) + T(T(4!)/4) \\
 4474 &:= F(F(4)!)!/(F(7) - 4) - F(4)! \\
 &:= T(4) + 7! - 4! \times 4! \\
 4476 &:= F(6)!/(F(7) - 4) - 4 \\
 &:= T(T(6 + 7)) - T(4) + T(4!) \\
 4483 &:= 3 + 8!/(F(4) \times F(4)) \\
 &:= -3 + T(T(8) + T(T(4))) + T(4!) \\
 4485 &:= 5 + 8!/(F(4) \times F(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(4!/4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4488} := 8 + 8!/(F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$:= 8 \times T(T(8)/4 + 4!)$$

$$\mathbf{4489} := 9 + 8!/(F(4) \times F(4))$$

$$:= (T((98 - 4)) + (4)!)$$

$$\mathbf{4496} := F(6)!/9 + 4 \times 4$$

$$:= T(6) + T(94) + T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{4498} := 8!/9 - F(4)! + 4!$$

$$:= 8 \times T(9 + 4!) + T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{4567} := -F(F(7)) + (6! - 5!) \times F(F(4)!)$$

$$:= 7 + T(6! - 5^4)$$

$$\mathbf{4574} := -F(F(4)) \times F(F(7)) + (5 + F(F(4)))!$$

$$:= -4 + T(-T(7) + 5!) + T(4!)$$

$$\mathbf{4578} := F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - 5 \times F(4))$$

$$:= T(87 + 5) + T(4!)$$

$$\mathbf{4594} := F(F(4)!)/9 + 5! - F(4)!$$

$$:= T(4) + T(95) + 4!$$

$$\mathbf{4596} := (-6 + T(T(9)) + 5!) \times 4$$

$$:= F(6)!/9 + 5! - 4$$

$$\mathbf{4599} := (99 + 5!) \times F(F(F(4)!))$$

$$:= 99 + T(5) \times T(4!)$$

$$\mathbf{4608} := (8 + 0!) \times F(6)^{F(4)}$$

$$:= (8!/T(-0! + T(6))) \times 4!$$

$$\mathbf{4634} := F(F(4)) \times (3!! + F(F(F(6)) - 4))$$

$$:= (T(4!) - T(3)) \times T(6) - T(T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4644} := 4 \times (F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{F(F(4))})$$

$$:= T(T(4)) \times (4 \times T(6)) + 4!$$

$$\mathbf{4656} := (6! + 56) \times F(4)!$$

$$:= (6! + T(T(4))) \times 6 - 4$$

$$\mathbf{4657} := F(F(7)) \times 5!/6 - F(4)$$

$$:= 7 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{4658} := -F(F(8)) + 5^6 - F(F(F(4)!))$$

$$:= 8 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{4674} := -F(4)! + F(7) \times 6!/F(F(4))$$

$$:= -T(4!) + 7! - T(T(6) - T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4676} := (6! \times F(7) - F(6))/F(F(4))$$

$$:= T(6) + 7 \times (6! - T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4687} := 7! - F(8 + 6) + 4!$$

$$:= 7 \times T(T(8)) + T(6) + 4$$

$$\mathbf{4688} := 8 \times (F(F(8)) - 6) - 4!$$

$$:= 8 - (T(8) - T(T(6))) \times 4!$$

$$\mathbf{4689} := 9 \times F(8) \times F(F(6)) + F(4)!!$$

$$:= 9 - (T(8) - T(T(6))) \times 4!$$

$$\mathbf{4697} := 7! + (F(9) - 6!)/F(F(4))$$

$$:= 7 \times (-T(9) + 6! - 4)$$

$$\mathbf{4725} := F(F((5 - 2)!)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(4)!))$$

$$:= -T(5^2) + 7! + T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{4727} := 7! - F(2) - F(7) \times 4!$$

$$:= 7! - T(T(2)) - 7 - T(4!)$$

$$\mathbf{4728} := (8 - F(2))! - F(7) \times 4!$$

$$:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(2))) \times 7 + 4!$$

$$\mathbf{4735} := 5 \times (3!! + F(F(7)) - F(4)!)$$

$$:= -T(5) \times T(T(3)) + 7! + T(4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4736 &:= F(6)^{F(3)} \times 74 & &:= T(T(2)) + T(8) + 7! - T(4!) \\
 &:= 6! \times T(3) + T(T(7)) + T(4) \\
 4743 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (-F(4)! + F(F(7))) - 4! & &:= -T(T(T(3))) - T(8) + 7! - T(4) \\
 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T(-7 + 4!) \\
 4744 &:= (F(4)!/F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)!) & &:= T(98) - 7 - T(T(4)) \\
 &:= 4 - T(4!) + (T(7)/4)! \\
 4745 &:= 5 \times (-4 + F(F(7)) + F(4)!) & &:= 4! + T(9) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4!)) \\
 &:= -5 - T(4!) + 7! + T(4) \\
 4749 &:= 9! - F(F(4)!) - F(7 \times 4) & &:= -T(6) \times 9 + 7! - T(T(4)) \\
 &:= 9 - T(4!) + (T(7)/4)! \\
 4753 &:= -3!! + F(F(-5 + F(7)))/F(F(4)) & &:= 7! + 9 \times (T(7) - T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(3 \times T(5)) + T(7) + 4! \\
 4763 &:= F(F(3!)) \times (-6 + F(F(7))) - 4 & &:= (F(F(7)) - 2) \times F(8) - 4! \\
 &:= T(T(3)) + T(6 + 7) + T(4) \\
 4764 &:= F(4)! \times (6! + 74) & &:= 7 \times (3!! - F(8) - F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= -T(4 \times 6) + 7! + 4! & &:= 7 \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) + 4) \\
 4765 &:= 5! \times (6! + F(F(7)))/4! & &:= 4845 := F(5 \times 4) - 8!/F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= T(T(5 + 6)) + T(7) + T(4!) & &:= T(5 \times T(4)) + T(84) \\
 4767 &:= 7 \times (6! - F(7) \times F(4)) & &:= 4848 := -8 \times 4! + (F(8)/F(4))! \\
 &:= 7! + T(T(6)) - 7!/T(4) & &:= (T(8) + T(48)) \times 4 \\
 4773 &:= 3!! + 7! - F(F(7) + F(4)) & &:= 4857 := 7! - 5! - F(8) \times F(4) \\
 &:= T(3)! - 7 + T(T(7)) \times T(4) & &:= 7! - 5! - 8 - T(T(4)) \\
 4778 &:= -F(8) - F(F(7)) + 7! - F(F(4)!) & &:= 4859 := -F(9) + F(5 + 8) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 &:= -T(8) \times 7 + 7! - T(4) & &:= 9 \times (-5! + T(T(8))) - T(T(4)) \\
 4779 &:= -F(9) - F(F(7)) + 7! + F(4)! & &:= 4875 := -5! + 7! - F(8) - 4! \\
 &:= 9 \times (T(-7 + T(7)) + T(4!)) & &:= T(5) \times T(-7 + 8 \times 4) \\
 4782 &:= -2^8 + 7! - F(F(4)) & &:= 4882 := 2 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!) \\
 & & &:= -T(T(2)) + 8 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4884 &:= 4 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!) \\
 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - 4 \\
 4886 &:= 6 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!) \\
 &:= 6! \times 8 + T(T(8)) - T(T(T(4))) \\
 4887 &:= 7 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!) \\
 &:= 7! - T(8 + T(8)/4) \\
 4888 &:= 8 + 8 \times F(F(8) - F(4)!) \\
 &:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(8 - 4))) \\
 4896 &:= 6 \times F(9) \times (8 - 4)! \\
 &:= T(6) + T(98) + 4! \\
 4897 &:= 7! - F(-9 + F(8)) + F(F(F(4))) \\
 &:= 7! - T(9 + 8) + T(4) \\
 4904 &:= (F(4)! + 0!)! - F(9) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 \times (0! + T(T(9) + 4)) \\
 4914 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (1 + F(9 + 4)) \\
 &:= (T(T(4)) - 1) \times T(9 + 4) \\
 4927 &:= 7! - F(2 + 9) - 4! \\
 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(2) + 9) + T(T(4)) \\
 4937 &:= 7! - F(F(3)) - F(9) \times F(4) \\
 &:= 7! - 3 - T(9) - T(T(4)) \\
 4944 &:= 4! \times (F(4)! \times F(9) + F(F(4))) \\
 &:= 4! \times (4! \times 9 - T(4)) \\
 4947 &:= 7! + (F(4) - F(9)) \times F(4) \\
 &:= 7! - 4! - T(9) - 4! \\
 4957 &:= 7! - 5! + F(9) + F(4) \\
 &:= 7 + T(5 + 94) \\
 4968 &:= 8 \times (6! - 9) - F(4)!! \\
 &:= (T(8) \times 6 - 9) \times 4! \\
 4971 &:= -1 + 7! - F(9) \times F(F(4)) \\
 &:= 1 \times 7! - T(9) - 4! \\
 4972 &:= F(2) \times 7! - F(9) \times F(F(4)) \\
 &:= T(T(2))! + (T(7) + T(T(9))) \times 4 \\
 4973 &:= F(F(3)) + 7! - F(9) \times F(F(4)) \\
 &:= -3 + 7! - 9 - T(T(4)) \\
 4974 &:= F(4)! \times (F(7) + F(9) \times 4!) \\
 &:= T((4 + 7) \times 9) + 4! \\
 4975 &:= -5! + 7! + F(F(9) - 4!) \\
 &:= -5! + 7! + T(9) + T(4) \\
 4976 &:= -6 + 7! - F(9) - 4! \\
 &:= 6! \times 7 - 9 - T(T(4)) \\
 4977 &:= 7! + (F(7) - F(9)) \times F(4) \\
 &:= 7! + T(7) - T(9 + 4) \\
 5027 &:= 7! - F(2 + 05) \\
 &:= 7! + 2 - T(05) \\
 5032 &:= (F(2) + 3!)! - F(0! + 5) \\
 &:= -T(2) + (T(3) + 0!)! - 5 \\
 5035 &:= -5 + (F(3) - 0 + 5)! \\
 &:= -5 + (T(3) + (0 \times 5)!)! \\
 5036 &:= F(6)!/F(3!) + 0! - 5 \\
 &:= (T(6)/3)! + 0! - 5 \\
 5061 &:= (1 + 6)! + F(F(0! + 5)) \\
 &:= (1 + 6)! + T(0! + 5) \\
 5066 &:= F(F(6)) + (F(6) - 0!)! + 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(6) + (6 + 0!) + 5$$

$$\mathbf{5067} := 7! + F(F(6)) + 0! + 5$$

$$:= 7! + T(6) + 0! + 5$$

$$\mathbf{5079} := F(9) + 7! + 05$$

$$:= T(9) + 7! - 0! - 5$$

$$\mathbf{5082} := 2 \times F(8) \times (0! + 5!)$$

$$:= (T(T(2)) + T(8)) \times (0! + 5!)$$

$$\mathbf{5272} := -F(2) + F(F(7)) + (2 + 5)!$$

$$:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(7)) \times (-2 + T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5273} := F(3! + 7) + (2 + 5)!$$

$$:= T(T(T(3))) + 7! - T(2) + 5$$

$$\mathbf{5274} := -F(4)! + 7! + 2 \times 5!$$

$$:= (T(4!) - 7) \times (T(2) + T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5337} := 7! - 3 \times F(F(3!)) - 5!$$

$$:= 7! - 3 \times (T(T(3)) - 5!)$$

$$\mathbf{5395} := (5! \times 9 - F(F(3))) \times 5$$

$$:= -5 + T(9) \times T(3 \times 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5409} := 9 + T(-0! + T(4)) \times 5!$$

$$:= 9 \times (0! + F(4)!! - 5!)$$

$$\mathbf{5433} := 3 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) + 5!$$

$$:= F(F(F(3!)))/F(3) - F(F(4)!) \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{5443} := (T(T(T(3))) - 4) \times 4! - 5$$

$$:= F(F(F(3!)))/F(F(4)) - F(4)! \times 5$$

$$\mathbf{5448} := -8! - F(4)!! + F(4!) + 5!$$

$$:= 8 \times T(T(4 + 4)) + 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5472} := F(F(2) \times F(7)) \times 4! - 5!$$

$$:= -T(2) + 7! + T(4! + 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5473} := F(3 \times 7)/(-F(4) + 5)$$

$$:= T(3)! + T(T(7) \times 4 - T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5484} := F(4)! + F(F(8))/F(F(4)) + 5$$

$$:= T(4!) + T(8) \times (4! + 5!)$$

$$\mathbf{5487} := -F(F(7)) + 8 \times (F(4)!! - 5)$$

$$:= 7 \times T(T(8)) + T(T(4)) \times T(5)$$

$$\mathbf{5535} := (5! + F(F(F(3!))) - 5) \times 5$$

$$:= -T(5) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 5! \times 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5544} := F(F(F(4)!)) \times (4! + 5! + 5!)$$

$$:= 4! \times T(-4 + 5 \times 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5597} := F(F(7)) \times (9 - 5)! + 5$$

$$:= -T(7) + T(9) \times (5 + 5!)$$

$$\mathbf{5634} := -F(4)! + F(3!) \times 6! - 5!$$

$$:= T(4!) \times T(T(3)) - T(T(6) + T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5643} := 3 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5!$$

$$:= -T(T(3)) + 4! \times T(T(6)) + 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5646} := 6 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5!$$

$$:= 6! - 4! + T(-T(6) + 5!)$$

$$\mathbf{5664} := (F(4) + 6!) \times F(6) - 5!$$

$$:= 4 \times 6 \times T(T(6)) + 5!$$

$$\mathbf{5673} := F(F(F(3!))) - 7! - F(F(6) + 5)$$

$$:= 3 \times T(76 - T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5697} := F(F(7)) \times 9 + 6! \times 5$$

$$:= 7! - 9 + T(T(6) + T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5733} := 3!! + F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7)) + 5!$$

$$:= 3 \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(7) - T(5))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5736 &:= (6! - 3) \times (F(7) - 5) &:= T(4!) \times T(T(T(2))) + 3 + T(6) \\ &:= (6! - 3) \times (-7 + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5738 &:= F(8)^{F(3)} \times F(7) + 5 &6336 &:= 6^{3!} - (F(3) + 6)! \\ &:= 8 \times T(3)! - 7 - T(5) &&:= T(63) + T(3) \times 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5747 &:= -F(7) + F(4)!! \times (F(7) - 5) &6384 &:= 4!!/F(8)! - F(3!) \times 6! \\ &:= -T(7) + T(T(4)) \times 7 \times T(5) &&:= (4 + T(8 \times 3)) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5773 &:= F(F(F(3!))) - 7! - F(7) - 5! &6426 &:= ((F(6) - F(2))! + F(4!))/F(6) \\ &:= T(3)! + 7! + T(7) - T(5) &&:= (6 + T(24)) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5783 &:= -3 + F(F(8)) - 7! + 5! &6435 &:= (5! - 3) \times F(4 + 6) \\ &:= T(3)! + 8 + 7! + T(5) &&:= (5! - 3) \times T(4 + 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5784 &:= F(4!)/8 - 7 - 5 &6444 &:= F(4) \times F(4) \times (-4 + 6!) \\ &:= 4! \times T(8) + 7! - 5! &&:= -4! + (4 + 4!) \times T(T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5786 &:= 6! + F(8) + 7! + 5 &6447 &:= (7! + F(4!))/F(F(4)!) + F(F(6)) \\ &:= T(6) + 8!/7 - 5 &&:= (T(7)/4 + T(4!)) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5994 &:= F(4!) \times 9 \times (-9 + 5!) &6459 &:= 9 \times 5! \times F(4)! - F(F(6)) \\ &:= T(4 \times 9) \times T(9)/5 &&:= T(9) \times (5! + 4!) - T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6024 &:= -F(4)!! + F(20) - F(F(6)) &6469 &:= 9 \times 6! + T(4) - T(6) \\ &:= 4! \times (-2 + T(0! + T(6))) &&:= 9 \times 6! - F(4) - F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6027 &:= 7! + F(2 \times F(06)) &6473 &:= 3!! - 7 + F(4)!! \times F(6) \\ &:= 7 \times T(20 + T(6)) &&:= -T(3)! - 7 + T(4) \times 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6069 &:= 9!/60 + F(F(6)) &6496 &:= 6! \times 9 + 4! - F(6) \\ &:= 9!/60 + T(6) &&:= 6! \times 9 + T(4) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6174 &:= (T(4!) - 7 + 1) \times T(6) &6497 &:= F(F(7)) + 9 \times (-4! + 6!) \\ &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(7) + 1) \times F(F(6)) &&:= 7 \times (T(T(9)) - 4) - 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6264 &:= (-4! + 6!) \times (F(2) + F(6)) &6525 &:= -5! \times 2 + F(5!/6) \\ &:= 4! \times (6!/T(2) + T(6)) &&:= T(5) \times (T(T(2) + 5 + T(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6324 &:= -F(F(F(4)!))^2 + F(-F(F(3))) + F(F(6)) &6549 &:= -9 \times 4! + F(5!/6) \\ &&&:= -T(9) + T(T(4)) \times 5! - 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6594 &:= F(4)!! \times 9 + 5! - 6 \\
 &:= (T(4) + T(9)) \times 5! - 6 \\
 6642 &:= F(2^4) \times 6 + 6! \\
 &:= 2 \times T(T(4) \times 6 + T(6)) \\
 6644 &:= F(4)! \times (F(4) - 6!) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 &:= T(4) \times (-T(T(4)) + 6!) - 6 \\
 6648 &:= (F(8) + F(4)!!) \times F(6) + 6! \\
 &:= T(T(8)) \times T(4) - 6 - 6 \\
 6699 &:= 9! / (9 \times 6) - F(F(6)) \\
 &:= 9! / (9 \times 6) - T(6) \\
 6721 &:= 1 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6 \\
 &:= T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(7) \times T(T(6)) \\
 6726 &:= 6 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6 \\
 &:= 6! / T(2) \times T(7) + 6 \\
 6727 &:= 7 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6 \\
 &:= T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(7) \times T(T(6)) \\
 6728 &:= 8 + (F(2) + 7)! / 6 \\
 &:= 8 \times (T(T(2)) + 7!) / 6 \\
 6834 &:= -F(4)! + (3!! + 8!) / 6 \\
 &:= T(4) \times (T(3)! - T(8)) - 6 \\
 6867 &:= 7 \times F(F(6)) + 8! / 6 \\
 &:= 7 \times T(6) + 8! / 6 \\
 7056 &:= F(6)! / 5! \times F(0! + 7) \\
 &:= T(6! / T(5)) \times (-0! + 7) \\
 7227 &:= 7! + (T(T(2)) / 2)^7 \\
 &:= 7! + F(2 + 2)^7 \\
 7237 &:= F(7)^3 \times F(2) + 7! \\
 &:= (7 + T(3))^{T(2)} + 7! \\
 7344 &:= (4! + 4!)^{F(3)} + 7! \\
 &:= 4! \times (-T(4!) / 3 + T(T(7))) \\
 7353 &:= F(F(F(3!))) - 5 \times 3!! + 7 \\
 &:= 3 \times (T(5) + T(3) \times T(T(7))) \\
 7413 &:= F(F(3!)) \times ((1 + 4)! + F(F(7))) \\
 &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(1 + 4!) + T(7)) \\
 7455 &:= (5! - 5) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + 7! \\
 &:= T(5) / 5 \times T(T(4) \times 7) \\
 7456 &:= (F(6) + 5!) / 4 \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= (6! - T(5)) \times T(4) + T(T(7)) \\
 7472 &:= 2^{F(7)} - (-4 + 7)!! \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)) - 4 + 7! \\
 7476 &:= F(F(6)) \times (7^{F(4)} + F(7)) \\
 &:= 6 \times T(7 \times 4) + 7! \\
 7495 &:= F((-5 + 9)! / F(4)! - F(F(7))) \\
 &:= -5! + T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4))) + 7! \\
 7584 &:= 4! + F(8) \times 5! + 7! \\
 &:= 4 \times T(T(8)) - 5! + 7! \\
 7644 &:= (4! + 4) \times F(F(6)) \times F(7) \\
 &:= T(4! + 4!) + T(T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 7689 &:= (F(9) - F(8 - 6)) \times F(F(7)) \\
 &:= T(9 \times 8) + T(6) + 7! \\
 7728 &:= F(8) \times 2^7 + 7! \\
 &:= T(8 \times 2 + 7) \times T(7) \\
 7874 &:= (4! + 7) \times (F(8) + F(F(7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -T(T(T(4))) + 7! - T(T(8)) + 7! \\
 \mathbf{7937} & := 7 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7) \\
 & := -T(7) + T(3!) + T(T(9)) \times 7 \\
 \mathbf{7942} & := -F(2) + F(F(F(4)!)) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\
 & := (-2 + 4!) \times (-T(9) + T(T(7))) \\
 \mathbf{7993} & := F(F(3!))! / (9 + 9)! + F(7) \\
 & := T(T(3)! / 9) + T(97) \\
 \mathbf{8344} & := F(F(4) \times F(4)!) + 3!! \times 8 \\
 & := 4! + 4 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{8396} & := F(F(F(6))) + F(9) - F(-3 + F(8)) \\
 & := 6! / 9 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{8447} & := -7! / F(F(4)) + F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) \\
 & := T(7) \times T(4!) + T(T(4)) - 8 \\
 \mathbf{8694} & := F(4!) \times 9 / (6 \times 8) \\
 & := (4 + 9) \times 6! - T(T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{8784} & := F(4)!! + 8! / (F(7) - 8) \\
 & := (T(4!) - 8 \times 7) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{8786} & := -6! \times F(8) / 7 + F(F(8)) \\
 & := 6! / T(8) \times T(T(7)) + T(T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{8856} & := 6 \times (5 + T(8)) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(6) \times (5! + F(8 + 8)) \\
 \mathbf{8968} & := (8! + F(6)!) / 9 + 8 \\
 & := (86 + T(T(9))) \times 8 \\
 \mathbf{8972} & := -2 \times F(7 + 9) + F(F(8)) \\
 & := T(T(2))! - T(7) + T(T(9)) \times 8 \\
 \mathbf{9333} & := F(F(3!))³ + F(3!) \times 9 \\
 & := 3 \times (T(3) + 3 \times T(T(9))) \\
 \mathbf{9384} & := F(4!) / (F(8) \times F(3!)) \times F(9) \\
 & := -4! + 8 \times T(3 + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{9407} & := F(7) \times (0! + F(4)!!) + F(9) \\
 & := T(7) \times (-0! + T(4!)) + T(T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{9454} & := -F(F(F(F(4)!))) + (-5! + F(4)!!) \times F(9) \\
 & := 4 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{9474} & := -F(4) + F(7) \times (F(4)!! + 9) \\
 & := 4! + 7! / 4! \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{9657} & := (F(F(7)) + 5! + 6!) \times 9 \\
 & := 7! / 5! \times T(T(6)) - T(9) \\
 \mathbf{9667} & := F(7) \times (6! + F(F(6))) + F(9) \\
 & := T(T(7)) + T(6)⁻⁶⁺⁹ \\
 \mathbf{9672} & := 2 \times (7! - 6 \times F(9)) \\
 & := (T(2) - T(T(7))) \times (T(6) - T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{9724} & := (4! - 2) \times F(7) \times F(9) \\
 & := (T(T(T(4))) - T(2)) \times 7 - T(T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{9744} & := (F(4!) + F(4!) - 7!) / 9 \\
 & := 4! \times T(T(4! + T(7) - T(9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

2.3 With Square-Root

In this subsection, we shall bring **selfie numbers written in terms of Fibonacci sequence and Triangular numbers** at the same time. The numbers are with used of **basic operations and square-root**. Again, the work is divided in two subsections, one in digit's order and another in reverse order of digits.

2.3.1 Digit's Order

$$\begin{aligned}
 84 &:= F(8) \times 4 & := 1 + (-3 + T(T(6))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times 4 \\
 189 &:= 1 \times F(8) \times 9 & := (-1 + T(T(T(3))) + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \\
 &:= (1 + 8) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 378 &:= F(F(3)) + F(-7 + F(8)) & := 1 + T((5 + \sqrt{9}) \times 7) \\
 &:= T(T(T(3)) + \sqrt{T(7) + 8}) \\
 379 &:= F(F(3) \times 7) + F(\sqrt{9}) & := -T(T(-1 + 5)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(8) \\
 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(7)) - T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 486 &:= \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 6 & := T(1 + T(T(-5 + 9))) + \sqrt{9} \\
 &:= \sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^8} \times 6 \\
 699 &:= F(F(F(F(6))/\sqrt{9})) \times \sqrt{9} & := (-1 + F(7))^{F(\sqrt{2 \times 8})} \\
 &:= T(T(6)) \times \sqrt{9} + T(\sqrt{9}) & := (-1 + 7^2) \times T(8) \\
 966 &:= F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6)) - F(F(6)) & := -1 + 8 \times (-\sqrt{4} + F(F(7))) \\
 &:= T(9) \times T(6) + T(6) & := T(T(1 + 8)) + \sqrt{4} \times T(T(7)) \\
 987 &:= F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times (F(8) - F(7))) & := F(1 \times 8) \times F(F(6) + \sqrt{9}) \\
 &:= -T(T(\sqrt{9})) + (T(8) \times T(7)) & := 1 \times 8 \times T(T(6)) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 996 &:= (9 + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) & := F(1 + F(8) - 8) \times 5 \\
 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 6 & := (-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 5 \\
 1294 &:= F(12) \times 9 - \sqrt{4} & := F(1 \times 8) \times 90 \\
 &:= -1 \times 2 + T(\sqrt{9})^4 & := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9 + 0} \\
 1296 &:= F(12) \times (\sqrt{9} + 6) & := (-1 + 8 \times F(9)) \times 7 \\
 &:= T(1 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 6 & := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 7 \\
 1369 &:= (1 + 36)^{F(\sqrt{9})} & := F(1 \times 9 + 7) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 & & := T(T(\sqrt{1 \times 9})) + T(7 + T(T(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2589 &:= \sqrt{25} + F(F(8) - \sqrt{9}) \\ &:= T(2) \times T(5 + T(8)) + T(\sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3969 &:= (\sqrt{3 \times \sqrt{9} \times F(F(6))})^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\ &:= T(T(3)) \times \sqrt{9} \times T(6) \times \sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2594 &:= 2 \times 5 + F(9 \times \sqrt{4}) \\ &:= T(T(2))^5 / \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4179 &:= F(\sqrt{4} + 17) - F(\sqrt{9}) \\ &:= -T(T(\sqrt{4})) - 1 + T(T(7 + T(\sqrt{9}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2645 &:= (2 + F(F(6)))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \\ &:= (2 + T(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4182 &:= (F(\sqrt{4}) + F((18 + F(2)))) \\ &:= T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(1 + T(8)) - T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2646 &:= F(2 + 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 6 \\ &:= T(2) \times T(6) \times \sqrt{4} \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4184 &:= F(4) + F(F(1 \times 8) - \sqrt{4}) \\ &:= -\sqrt{4} + T(T(1 + 8 + 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2796 &:= F(F(2) \times F(7)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \times 6 \\ &:= T(2 + T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4197 &:= F(4) + F(19) + F(7) \\ &:= T(4) + 1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}) + 7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2797 &:= F(2 + F(7)) + \sqrt{9^7} \\ &:= T(2 + T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4373 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + 3^7 \times F(3) \\ &:= \sqrt{4} + T((3 + T(7)) \times 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2962 &:= F(2) + \sqrt{9} \times F(F(6) \times 2) \\ &:= T(-2 + T(9)) + T(T(6) \times T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4394 &:= (T(4) + 3)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \\ &:= F(4 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2964 &:= (F(2) + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times F(4) \\ &:= (-T(2) + T(9 \times 6)) \times \sqrt{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4647 &:= F(-\sqrt{4} + F(F(6))) + \sqrt{4} \times F(F(7)) \\ &:= T(T(-T(4) + T(6))) + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3364 &:= (3 + F(F(3) + F(6)))^{\sqrt{4}} \\ &:= T(33) \times 6 - \sqrt{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4768 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times F(8) \\ &:= -T(T(4)) - T(7) + T(T(6)) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3384 &:= (3 + F(-F(F(3)) + F(8))) / \sqrt{4} \\ &:= T(3) \times (T(-3 + T(8)) + T(\sqrt{4})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4860 &:= \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 60 \\ &:= \sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^8} \times 60 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3669 &:= F(-F(3) + F(F(6))) - F(6)^{\sqrt{9}} \\ &:= T(36) + T(T(T(6)) / \sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4864 &:= \sqrt{4^8} \times (F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4}) \\ &:= \sqrt{4^8} \times (T(6) - \sqrt{4}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3944 &:= (-F(F(3)) + F(F(\sqrt{9}^4))) \times 4 \\ &:= (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4872 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2)) \\ &:= T(\sqrt{4}) \times 8 \times T(T(7)) / 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4873 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(F(3))) \\ &:= (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(8) \times T(T(7)))/3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5825 &:= F(5 + 8) \times 25 \\ &:= 5 \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 2) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4874 &:= \sqrt{4} + F(8) \times (F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{4})) \\ &:= \sqrt{4} \times (T(8) + 7^4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6939 &:= 6 \times F(9)^{F(3)} + \sqrt{9} \\ &:= 6 \times T(T(9)) + 3^{T(\sqrt{9})} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4878 &:= -\sqrt{4} + 8 \times F(7 + 8) \\ &:= (4 + 8) \times T(T(7)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6942 &:= 6 \times (F(9)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(2)) \\ &:= 6 \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(4)) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4879 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + 8 \times F(F(7) + F(\sqrt{9})) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) - \sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(7)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7448 &:= (F(F(7)) \times 4 - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 8 \\ &:= T(7) \times (T(4) + \sqrt{4^8}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4887 &:= \sqrt{4} - 8 + F(8) \times F(F(7)) \\ &:= -T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(8)) \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7875 &:= (F(F(7)) - 8) \times 7 \times 5 \\ &:= T(-7 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 75 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4894 &:= F(4 + 8) \times F(9) - \sqrt{4} \\ &:= -\sqrt{4} + T(8) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7889 &:= -7 + 8 \times F(8 \times F(\sqrt{9})) \\ &:= -T(T(7)) + T(8) \times T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4899 &:= F(4 + 8) \times F(9) + \sqrt{9} \\ &:= T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(9) - \sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7896 &:= (-F(7) + F(8)) \times F(F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(6) \\ &:= 7 \times T(8 + T(9) - 6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4945 &:= (\sqrt{4} + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 5 \\ &:= T(T(4)) \times 9 \times T(4) - 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7922 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9 \times 2/2) \\ &:= (T(7) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times (2 + T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4998 &:= \sqrt{49} \times F(9) \times F(8) \\ &:= (T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(9)) \times 98 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7928 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 8 \\ &:= -T(7) + (T(T(9) + T(T(2)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5184 &:= (51 + F(8))^{\sqrt{4}} \\ &:= (\sqrt{5-1} \times T(8))^{\sqrt{4}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7959 &:= -F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9})^{F(5+F(\sqrt{9}))} \\ &:= (T(7) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 5) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5439 &:= F(F(5 + F(4)))/F(3) - F(9) \\ &:= (T(5 + \sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7994 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(9) + 4 \\ &:= \sqrt{T(T(7)) - T(\sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} - T(T(\sqrt{4}))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5482 &:= 5 + 4 + F(F(8))/2 \\ &:= T(T(T(5) - \sqrt{4})) + T(8)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$7995 := (F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(9) + 5$$

$$:= \sqrt{T(T(7)) - T(\sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} - 5}$$

$$\mathbf{7998} := (F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(9) + 8$$

$$:= (T(7 + T(9)) - T(9)) \times \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$\mathbf{8213} := F(8) + 2^{13}$$

$$:= T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 2^{13}$$

$$\mathbf{8294} := (F(F(8) - 2) - F(9)) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$:= 8 \times (2 + T(T(9))) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$\mathbf{8364} := F(F(8)) - F(3 \times 6) + \sqrt{4}$$

$$:= -T(T(8)) - T(T(T(3))) + T(6)^{T(\sqrt{4})}$$

$$\mathbf{8400} := F(8) \times 400$$

$$:= T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times 400$$

$$\mathbf{8464} := (84 + F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$:= (8 + 4 \times T(6))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$\mathbf{8749} := (T(T(8)) + 7) \times (4 + 9)$$

$$:= F(F(8)) - F(7)^{\sqrt{F(4) \times \sqrt{9}}}$$

$$\mathbf{8820} := F(8) \times F(8) \times 20$$

$$:= (T(8) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(20)$$

$$\mathbf{8883} := F(8 + 8) \times (8 + F(F(3)))$$

$$:= -T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(\sqrt{T(8)})^3$$

$$\mathbf{8898} := F(F(8)) - 8 \times F(\sqrt{9})^8$$

$$:= T(T(8)) + (-\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(9))) \times 8$$

$$\mathbf{9259} := -F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(F(2) + 5))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$:= T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{T(2)} - 5 + \sqrt{9}$$

$$\mathbf{9261} := F(9 - F(2))^{\sqrt{F(6)+1}}$$

$$:= T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{\sqrt{2+6+1}}$$

$$\mathbf{9263} := F(\sqrt{9}) + F(2 + 6)^3$$

$$:= T(\sqrt{9})/T(2) + T(6)^3$$

$$\mathbf{9264} := \sqrt{9} + F(2 + 6)^{F(4)}$$

$$:= 9/T(2) + T(6)^{T(\sqrt{4})}$$

$$\mathbf{9269} := 9 - F(2) + F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$:= T(\sqrt{9}) + 2 + T(6)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$\mathbf{9348} := -F(F(9)/F(3)) - F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(8))$$

$$:= (\sqrt{9} \times T(3) + T(T(T(4)))) \times \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$\mathbf{9375} := \sqrt{9} \times (-F(3) + 7)^5$$

$$:= \sqrt{9} \times \sqrt{(-3 + T(7))^5}$$

$$\mathbf{9576} := F(\sqrt{9}) \times (-5 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))$$

$$:= T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(5 \times 7 + T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{9648} := -F(\sqrt{9}) - 6^4 + F(F(8))$$

$$:= (T(9) \times 6 - \sqrt{4}) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{9789} := F(\sqrt{9})^{F(7)} + F(8 + 9)$$

$$:= \sqrt{9} \times T(T(7)) \times 8 + T(9)$$

2.3.2 Reverse Order of Digits

$$\begin{aligned}
 84 &:= 4 \times F(8) & &:= \sqrt{9} \times (8 + T(10)) \\
 &:= 4 \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \\
 189 &:= 9 \times F(8 \times 1) \\
 &:= 9 \times T(T(\sqrt{8+1})) \\
 378 &:= F(F(8) - 7) + F(F(3)) \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{T(8)} + 7 \times 3) \\
 379 &:= F(\sqrt{9}) + F(7 \times F(3)) \\
 &:= -T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(7)) - T(T(3)) \\
 438 &:= F(8)^{F(3)} - F(4) \\
 &:= T(8 + T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 648 &:= 8 \times \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} \\
 &:= T(8) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \times 6 \\
 699 &:= \sqrt{9} \times F(F(9) - F(F(6))) \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{9}) + \sqrt{9} \times T(T(6)) \\
 966 &:= -F(F(6)) + F(F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 &:= (T(6) + (T(6) \times T(9))) \\
 987 &:= F((-F(7) + F(8)) \times F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 &:= T(7) \times T(8) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 996 &:= F(F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \\
 &:= 6 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
 0142 &:= -2 + F(\sqrt{4} + 10) \\
 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 10) \\
 0174 &:= -4 + F(F(7)) - F(10) \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(7) - 10) \\
 0189 &:= 9 \times F(8 \times 1 + 0) \\
 0199 &:= F(9) + \sqrt{9} \times F(10) \\
 &:= 9 + T(9 + 10) \\
 0347 &:= F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) - 30 \\
 &:= T(T(7)) \times \sqrt{4} - T(30) \\
 0379 &:= F(\sqrt{9}) + F(7 \times F(3 + 0)) \\
 &:= \sqrt{9} + T(T(7)) - 30 \\
 1293 &:= F(F(3) \times 9)/2 + 1 \\
 &:= -3 + T(\sqrt{9})^{T(2)+1} \\
 1598 &:= F(8 + 9) + F(\sqrt{5 - 1}) \\
 &:= T(T(8) + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - T(T(5 - 1)) \\
 1599 &:= F(\sqrt{9}) + F(9 + F(5 + 1)) \\
 &:= \sqrt{9} + T(T(T(9 - 5)) + 1) \\
 1847 &:= (F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4}) \times 8 - 1 \\
 &:= T(T(7)) \times \sqrt{4} + T(T(8 + 1)) \\
 1864 &:= (\sqrt{4} + 6) \times F(F(8 - 1)) \\
 &:= (\sqrt{4} + T(T(6))) \times 8 \times 1 \\
 1869 &:= F(\sqrt{9} + F(6)) \times F(8 \times 1) \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(6)) \times 8 \times 1 \\
 1897 &:= 7 \times (F(9) \times 8 - 1) \\
 &:= 7 + \sqrt{9} \times T(T(8) - 1) \\
 1974 &:= \sqrt{4} \times F(7 + 9 \times 1) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(7)) + T(T(\sqrt{9}) + 1) \\
 2197 &:= F(7)^{9/(1+2)} \\
 &:= (7 + T(\sqrt{9}))^{1+2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2589 &:= F(-\sqrt{9} + F(8)) + \sqrt{5^2} \\
 &:= \sqrt{9} \times T(T(8) + 5) + T(T(2)) \\
 2594 &:= F(\sqrt{4} \times 9) + 5 \times 2 \\
 &:= \sqrt{4} + T(\sqrt{9})^5 / T(2) \\
 2646 &:= 6 \times F(\sqrt{4} + 6)^2 \\
 &:= T(6)^{\sqrt{4}} \times T(6/2) \\
 2797 &:= (F(7) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times F(F(7)) + F(2) \\
 &:= (T(T(7)) - T(\sqrt{9})) \times 7 - T(2) \\
 2798 &:= (F(8) - 9) \times F(F(7)) + 2 \\
 &:= (8 + T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(7) + 2)) \\
 2889 &:= -F(-\sqrt{9} + F(8)) + F(F(8))/2 \\
 &:= (T(T(9)) - T(8) - T(8)) \times T(2) \\
 2961 &:= F(16) \times \sqrt{9} \times F(2) \\
 &:= (T(T(-1 + 6)) + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times T(T(T(2))) \\
 2962 &:= F(2 \times F(6)) \times \sqrt{9} + F(2) \\
 &:= T(T(2) \times T(6)) + T(T(9) - 2) \\
 2964 &:= F(4) \times (F(F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9}))) + F(2) \\
 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (T(6 \times 9) - T(2)) \\
 2977 &:= F(7) \times (F(F(7)) - \sqrt{9} - F(2)) \\
 &:= 7 \times T(T(7)) + T(9) \times T(2) \\
 3647 &:= (-7 + \sqrt{4} + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\
 &:= T(T(7) \times T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(6))/3 \\
 3669 &:= F(-F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6))) - F(6)^3 \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{9}) \times 6) + T(T(T(6))/3) \\
 3993 &:= (F(3) + 9)^{\sqrt{9}} \times 3 \\
 &:= -T(3 \times 9) + T(93) \\
 3999 &:= (9 + F(9)) \times 93 \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(9) - 9) + 3 \\
 4179 &:= -F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(7 + 1) - \sqrt{4}) \\
 &:= T(T(T(\sqrt{9}) + 7)) - 1 - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 4182 &:= F(2) + F(F(8) - \sqrt{1 \times 4}) \\
 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(8) + 1)) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 4184 &:= F(4) + F(F(8) - \sqrt{1 \times 4}) \\
 &:= -\sqrt{4} + T(T(8 + 1 + 4)) \\
 4356 &:= (65 + F(F(3)))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 &:= ((6 + 5) \times T(3))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 4373 &:= 3^7 \times F(3) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 &:= T((3 + T(7)) \times 3) + \sqrt{4} \\
 4397 &:= F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \times F(3) + F(4) \\
 &:= T(7) + T(93) - \sqrt{4} \\
 4647 &:= F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4} + F(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4}) \\
 &:= T(T(7)) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(T(6) - T(4))) \\
 4768 &:= F(8) \times (-6 + F(F(7))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(T(6)) - T(7) - T(T(4)) \\
 4796 &:= -6 + F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7^4 \\
 &:= T(6) \times T(\sqrt{9} \times 7) - T(T(4)) \\
 4799 &:= -\sqrt{9} + F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7^4 \\
 &:= -9 + T(97) + T(T(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$4847 := (F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4}) \times F(8) - 4$$

$$:= T(T(7))^{\sqrt{4}}/8 - 4$$

$$5428 := F(F(8))/2 - 45$$

$$:= (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 2) \times (T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 5)$$

$$4864 := \sqrt{4}^{F(6)} \times (F(8) - \sqrt{4})$$

$$:= (T(T(4)) + T(6)) \times \sqrt{8^4}$$

$$5825 := 5^2 \times F(8 + 5)$$

$$:= 5 \times (2 + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 5$$

$$4873 := (3 + T(T(7)) \times T(8))/T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$:= (-F(F(3)) + F(F(7))) \times F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})$$

$$6394 := 4 \times F(F(9)/F(3)) + 6$$

$$:= T(T(T(4))) + \sqrt{9} + T(T(3)) \times T(T(6))$$

$$4876 := F(6) \times F(7 + 8) - 4$$

$$:= (T(T(6) + T(7)) - \sqrt{T(8)}) \times 4$$

$$7448 := 8 \times (-F(\sqrt{4}) + 4 \times F(F(7)))$$

$$:= (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + \sqrt{4}) - T(4)) \times T(7)$$

$$4878 := 8 \times F(7 + 8) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$:= \sqrt{T(8)} \times (-7 + T(T(8) + 4))$$

$$7458 := 85^{\sqrt{4}} + F(F(7))$$

$$:= (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) - 5) \times T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))))/7$$

$$4892 := F(F(-2 + 9)) \times F(8) - F(\sqrt{4})$$

$$:= -T(T(T(2))) + (9 + 8)^{T(\sqrt{4})}$$

$$7889 := F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 8) \times 8 - 7$$

$$:= T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times T(8) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) - T(T(7))$$

$$4893 := -3 + F(9) \times F(8 + 4)$$

$$:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(8) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$7949 := 9 \times F(4) + F(9) \times F(F(7))$$

$$:= T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(9)) - 7$$

$$4894 := -\sqrt{4} + F(9) \times F(8 + 4)$$

$$:= (T(T(4) + T(\sqrt{9}))) \times T(8) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$7959 := F(\sqrt{9})^{F(5+F(\sqrt{9}))} - F(F(7))$$

$$:= T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) + T(7))$$

$$4895 := F(5 \times F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(8 + F(4))$$

$$:= (5^{\sqrt{9}} - T(8)) \times T(T(4))$$

$$7992 := 2 + F(9) \times (F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(7)))$$

$$:= T(T(2))^{\sqrt{9}} \times (9 + T(7))$$

$$4899 := \sqrt{9} + F(9) \times F(8 + 4)$$

$$:= T(9) + T(98) + T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$7995 := 5 + F(9) \times (F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(7)))$$

$$:= T(T(5)) - T(9) \times (T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) - T(T(7))$$

$$4913 := (-F(3) + 19)^{F(4)}$$

$$:= (T(T(3)) - 1 - \sqrt{9})^{T(\sqrt{4})}$$

$$7998 := 8 + F(9) \times (F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(7)))$$

$$:= \sqrt{T(8)} \times (-T(9) + T(T(9) + 7))$$

$$4998 := F(8) \times F(9) \times (9 - \sqrt{4})$$

$$:= T(T(8))/T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(9) + T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$8364 := \sqrt{4} - F(6 \times 3) + F(F(8))$$

$$:= T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(T(6)) \times T(3) + 8)$$

$$:= -2 + T(6)^{T(2)} + \sqrt{9}$$

$$8898 := F(F(8)) - F(\sqrt{9})^8 \times 8$$

$$:= (-\sqrt{T(8) + T(T(9))}) \times 8 + T(T(8))$$

$$9264 := F(4) + F(6 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$:= T(\sqrt{4}) + T(6)^{\sqrt{T(2) \times \sqrt{9}}}$$

$$9216 := (F(6) \times 12)^{F(\sqrt{9})}$$

$$:= T(6)^{1+2} - T(9)$$

$$9375 := 5^{7-F(3)} \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$:= 5^{\sqrt{T(7)-3}} \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$9258 := F(8)^{5-2} - \sqrt{9}$$

$$:= (T(8) - T(5))^{T(2)} - \sqrt{9}$$

$$9477 := F(7) \times (F(7) - 4)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$:= T(7) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(T(4))) + T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$9259 := -F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(5 + F(2)))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$:= \sqrt{9} - 5 + T(T(T(2)))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9576 := F(F(6)) \times (F(F(7)) - 5) \times F(\sqrt{9})$$

$$:= 6 \times T(7 \times (5 + \sqrt{9}))$$

$$9261 := F(16/2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$:= ((1 + 6) \times T(2))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9789 := (F(9) + 8) \times F(F(7)) + \sqrt{9}$$

$$:= \sqrt{9} \times 8 \times T(T(7)) + T(9)$$

$$9262 := F(2) + F(6 + 2)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

2.4 With Factorial and Square-Root

In this subsection, we shall bring **selfie numbers written in terms of Fibonacci sequence and Triangular numbers** at the same time. The numbers are with used of **basic operations, factorial and square-root**. Again, the work is divided in two subsections, one in digit's order and another in reverse order of digits.

2.4.1 Digit's Order

- Symmetric

$$720 := (7 - F(2))! + 0 = T(\sqrt{7+2})! + 0$$

$$721 := (7 - F(2))! + 1 = T(\sqrt{7+2})! + 1$$

$$722 := (7 - F(2))! + 2 = T(\sqrt{7+2})! + 2$$

$$723 := (7 - F(2))! + 3 = T(\sqrt{7+2})! + 3$$

$$724 := (7 - F(2))! + 4 = T(\sqrt{7+2})! + 4$$

$$725 := (7 - F(2))! + 5 = T(\sqrt{7+2})! + 5$$

$$726 := (7 - F(2))! + 6 = T(\sqrt{7+2})! + 6$$

$$727 := (7 - F(2))! + 7 = T(\sqrt{7+2})! + 7$$

$$728 := (7 - F(2))! + 8 = T(\sqrt{7+2})! + 8$$

$$729 := (7 - F(2))! + 9 = T(\sqrt{7+2})! + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4350 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 0 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! + 5) + 0 \\
 4351 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 1 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! + 5) + 1 \\
 4352 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 2 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! + 5) + 2 \\
 4353 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 3 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! + 5) + 3 \\
 4354 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 4 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! + 5) + 4 \\
 4355 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 5 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! + 5) + 5 \\
 4356 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 6 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! + 5) + 6 \\
 4357 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 7 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! + 5) + 7 \\
 4358 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 8 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! + 5) + 8 \\
 4359 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + 5) + 9 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! + 5) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5490 &:= F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 0 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 0 \\
 5491 &:= F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 1 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 1 \\
 5492 &:= F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 2 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 2 \\
 5493 &:= F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 3 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 3 \\
 5494 &:= F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 4 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 4 \\
 5495 &:= F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 5 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 5 \\
 5496 &:= F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 6 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 6 \\
 5497 &:= F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 7 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 7 \\
 5498 &:= F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 8 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 8 \\
 5499 &:= F(5 \times F(4)) \times 9 + 9 = (5! + \sqrt{4}) \times T(9) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

• **Nonsymmetric**

$$\begin{aligned}
 42 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times 2 & &:= T(T(2)!)/T(\sqrt{4}) + 7 \\
 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(T(T(2))) \\
 48 &:= F(4)! \times 8 & &284 := \sqrt{2 \times (8! + F(F(4)!))} \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 8 & &:= -2 \times 8 + T(4!) \\
 199 &:= F(F(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - F(9) & &297 := 2^{(\sqrt{9})!} + F(F(7)) \\
 &:= T(19) + 9 & &:= -T(2) + T((\sqrt{9} + 7)!) \\
 239 &:= -F(2) + 3!!/\sqrt{9} & &364 := (F(3!) + 6!)/\sqrt{4} \\
 &:= (-T(2) + T(3)!)/\sqrt{9} & &:= -T(T(T(3))) + T(-T(6) + T(T(4))) \\
 247 &:= (-2 + F(F(F(4)!))) \times F(7) & &369 := -F(3!) + F(F(6) + (\sqrt{9})!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -T(36) + T(T(9)) & & := T(\sqrt{4} + T(5)) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{374} & := (T(3)! + T(7))/\sqrt{4} & & \mathbf{464} := -\sqrt{4^{F(6)}} + F(4)!! \\
 & := -3 + F(7 \times \sqrt{4}) & & := \sqrt{4} \times T(T(6)) + \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{398} & := F(F(3!)) + F((\sqrt{9})! + 8) & & \mathbf{474} := (4 + F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 & := T(T(T(T(3))/\sqrt{9})) - 8 & & := (-T(4!) + 7!)/T(4) \\
 \mathbf{399} & := (F(F(3!)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) & & \mathbf{480} := 4! \times (F(8) - 0!) \\
 & := -T(3) + 9 \times T(9) & & := 4 \times (\sqrt{T(8)} - 0!) \\
 \mathbf{438} & := -F(4) + F(F(3!)) \times F(8) & & \mathbf{483} := (\sqrt{4} + F(8)) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 & := T(4! \times 3)/\sqrt{T(8)} & & := (\sqrt{4} + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{439} & := -\sqrt{4} + F(F(3!))^{F(\sqrt{9})} & & \mathbf{487} := (4!/8)!! - F(F(7)) \\
 & := -\sqrt{4} + T(T(3)) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) & & := \sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^8} + T(T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{440} & := F(F(F(4)!))\sqrt{4} - 0! & & \mathbf{496} := -F(F(4)!) + 9!/6! \\
 & := T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))\sqrt{4} - 0! & & := T(4 + \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}) \\
 \mathbf{441} & := F(F(F(4)!))^{F(4-1)} & & \mathbf{497} := 4! \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 7 \\
 & := T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))\sqrt{4 \times 1} & & := T(4 + 9) + T(T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{442} & := T(T(T(4)) - 4)/T(2) & & \mathbf{589} := F(5!/8) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 & := F(F(F(4)!))\sqrt{4} + F(2) & & := T(5 \times 8) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 \mathbf{443} & := F(F(F(4)!))\sqrt{4} + F(3) & & \mathbf{594} := -5! + (\sqrt{9})!! - F(4)! \\
 & := \sqrt{4} + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(T(3)) & & := -5! + T(\sqrt{9})! - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 \mathbf{444} & := F(F(F(4)!))\sqrt{4} + F(4) & & \mathbf{648} := (-6 + 4!) \times T(8) \\
 & := T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 4! + T(4!) & & := F(6) \times \sqrt{F(4)^8} \\
 \mathbf{447} & := F(4)!! - F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(7) & & \mathbf{664} := -F(6)!/6! + F(4)!! \\
 & := T(4!) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times 7 & & := T(6 \times 6) - \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{449} & := F(F((F(4)!))\sqrt{4} + F((\sqrt{9})!)) & & \mathbf{696} := 6! - \sqrt{9} \times F(6) \\
 & := -T(T(4)) + 4! \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) & & := 6! - T(9) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{459} & := 4 \times 5! - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 699 &:= -F(F(6)) + (9 - \sqrt{9})! \\ &:= -T(6) + (9 - \sqrt{9})! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 714 &:= (7 - 1)! - F(4)! \\ &:= (7 - 1)! - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 734 &:= F(7) + 3!! + F(\sqrt{4}) \\ &:= -7 + T(T(3)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 739 &:= F(7) + 3!! + (\sqrt{9})! \\ &:= T(7) + T(3)! - 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 746 &:= F(7) \times \sqrt{4} + 6! \\ &:= T(7) - \sqrt{4} + 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 840 &:= F(8) \times 40 \\ &:= (\sqrt{T(8)})! + (4 + 0)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 846 &:= F(8) \times F(4)! + 6! \\ &:= T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 945 &:= F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 45 \\ &:= \sqrt{9} \times (T(4!) + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 979 &:= F(9 + 7) - F((\sqrt{9})!) \\ &:= T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(7) + T(\sqrt{9})! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 984 &:= -\sqrt{9} + F(8 \times \sqrt{4}) \\ &:= T(\sqrt{9})! - T(8) + T(4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 993 &:= (\sqrt{9})! + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(3!)) \\ &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 995 &:= F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 5) \\ &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1089 &:= (-1 + F(0! + 8))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\ &:= (1 + (-0! + \sqrt{T(8)})!) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1149 &:= F(11) \times F(F(F(4)!)) - (\sqrt{9})!! \\ &:= 114 + T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1299 &:= F(12) \times 9 + \sqrt{9} \\ &:= 12!/9! - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1359 &:= -1 + F(3!) \times 5 \times F(9) \\ &:= T(13) \times T(5) - T(\sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1379 &:= -1 + (-3 + F(F(7))) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\ &:= 1 + T(T(3 + 7) - \sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1394 &:= F(13) \times (\sqrt{9})! - 4 \\ &:= -1 + 3 \times T(\sqrt{9} \times T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1428 &:= F(1 + F(F(4)!)) \times 2 \times F(8) \\ &:= (T(1 + T(4)) + 2) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1433 &:= -1 - F(4)! + 3!! + 3!! \\ &:= -1 + \sqrt{4} \times T(3)! - T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1440 &:= \sqrt{1 \times 4} \times F(4 + 0)!! \\ &:= \sqrt{1 \times 4} \times T(4 - 0)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1443 &:= F(1 \times 4) + \sqrt{4} \times 3!! \\ &:= -1 + 4 + \sqrt{4} \times T(3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1447 &:= \sqrt{1 \times 4} \times F(4)!! + 7 \\ &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(4) - T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1449 &:= F(1 \times 4!) / (-\sqrt{4} + F(9)) \\ &:= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(4) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1452 &:= (1 + F(4)!! + 5) \times 2 \\ &:= (-1 + T(\sqrt{4})^5) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1459 &:= 1 + F(4)^5 \times (\sqrt{9})! \\ &:= 1 + T(\sqrt{4})^5 \times T(\sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

$$1467 := 1 + \sqrt{4} \times (6! + F(7))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -1 + \sqrt{4} \times 6! + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{1476} & := (F(1 + F(4)!) + F(F(7))) \times 6 \\
 & := (T(1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - 7) \times 6 \\
 \mathbf{1477} & := 1 + F(4)! \times (F(F(7)) + F(7)) \\
 & := T(-1 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 7 + 7 \\
 \mathbf{1489} & := 1 + F(4)!/F(8) - (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 & := 1 \times 4 + T(\sqrt{T(8)} \times 9) \\
 \mathbf{1529} & := F(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) + 2 \times (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 & := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 2 - 9 \\
 \mathbf{1547} & := (1 + 5! - \sqrt{4}) \times F(7) \\
 & := T(1 + 54) + 7 \\
 \mathbf{1584} & := \sqrt{1 + 5!} \times F(8 + 4) \\
 & := (1 + 5)! + T(8) \times 4! \\
 \mathbf{1674} & := -1 \times 6 + 7!/F(4) \\
 & := 1 + (-T(6) + 7!)/T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{1696} & := (F(F(1 + 6)) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times F(6) \\
 & := 1 + T(69) - 6! \\
 \mathbf{1724} & := -1 - 7! + F(-F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 & := \sqrt{1 + 7!} + T(2 + T(T(4))) \\
 \mathbf{1749} & := (-1 + F(7))^{F(4)} + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 & := \sqrt{1 + 7!} \times 4! + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1779} & := 1 + 7 \times (F(F(7)) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \\
 & := T(1 + T(T(7)))/7 + 9 \\
 \mathbf{1793} & := 1 + (F(F(7)) - 9) \times F(3!) \\
 & := 1 + T(T(7)) + T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{1799} & := -1 + 7!/F(\sqrt{9}) - (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 & := (-1 + T((\sqrt{7+9})!)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{1833} & := (1 + F(F(8) - 3!)) \times 3 \\
 & := T\left(\sqrt{\left(-1 + \sqrt{T(8)}\right) \times T(3)!}\right) + 3 \\
 \mathbf{1849} & := (1 + F(8) \times \sqrt{4})^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 & := 1 + 8 \times T(4! - \sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{1865} & := 1 + 8 \times F(F(6) + 5) \\
 & := -1 + T(8) + T(\sqrt{6! \times 5}) \\
 \mathbf{1898} & := -1 + 8!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - F(8) \\
 & := T(-1 + T(8)) \times \sqrt{9} + 8 \\
 \mathbf{1899} & := 1 \times 8!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 & := (T(-1 + T(8)) + \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{1919} & := -1 + F((\sqrt{9})!)/F(-1 + 9) \\
 & := -1 + (9 - 1)!/T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{1932} & := F((1 + \sqrt{9})!)/(F(3) + 2)! \\
 & := (1 + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{1939} & := 19 + F(3)!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 & := 1 + T(T(9)) + T(-3 + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{1943} & := 1 + T(\sqrt{9} + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))) \\
 & := -1 + 9 \times F(4)!^3 \\
 \mathbf{1945} & := 1 + F((\sqrt{9})!) \times F(4)^5 \\
 & := 1 + 9 \times (T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{2054} & := 2^{\sqrt{0!+5!}} + F(4)! \\
 & := 2^{\sqrt{0!+5!}} + T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 \mathbf{2099} & := 2 + (F(F(0! + (\sqrt{9})!)) \times 9) \\
 & := 20 + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times 9 \\
 \mathbf{2199} & := 2 + F(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)^{\sqrt{9}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (T(T(2)) - 1)! + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times 9 \\
 \mathbf{2354} & := (2 - F(F(3!)) \times (-5! + F(F(4!)))) \\
 & := 2 \times T(T(3)!/T(5)) + \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{2393} & := F(F(F(2) + 3!)) + \sqrt{9} \times 3!! \\
 & := 2 + T(T(T(3))) + \sqrt{9} \times T(3)! \\
 \mathbf{2394} & := ((2 + 3)! - (\sqrt{9})!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 & := -T(2 \times 3) + T(T(9) + 4!) \\
 \mathbf{2395} & := F(2) - F(F(3!)) \times ((\sqrt{9})! - 5!) \\
 & := T(2^{T(3)}) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{2435} & := (-F(F(F(2) + F(4!))) + 3!!) \times 5 \\
 & := ((T(T(2)))! - \sqrt{4} - T(T(T(3)))) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{2438} & := -2 + 4 \times F(-3! + F(8)) \\
 & := (2 + T(T(4 + 3)) \times \sqrt{T(8)}) \\
 \mathbf{2456} & := (-F(2) - F(4) + 5!) \times F(F(6)) \\
 & := -2^{T(T(\sqrt{4}))} + 5! \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{2458} & := F(2) - (F(4) - 5!) \times F(8) \\
 & := -2 + T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(5 \times 8) \\
 \mathbf{2459} & := 2 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! - \sqrt{9}) \\
 & := 2 - (T(\sqrt{4}) - 5!) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{2493} & := -F(2) + F(F(4)!)/\sqrt{9} - F(F(F(3!))) \\
 & := T(T(2) \times 4!) - T(9) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{2494} & := -F(F(2 \times 4)) + F((\sqrt{9})!)/F(4) \\
 & := (T(2) + T(T(4))) \times (T(9) - \sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{2495} & := -F(2) - 4! + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 5! \\
 & := T(T(2))! - T(T(4)) + T(T(9) + T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{2497} & := F(2) + 4! \times F((\sqrt{9})!) \times F(7) \\
 & := T(T(2)) + T(T(4)) + T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{2499} & := (-F(2) + (-4 + 9)!) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 & := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times (T(9) + T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{2518} & := -2 + 5! \times 1 \times F(8) \\
 & := -2 + 5! \times T(T(\sqrt{1 + 8})) \\
 \mathbf{2539} & := (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F(3!)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 & := -2 + 5! \times T(T(3)) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{2543} & := 2 + (5! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 & := T(T(T(2))) \times 5! + \sqrt{4} + T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{2549} & := (F(2) + 5!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + F((\sqrt{9})!) \\
 & := T(T(T(2)) \times T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) - T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{2564} & := (2 + 5!) \times F(F(6)) + \sqrt{4} \\
 & := (2 + 5!) \times T(6) + \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{2574} & := \sqrt{F(2) + 5!} \times (F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \\
 & := T(2) \times (-5! + T(T(7))) \times T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{2578} & := 2 + F(5 + F(7)) - 8 \\
 & := T(\sqrt{T(T(2))! \times 5}) + T(7) + (\sqrt{T(8)})! \\
 \mathbf{2579} & := -2 + F(5 + F(7)) - \sqrt{9} \\
 & := -2 - 5! + T(T(7) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{2596} & := (-2 + 5!) \times (F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(6))) \\
 & := T(T(2 \times 5)) + T(T(9)) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{2689} & := F(2) - F(6)!/(-F(8) + (\sqrt{9})!) \\
 & := -2 + (T(T(6)) + T(T(8))) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{2694} & := F(2 \times F(6)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) + F(4)!! \\
 & := \sqrt{2 \times (T(6) - \sqrt{9} + T(4)!)} \\
 \mathbf{2709} & := (2^7 + 0!) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(2) \times T(7 \times T(\sqrt{09})) & & := T(2) + (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{2743} & := -F(2) + (7 \times \sqrt{4})^3 & & \mathbf{2944} := (2 \times F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(4)!) \times 4 \\
 & := T(T(2))! + 7 + T(T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(3))) & & := T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 4 \\
 \mathbf{2746} & := 2 + 7^{F(4)} \times F(6) & & \mathbf{2949} := (F(2 \times F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 4) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 & := T(T(T(T(2)) + 7)) - \sqrt{4} \times 6! & & := (T(2) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{2759} & := -2^{F(7)} + 5 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) & & \mathbf{2959} := -2 + (F(F((\sqrt{9})!) + 5!) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 & := T(T(2))! + T(T(7)) \times 5 + 9 & & := -2 + (T(T(\sqrt{9}) + 5!) \times T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 \mathbf{2792} & := 2 \times (F(F(7)) \times (\sqrt{9})! - 2) & & \mathbf{2961} := F(2 \times F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times \sqrt{F(6) + 1} \\
 & := T(2 + T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 2 & & := T(T(T(2) + 9)) - (6 - 1)! \\
 \mathbf{2793} & := 2 \times F(F(7)) \times (\sqrt{9})! - 3 & & \mathbf{2977} := (-F(2) - \sqrt{9} + F(F(7))) \times F(7) \\
 & := (-T(2) + T(7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) & & := -2 \times T(T(9)) + 7! + 7 \\
 \mathbf{2799} & := 2 \times F(F(7)) \times (\sqrt{9})! + \sqrt{9} & & \mathbf{3066} := 3! \times (-0! + \sqrt{F(6)^6}) \\
 & := T(2 + T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + 9 & & := -T(T(3) - 0!) + T(T(6 + 6)) \\
 \mathbf{2835} & := (F(2) + 8)! / (F(3!) + 5!) & & \mathbf{3087} := F(F(3!)) \times F(08) \times 7 \\
 & := \sqrt{T(2)^8} \times 35 & & := T(T(3)) \times T(\sqrt{T(08)}) \times 7 \\
 \mathbf{2859} & := (\sqrt{2 \times 8})! \times 5! - F(F(\sqrt{9})!) & & \mathbf{3155} := (3!! - F(\sqrt{1 + 5!})) \times 5 \\
 & := T(2) + \sqrt{T(8)} + T(5! - T(9)) & & := (T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 5) \\
 \mathbf{2879} & := (-2 + 8!/7) / F(\sqrt{9}) & & \mathbf{3194} := T(3)! - 1 + T(9) \times T(T(4)) \\
 & := T(T(2)) \times (\sqrt{T(8)})! - T(T(7)) - T(T(9)) & & := F(3) \times F(19 - \sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{2884} & := (F(2) + F(\sqrt{8 + 8}))! \times 4 & & \mathbf{3328} := (F(F(F(3)) + 3!)) \times 2^8 \\
 & := 2^8 + T(T(8) \times \sqrt{4}) & & := T(T(3))/3 + T(\sqrt{T(2)^8}) \\
 \mathbf{2896} & := 2 \times (8 + F(\sqrt{9}) \times 6!) & & \mathbf{3347} := F(3)! / (3 \times 4) - F(7) \\
 & := 2 \times (8 + T(\sqrt{9})! + 6!) & & := (T(T(3)) - T(3))^{T(\sqrt{4})} - T(7) \\
 \mathbf{2898} & := (2 + F(8)) \times (\sqrt{9})! \times F(8) & & \mathbf{3355} := F(3)! / \sqrt{3!!/5} - 5 \\
 & := 2 \times T(8 + T(9)) + T(8) & & := (T(T(3) \times T(3)) + 5) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{2943} & := (F(2 \times F((\sqrt{9})!)) - F(4)!) \times 3 & & \mathbf{3369} := -3! + (-3! + F(F(6)))^{\sqrt{9}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(33) \times 6 + \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{3394} & := F(3! + F(3!)) \times 9 + F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 & := T(3 \times T(T(3))) + T(-\sqrt{9} + T(T(4))) \\
 \mathbf{3399} & := F(3! + F(3!)) \times 9 + (\sqrt{9})! \\
 & := T(3^3) \times 9 - \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{3409} & := (F(F(F(3!))) - F(4)!! + 0!) / \sqrt{9} \\
 & := T(3^4 + 0!) + T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{3443} & := (3 + 4)! - F(-4 + F(F(3!))) \\
 & := T(3 + T(T(4))) \times \sqrt{4} + T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3447} & := -F(F(F(3!)) - 4) + 4 + 7! \\
 & := -(T(T(T(3))) + T(4!)) \times T(\sqrt{4}) + 7! \\
 \mathbf{3462} & := 3! + 4! \times F(6 \times 2) \\
 & := T(3 + \sqrt{4}) \times T(T(6)) - T(2) \\
 \mathbf{3469} & := F(3!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 & := T(T(T(3))) - \sqrt{4} + T(6!/9) \\
 \mathbf{3485} & := (3!! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 5 \\
 & := (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{3538} & := (F(3) + 5!) \times (F(3!) + F(8)) \\
 & := T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(T(3)) - 5} \right) \right) \right) + 3 \times T(T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{3545} & := 3!! \times 5 - F(\sqrt{4} \times 5) \\
 & := T(3)! \times 5 - T(\sqrt{4} \times 5) \\
 \mathbf{3574} & := 3!! \times 5 - F(7) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 & := T(3)! \times 5 - T(7) + \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{3580} & := 3!! \times 5 - F(8) + 0! \\
 & := T(3)! \times 5 - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 0! \\
 \mathbf{3587} & := 3!! \times \sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} - F(7)} \\
 & := 3 + (5! + 8) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{3592} & := 3!! \times 5 - 9 + F(2) \\
 & := T(3)! \times 5 - T(\sqrt{9}) - 2 \\
 \mathbf{3593} & := 3!! \times 5 - 9 + F(3) \\
 & := (T(3)! \times T(5) - T(T(\sqrt{9}))) / 3 \\
 \mathbf{3595} & := (3!! - F(5 - \sqrt{9})) \times 5 \\
 & := T(3)! \times T(5) / \sqrt{9} - 5 \\
 \mathbf{3598} & := -F(3) + 5! \times (9 + F(8)) \\
 & := T(3)! \times 5 + T(\sqrt{9}) - 8 \\
 \mathbf{3644} & := (-F(3!) + F(F(F(6)))) / F(4) - \sqrt{4} \\
 & := T(3)! + T(T(6) + T(T(4))) - \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{3684} & := 3!! + (6! + F(8)) \times 4 \\
 & := (-T(3) + T(T(6)) \times 8) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{3694} & := -F(F(F(3!))) + F(6 + 9) \times 4! \\
 & := T(3)! \times T(T(6)) / T(9) - \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{3696} & := (3! + F(6 + 9)) \times 6 \\
 & := T(3)! \times T(T(6)) / T(\sqrt{9} + 6) \\
 \mathbf{3699} & := (F(3! + F(6)) + F(9)) \times 9 \\
 & := T(\sqrt{3^6}) + T(9 \times 9) \\
 \mathbf{3724} & := (F(3!) \times F(F(7)) - 2) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 & := -3 + T(T(7)) + T(T(2)^4) \\
 \mathbf{3729} & := (F(3!) \times F(F(7))) \times 2 + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 & := T(T(3)) + (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) \times 9 \\
 \mathbf{3792} & := 3! \times (7! / F((\sqrt{9})!)) + 2 \\
 & := (3 - T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{3795} & := (3!! + F(7) \times \sqrt{9}) \times 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (3 \times T(7)) \times T(9) + T(5) & & := -T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9+4)) - T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{3834} & := (-\sqrt{3^6} + 3!!) \times F(4)! & & \mathbf{3955} := (-F(F(3)) + F(9)) \times 5! - 5 \\
 & := T(3) + T(83+4) & & := -T(T(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9}+5+5)) \\
 \mathbf{3843} & := 3 + 8! \times \sqrt{4}/T(T(3)) & & \mathbf{3959} := (-F(F(3)) + F(9)) \times 5! - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 & := F(3!)/F(8) \times \sqrt{4} + 3 & & := -T(T(3)!/T(9)) + T(T(5) \times T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{3845} & := 3!! + (8 - F(4))^5 & & \mathbf{3963} := -3! + (\sqrt{9} \times F(F(6)))^{F(3)} \\
 & := (T(3)! - \sqrt{T(8) + T(T(4))}) \times 5 & & := T(T(3)) \times 9 \times T(6) - T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3846} & := 3! + 8! \times \sqrt{4}/F(F(6)) & & \mathbf{3976} := F(3!) \times (9! - 7!)/6! \\
 & := T(3) + 8! \times \sqrt{4}/T(6) & & := -T(T(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(7+6)) \\
 \mathbf{3848} & := F(3!) + 8! \times \sqrt{4}/F(8) & & \mathbf{3984} := -F(3!) \times ((\sqrt{9})! - F(8) \times 4!) \\
 & := (-T(T(T(3))) - 8 + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))!) \times 8 & & := -3 - T(9) + 8!/T(4) \\
 \mathbf{3849} & := F(3!)/F(8) \times \sqrt{4} + 9 & & \mathbf{3990} := 3! \times ((\sqrt{9})!! - F(9+0!)) \\
 & := T(T(3)) + T(T(8+4) + 9) & & := T(T(3)) \times T(9+9+0!) \\
 \mathbf{3857} & := (F(3!) + F(8)) \times (5! + F(7)) & & \mathbf{3994} := -3 \times F(9) + F((\sqrt{9})!)^4 \\
 & := -T(T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{T(8) \times T(5)}) - 7 & & := T(3) \times T(T(9) - 9) - \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{3879} & := -F(F(3!)) \times F(8) + 7! - (\sqrt{9})!! & & \mathbf{4093} := -F(4) + (0! + \sqrt{9})^3 \\
 & := T(3) + T(87) + T(9) & & := 4^{T(\sqrt{09})} - 3 \\
 \mathbf{3897} & := F(F(3)) + 8 \times ((\sqrt{9})!! - F(F(7))) & & \mathbf{4128} := (F(4!) + F((1+2)!))/F(8) \\
 & := -3 \times T(8) - T(T(9)) + 7! & & := T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{3924} & := (-3! + F(F((\sqrt{9})!) \times 2)) \times 4 & & \mathbf{4187} := F(4)! + F((\sqrt{1+8})! + F(7)) \\
 & := (T(3)! - T(9+2)) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) & & := -T(41) + 8 + 7! \\
 \mathbf{3936} & := (-F(3)^{(\sqrt{9})!} + 3!!) \times 6 & & \mathbf{4189} := F(F(4)!) + F(1 + F(8) - \sqrt{9}) \\
 & := T(3+93) - 6! & & := T(T(4+1+8)) + \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{3947} & := F(F(F(3!)) - F(\sqrt{9})) - F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(7)) & & \mathbf{4194} := (-F(F((4-1)!)) + (\sqrt{9})!!) \times F(4)! \\
 & := -3 - T(T(9)) - T(T(4)) + 7! & & := T(T(4)) - 1 + T(T(9)) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{3949} & := F((F(3!) \times F(\sqrt{9}))) \times 4 + F(F(\sqrt{9})) & & \mathbf{4229} := 4! \times 2 + F(-2 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \\
 & & & := T(T(T(4) + T(2))) - 2 + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4247 &:= F(F(4)!)/(F(2) + F(F(4)!)) - F(F(7)) \\
 &:= T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) - 2^{T(4)} + 7! \\
 4249 &:= F(F(F((F(4)!))) - 2) + \sqrt{4} \times F(9) \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4+9)) \\
 4254 &:= (F(4)!! - \sqrt{F(2) + 5!}) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= (-4! + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5) + \sqrt{4}) \\
 4294 &:= -4! - 2 + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(4)!! \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 4 \\
 4295 &:= F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) - (\sqrt{9})! + 5! \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 5 \\
 4297 &:= -4! + F(2) - (\sqrt{9})!! + 7! \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 7 \\
 4299 &:= (F(4)!! - 2) \times (\sqrt{9})! - 9 \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 9 \\
 4307 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - F(07) \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(3)! - 0!) - 7 \\
 4312 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - F((1+2)!) \\
 &:= -\sqrt{4} + (T(3)! - 1) \times T(T(2)) \\
 4313 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - 1 - 3! \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(3)! - 1 - T(3) \\
 4315 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - 1 \times 5 \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(3)! - 1 \times 5 \\
 4318 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - F(\sqrt{1+8}) \\
 &:= -\sqrt{4} - T(3)! + (-1+8)! \\
 4319 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! - 1^9 \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(3)! - 1^9 \\
 4322 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + \sqrt{2+2} \\
 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(3)! \times T(2) + 2 \\
 4325 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + \sqrt{25} \\
 &:= \sqrt{4} \times T(3)! \times T(2) + 5 \\
 4339 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) + (3+3!!) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
 &:= T(4) + T(3)! \times T(3) + 9 \\
 4340 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + 3!! \times F(4)! - 0! \\
 &:= T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(3)! \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) - 0! \\
 4341 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + F(F((4-1)!)) \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(3)! + T(T(4-1)) \\
 4342 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + 4! - 2 \\
 &:= 4 + (T(3)! + T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(2)) \\
 4349 &:= F(F(4)!) + F(F(3!)) + F(4)! \times (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 &:= (\sqrt{4} + T(T(T(3)))) - 4! \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 4364 &:= -4 + (F(3!) + 6!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{4})^{T(3)} \times 6 - T(4) \\
 4367 &:= F(4)^{3!} \times 6 - 7 \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{4})^{T(3)} \times 6 - 7 \\
 4376 &:= F(4)! \times 3!! + 7 \times F(6) \\
 &:= T(-\sqrt{4} + T(T(3))) + T(T(7+6)) \\
 4389 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + (3!! + 8) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
 &:= (4 + T(3)!) \times \sqrt{T(8)} + T(9) \\
 4392 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + (\sqrt{9})! \times 2) \\
 &:= T(4!) - 3 + T(T(9) \times 2) \\
 4393 &:= F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(3!))) - \sqrt{9^{F(3!)}} \\
 &:= T(T(4)) + (T(3)! + \sqrt{9}) \times T(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4397 &:= F(4)!^3 + F((\sqrt{9})! + F(7)) \\ &:= -T(T(\sqrt{4})!) + T(T(T(3))) / \sqrt{9} + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4482 &:= (F(F(4)!))! / (F(\sqrt{4}) + 8) + 2 \\ &:= (T(\sqrt{4})^4 + T(T(8))) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4398 &:= F(4)! \times (3!! + F(9) - F(8)) \\ &:= (4 + T(3)! + 9) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4484 &:= F(F(4)!)/ (F(\sqrt{4}) + 8) + 4 \\ &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(48)) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4414 &:= (F(4!)/F(F(F(4)!)) - 1) \times \sqrt{4} \\ &:= (-4 + T(T(T(4) + 1))) \times \sqrt{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4485 &:= F(F(4)!)/ (F(\sqrt{4}) + 8) + 5 \\ &:= T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(T(4)) + T(8) \times 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4437 &:= 4^4 + F(3! + F(7)) \\ &:= -T(4!) \times \sqrt{4} - 3 + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4487 &:= (-4! - T(T(4)) + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 7 \\ &:= F(F(4)!)/ (F(\sqrt{4}) + 8) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4438 &:= F(4)! \times (F(4)!! + F(F(3!))) - 8 \\ &:= T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(4))) + T(T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4488 &:= F(4)! \times F(4)!! + 8 \times F(8) \\ &:= 4 \times (\sqrt{4} + 8! / T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4439 &:= F(F(F(F(4)!))) - (F(4) + 3!) \times 9 \\ &:= -T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + T(3) \times T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4489 &:= (F(4)^4 + 8!) / 9 \\ &:= T(\sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} + 8! / 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4444 &:= (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! - \sqrt{4} \\ &:= 4 \times (T(T(\sqrt{4})))! + 4! + T(T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4493 &:= (F(4) - F(4)!!) \times 9 + F(F(F(3!))) \\ &:= (-T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(4!) \times T(9)) / 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4447 &:= -F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(4)!! + F(7)) \\ &:= \sqrt{4} - T(4! + T(4)) + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4494 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (4! \times 9 - \sqrt{4}) \\ &:= (T(T(T(4))) / \sqrt{4} - T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4449 &:= (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! + \sqrt{9} \\ &:= T(\sqrt{4})^4 \times T(T(4)) - T(\sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4499 &:= (-T(\sqrt{4}) + T(4!) \times T(9)) / \sqrt{9} \\ &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + (F(F(4)!))! / 9 - F(\sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4452 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (-F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(5 + 2))) \\ &:= (-T(\sqrt{4}) + T(4!)) \times T(5) - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4559 &:= -F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 5! + 5^{(\sqrt{9})!} \\ &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 59 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4472 &:= -F(F(4)!) + (F(F(4)!))! / (7 + 2) \\ &:= (T(T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(4)) + T(T(7))) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4579 &:= (4! - 5) \times (F(F(7)) + F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\ &:= T(4!) \times T(5) + 79 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4477 &:= -4! \times 4! + F(7) + 7! \\ &:= -\sqrt{4} - T(T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) / 7) + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4608 &:= 4!^{F(\sqrt{F(6)+0!})} \times 8 \\ &:= \sqrt{4^{6+0!}} \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4479 &:= -F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(4)!) \times 7! / 9 \\ &:= T(4!) \times T(-\sqrt{4} + 7) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4637 &:= (-\sqrt{4^{F(6)}} + F(F(3!)) \times F(F(7))) \\ &:= T(\sqrt{4}) + (T(6)/3)! - T(T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$4644 := ((F(4)!! + F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}) \times 4 \\ := -\sqrt{4} \times 6 + T(4! \times 4)$$

$$4789 := F(F(F(4)!)) + 7! - 8 \times F(9) \\ := T(4) \times T(T(7)) + (\sqrt{T(8)})! + 9$$

$$4660 := (-F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6))) \times F(F(F(6) - 0!)) \\ := (\sqrt{4} + T(T(6))) \times (T(6) - 0!)$$

$$4790 := F(4! - 7) \times \sqrt{9} - 0! \\ := T(\sqrt{4}) + 7! - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 0!$$

$$4679 := (-\sqrt{4} + 6! \times F(7))/F(\sqrt{9}) \\ := T(4)!/6! - T(T(7)) + T(9)$$

$$4791 := F(4) \times F(7 + 9 + 1) \\ := 4 + 7! - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 1$$

$$4696 := (-4!!/(F(F(6)))! + F((\sqrt{9}!)!))/6 \\ := T(T(T(4)) - 6 + T(9)) + T(T(6))$$

$$4792 := F(4! - 7) \times \sqrt{9} + F(2) \\ := 4 + T(7) \times T(9 \times 2)$$

$$4698 := F(4)! \times (6! + (\sqrt{9} \times F(8))) \\ := (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(-6 + T(9))) \times \sqrt{T(8)}$$

$$4793 := F(4! - 7) \times \sqrt{9} + F(3) \\ := -T(4) + 7! - T(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(T(3)))$$

$$4744 := (F(4)!! + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{4}) \times 4 \\ := T(T(4)) + 7! - T(4! + \sqrt{4})$$

$$4799 := F(4! - 7) \times \sqrt{9} + F((\sqrt{9}!) \\ := -T(4) + 7! - T(T(9 - \sqrt{9}))$$

$$4759 := (F(4)!! + F(F(7))) \times 5 - (\sqrt{9})! \\ := T(4 \times T(7) - T(5)) + T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$4807 := F(\sqrt{4}) \times (8 - 0!)! - F(F(7)) \\ := -T(\sqrt{4}) - T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 0! + 7!$$

$$4765 := (F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) + 6!) \times 5 \\ := T(4!) + T(T(7) + T(6 + 5))$$

$$4809 := (-4 + F(F(8 - 0!))) \times F(F((\sqrt{9}!) \\ := (-\sqrt{4} + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times T(T(\sqrt{09}))$$

$$4766 := -F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(F(7)) - 6) \times F(F(6)) \\ := T(4!) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(6))/T(6)$$

$$4845 := -F(F(4)!)/F(8) + F(4 \times 5) \\ := (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(8)) + T(4!)) \times 5$$

$$4767 := (-F(4) \times F(7) + 6!) \times 7 \\ := -T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(7 + 6) + 7!$$

$$4851 := F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(8) \times \sqrt{5! + 1}) \\ := T(T(T(4)) - 8 + 51)$$

$$4769 := F(\sqrt{4}) + 7! - F(6) \times F(9) \\ := -T(T(4)) + 7! - 6^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$4867 := F(F(4)!) \times F(F(8) - 6) - F(7) \\ := T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + T(86) + T(T(7))$$

$$4786 := -F(F(F(4)!)) + 7! - F(F(8) - F(6)) \\ := -\sqrt{4} + 7 \times (-T(8) + 6!)$$

$$4869 := -4! + F(8) \times F(F(F(6))/\sqrt{9}) \\ := -T(T(4) + 8) + (T(6)/\sqrt{9})!$$

$$4787 := F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(7)) - F(8) + 7! \\ := -T(\sqrt{4} \times 7 + 8) + 7!$$

$$4883 := F(4) + 8 \times F(F(8) - 3!) \\ := 4 \times 8 + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(T(T(3)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4885 &:= -F(F(4)!) + F(8) \times F(8 + 5) \\ &:= T(T(\sqrt{4}))! - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(8 + 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4890 &:= (-F(4) + F(8) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})! + 0!))) \\ &:= (T(T(\sqrt{4}))! - T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times (9 + 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4891 &:= -\sqrt{4} + F(8) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})! + 1)) \\ &:= T(4) \times ((\sqrt{T(8)})! - T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4893 &:= F(4 + 8) \times F(9) - 3 \\ &:= \sqrt{T(T(4)) - \sqrt{T(8)}} \times (T(\sqrt{9})! - T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4895 &:= F(\sqrt{4} + 8) \times F((\sqrt{9})! + 5) \\ &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8))/9 + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4897 &:= F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(8) - 9) + 7! \\ &:= 4 \times T(8) + T(97) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4898 &:= (-F(4!) + 8!) \times F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(8)) \\ &:= T(T(4)) - 8 + T(98) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4914 &:= -F(F(F(4)!)) \times (\sqrt{9})! + (1 + F(4))! \\ &:= T(4 + 9) \times (-1 + T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4917 &:= 4! + F(9 - 1) \times F(F(7)) \\ &:= -T(\sqrt{4}) - (T(\sqrt{9}) - 1)! + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4925 &:= (F(4^{F(\sqrt{9})}) - 2) \times 5 \\ &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (T(\sqrt{9}))!) \times T(T(2)) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4934 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) + (F(9)/F(3))^{F(4)} \\ &:= -T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 9 \times T(3)! - T(T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4938 &:= (-4! \times F(9) + F(3)!) / 8 \\ &:= (T(T(T(4))) + \sqrt{9} - T(3)!) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \end{aligned}$$

$$4946 := -(F(F(4)!)/(\sqrt{9})!) + F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$:= -4 + T((9 - 4)! - T(6))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4948 &:= -\sqrt{4} + (-\sqrt{9})!! + F(F(4)!) / 8 \\ &:= -\sqrt{4} + T(T(9 + 4) + 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4949 &:= (F(F(4)!) - (\sqrt{9})!!) / F(F(4)!) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\ &:= -T(4 + 9) + (\sqrt{49})! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4950 &:= ((F(F(4)!) - (\sqrt{9})!!) / F(5 + 0!)) \\ &:= T(49 + 50) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4951 &:= (\sqrt{49})! - F(\sqrt{5! + 1}) \\ &:= T(4 + 95) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4955 &:= (4 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) - 5) \times 5 \\ &:= T(4 + 95) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4956 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (-F(\sqrt{9}) + 5!) \times F(F(6)) \\ &:= T(4 + 95) + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4959 &:= -\sqrt{F(4)^{F((\sqrt{9})!)} + (5 + F(\sqrt{9}))!} \\ &:= T(4 + 95) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4964 &:= (\sqrt{49})! - T(6) - T(T(4)) \\ &:= F(4)^{F((\sqrt{9})!)} - F(F(F(6))) - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4965 &:= (F(4)! + F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6))) \times 5 \\ &:= (T(4)! / \sqrt{9} + T(T(6))) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4972 &:= (-\sqrt{4} \times F(9) + 7!) \times F(2) \\ &:= (T(4^{\sqrt{9}}) + T(T(7))) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4978 &:= -F(4)! \times 9 + 7! - 8 \\ &:= -T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 9 + 7! - 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4982 &:= -4! - F(9) + (8 - F(2))! \\ &:= -T(T(4)) - \sqrt{9} + (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) / T(2))! \end{aligned}$$

$$4984 := (F(4)!! - F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(8) / F(4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(\sqrt{9})! + T(T(8)) - \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{4986} & := -F(4)! \times 9 + 8!/F(6) \\
 & := (T(T(4)) \times \sqrt{9} + T(T(8))) \times 6 \\
 \mathbf{4987} & := \sqrt{4} - F(9) - F(8) + 7! \\
 & := T(T(4)) - \sqrt{9} \times T(8) + 7! \\
 \mathbf{4992} & := -4! \times F(\sqrt{9}) + (9 - 2)! \\
 & := 4^{\sqrt{9}} \times T(9 + T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{4994} & := F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F((\sqrt{9})!) \times ((\sqrt{9})!! + 4!) \\
 & := T(4! + 9) \times 9 - T(T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{4997} & := -F(4) \times \sqrt{9} - F(9) + 7! \\
 & := -4 + T(\sqrt{9}) - T(9) + 7! \\
 \mathbf{5019} & := -F(F(5 + 0!)) + (1 + (\sqrt{9})!)! \\
 & := -T(5 + 0!) + (1 + T(\sqrt{9}))! \\
 \mathbf{5127} & := F(\sqrt{5! + 1}) - 2 + 7! \\
 & := T(\sqrt{5! + 1}) + T(T(T(2))) + 7! \\
 \mathbf{5139} & := 5! + (1 + 3!)! - F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 & := 5! + (1 + T(3))! - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{5147} & := 5! - F(1 + F(4)!) + 7! \\
 & := T(T(5) - 1) + \sqrt{4} + 7! \\
 \mathbf{5157} & := -F(5 - 1) + 5! + 7! \\
 & := -T(\sqrt{5 - 1}) + 5! + 7! \\
 \mathbf{5159} & := 5! - 1 + (5 + F(\sqrt{9}))! \\
 & := -T(5) - 1 + 5 \times T(T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{5187} & := ((5 + 1)! + F(8)) \times 7 \\
 & := T(\sqrt{5 - 1} + T(8)) \times 7 \\
 \mathbf{5267} & := F(F(5 + 2)) - 6 + 7! \\
 & := -\sqrt{-5 + T(T(T(2)))} + T(T(6)) + 7! \\
 \mathbf{5274} & := (5 + 2)! + F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 & := (T(5) - 2) \times T(T(7)) - 4 \\
 \mathbf{5279} & := (5 + 2)! + F(F(7)) + (\sqrt{9})! \\
 & := 5 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 7! + \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{5346} & := (-5 \times 3!! + F(4!))/F(6) \\
 & := (T(T(5) + 3) + T(T(\sqrt{4})))! \times 6 \\
 \mathbf{5379} & := 5! \times 3 + 7! - F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 & := 5! \times 3 + 7! - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{5394} & := (-5! + 3!!) \times 9 - F(4)! \\
 & := T(5 \times 3) \times T(9) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 \mathbf{5445} & := (5! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 45 \\
 & := (T(5) \times 4! + T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{5449} & := -(5 - F(\sqrt{4}))! + F(F(F(F(4)!)))/F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 & := (-5! + T(T(T(4)))) \times 4 - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 \mathbf{5469} & := (F(F(5 + F(4))) - F(6))/F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 & := -5! + 4! \times T(T(6)) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{5474} & := -5! + 4! \times F(F(7)) + \sqrt{4} \\
 & := 5! \times T(T(4)) - T(T(7)) - (T(T(\sqrt{4})))! \\
 \mathbf{5484} & := 5 + F(4)! + F(F(8))/\sqrt{4} \\
 & := (5! + 4!) \times T(8) + T(4!) \\
 \mathbf{5489} & := -5 + F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8))/F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 & := 5 \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 + \sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{5592} & := 5!/5 \times F(F(9 - 2)) \\
 & := 5!/T(5) \times (T(\sqrt{9})! - T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{5649} & := (-5! + F(6) \times F(4)!) + 9 \\
 & := T(5! - T(6)) - T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(\sqrt{9})!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5734 &:= -5 + 7! - F(F((3)!)) + F(4)!! \\ &:= -5 + 7! - T(T(3)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5739 &:= -F(-5 + F(7)) + 3!! \times F((\sqrt{9})!) \\ &:= -T(5) + 7! + T(3)! - T(\sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5744 &:= (5 - 7 + F(4)!!) \times F(F(4)!) \\ &:= 5 + 7! + T(T(\sqrt{4}))! - T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5749 &:= -5 + 7! + F(4)!! - (\sqrt{9})! \\ &:= T(57) + 4^{T(\sqrt{9})} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5786 &:= 5 + 7! + F(8) + 6! \\ &:= 5 + 7! + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5789 &:= -5! - 7! + F(F(8)) + \sqrt{9} \\ &:= -T(5) - T(T(7)) + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5794 &:= -5! - 7! + F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(F(F(F(4)!))) \\ &:= T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) - \sqrt{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5795 &:= (5 \times F(F(7)) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times 5 \\ &:= (-5 + T(7) \times T(T(9))) / 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5796 &:= F((-5 + F(7)) \times \sqrt{9}) / F(6) \\ &:= (5! - T(7)) \times \sqrt{9} \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5799 &:= 5 + 7! + (\sqrt{9})!! + F(9) \\ &:= -5 - T(T(7)) + T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5874 &:= 5! + 8! / 7 - F(4)! \\ &:= -5! + T(T(8)) \times (7 + \sqrt{4}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5886 &:= (5! \times 8 + F(8)) \times 6 \\ &:= 5! + \sqrt{T(8)} + 8 \times 6! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5897 &:= F(F(F((-5 + 8)!))) - 9 - 7! \\ &:= T(58) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}) + 7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5922 &:= F(-5 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times (F(2 + 2))! \\ &:= (-5! + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5928 &:= -5! + F((\sqrt{9} + F(2))!) - 8! \\ &:= (5 + \sqrt{9}) \times T(2 + T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5929 &:= ((5! + F(9)) / 2)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\ &:= (T(T(T(5) - 9)))^2 / 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5934 &:= -5! + (\sqrt{9})! - F(3)! + F(4!) \\ &:= 5 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) / 3)^{\sqrt{4}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5944 &:= 5! + (F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(4)!!) \times F(F(4)!) \\ &:= T(5) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 4 \times T(T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5946 &:= -5! + (T(T(9)) - 4!) \times 6 \\ &:= -\sqrt{5^{F((\sqrt{9})!)}} \times F(F(4)!) + F(F(F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5949 &:= F(5! / (\sqrt{9})!) - 4! \times F(9) \\ &:= (-5 + T(9 \times 4)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5950 &:= (5! - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \times 50 \\ &:= (5 + T(9)) \times (5! - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5968 &:= (5 + (\sqrt{9})!! + F(F(6))) \times 8 \\ &:= (5 + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 6!) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5979 &:= 5! \times F((\sqrt{9})!) + 7! - F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\ &:= T(5) \times (-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(7))) - T(T(\sqrt{9})) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5994 &:= (5! - 9) \times 9 \times F(4)! \\ &:= (T(5) - T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(9 \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5997 &:= 5! \times F((\sqrt{9})!) - \sqrt{9} + 7! \\ &:= -T(T(5) - \sqrt{9}) + T(T(9)) + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6045 &:= -6! + F(04 \times 5) \\ &:= (T(T(6 + 0!)) - T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$6084 := (6 \times F(-0! + 8))^{\sqrt{4}}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(T(6) - 0! - 8)^{\sqrt{4}} & & := -T(6) + 5! \times T(7 + \sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{6144} & := F\left(\sqrt{F(6) + 1}\right)^{F(F(4)!)} \times 4! & \mathbf{6624} & := F((\sqrt{F(6) + F(6)!}) / (F(2) + F(4)!)) \\
 & := 6 \times 1 \times \sqrt{4^{T(4)}} & & := T(T(6) + \sqrt{6-2}) \times 4! \\
 \mathbf{6192} & := 6! - 1 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) / 2 & \mathbf{6639} & := F(6)! / 6 - \sqrt{3^{F((\sqrt{9}!)}} \\
 & := 6 \times (T(T(1 \times 9)) - T(2)) & & := T(66) \times 3 + T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{6194} & := 6! + 1 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) / \sqrt{4} & \mathbf{6645} & := -6! / 6 + F(4 \times 5) \\
 & := 6 \times (-1 + T(T(9))) - T(4) & & := (T(6) \times T(6) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{6279} & := (F(F(6)) + 2) \times F(7) \times F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) & \mathbf{6669} & := (6! + F(F(6))) \times (6 + \sqrt{9}) \\
 & := T(T(6)) + T(2) \times T(7 \times 9) & & := (6! + T(6)) \times (6 + \sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{6462} & := (6 + F(4)) \times (6! - 2) & \mathbf{6684} & := (-\sqrt{6^6} + 8!) / F(4)! \\
 & := (6! - \sqrt{4}) \times (6 + T(2)) & & := (T(T(6)) + 6! + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{6464} & := (6! - \sqrt{4}) \times F(6) + F(4)!! & \mathbf{6699} & := (F(6)! - F(F(6)) \times (\sqrt{9}!) / (\sqrt{9}!) \\
 & := T(T(6) / T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(6)) - 4 & & := T(T(6)) \times (-6! / T(9) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{6467} & := (6 + F(4)) \times 6! - F(7) & \mathbf{6714} & := F(6)! / (7 - 1) - F(4)! \\
 & := (-6 / T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(T(6)) \times T(7) & & := -6 + (7 + 1)! / T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 \mathbf{6474} & := 6! \times \sqrt{4} + 7! - F(4)! & \mathbf{6739} & := F(F(F(6))) / F(7) \times F((3!)) + \sqrt{9} \\
 & := T(6 \times \sqrt{4}) \times (T(7) + T(T(4))) & & := T(T(6)) + T(7) + T(3!) \times 9 \\
 \mathbf{6479} & := (6! - F(\sqrt{4})) + 7! + (\sqrt{9}!! & \mathbf{6794} & := -T(T(6) + 7) + T(\sqrt{9}!) \times (T(4)) \\
 & := (T(T(6)) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(7) - T(9) & & := F(6 + 7) + 9^4 \\
 \mathbf{6499} & := (6! + \sqrt{4}) \times 9 + F(F(\sqrt{9})) & \mathbf{6885} & := F(-F(6) / 8 + F(8)) + 5! \\
 & := T(6) - \sqrt{4} + T(\sqrt{9}!) \times 9 & & := (T(-6 + T(8)) - \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{6549} & := -\sqrt{6! / 5} + F(4)^{F((\sqrt{9}!) & \mathbf{6891} & := 6 \times F(8) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - 1) \\
 & := -6 + 5! \times T(T(4)) - T(9) & & := T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times (9 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{6578} & := -F(6)! / 5! \times F(7) + F(F(8)) & \mathbf{6924} & := 6 \times (F(9)^2 - \sqrt{4}) \\
 & := (T(6) + 5) \times T(T(7) - \sqrt{T(8)}) & & := 6! + T(T(9)) \times T(T(2)) - T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 \mathbf{6579} & := -F(F(6)) + 5! \times F(F(7) - \sqrt{9}) & \mathbf{6938} & := F(F(6) + (\sqrt{9}!)) + 3^8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := 6 \times T(T(9)) + T(3)! + 8 & & := (T(T(7) - T(\sqrt{4}))) \times (T(7) - 5) \\
 \mathbf{6960} & := F(6)!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + (F(6) - 0)! & & \mathbf{7479} := 7 + \sqrt{4^{F(7)}} - (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 & := (T(6) + 9) \times (T(T(6)) + 0!) & & := 7! + T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{6966} & := (F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6!) \times 6 & & \mathbf{7488} := F(7) \times \sqrt{4!^{\sqrt{8+8}}} \\
 & := (6 + T(T(9))) \times 6 + 6! & & := (T(7) - \sqrt{4}) \times 8 \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{6969} & := 6 \times F(9) + F(F(F(6)) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) & & \mathbf{7491} := (F(F(7)) - F(4)!) \times (F(9) - 1) \\
 & := -T(T(6)) + (T(\sqrt{9}))! + 6! \times 9 & & := T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - T(T(9 \times 1)) \\
 \mathbf{6974} & := F(F(F(6)) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) + F(F(7)) - 4! & & \mathbf{7494} := F(7) \times 4!^{F(\sqrt{9})} + F(4)! \\
 & := (T(T(T(6) - 9)) + T(T(7))) \times \sqrt{4} & & := T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - T(T(9)) + T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{6984} & := 6! \times 9 + F(8) \times 4 & & \mathbf{7497} := F(7) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 9 + 7! \\
 & := 6! \times T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(8)) \times 4 & & := \sqrt{7^4} \times T(T(9) - T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{6990} & := (-F(F(6)) + (\sqrt{9})!!) \times (9 + 0!) & & \mathbf{7539} := (-7 + 5! \times F(F(3!))) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 & := (-T(6) + (T(\sqrt{9}))!) \times (9 + 0!) & & := (-7 + 5! \times T(T(3))) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{7249} & := 7! + F(2) + F(4)!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) & & \mathbf{7599} := (F(7) + 5! \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 & := 7! - 2 + T(T(\sqrt{4} + 9)) & & := T(-T(7) + 5!) + T(9 \times 9) \\
 \mathbf{7384} & := F(7) \times \sqrt{(F(3!) + 8!) \times F(F(4)!)} & & \mathbf{7629} := 7 \times F(F(6) \times 2) + (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 & := (T(T(7)) + T(3)! + (\sqrt{T(8)!})! \times 4 & & := (-T(T(7)) + 6!) \times T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{7444} & := (F(F(7)) \times F(F(4)!) - F(4)) \times 4 & & \mathbf{7679} := 7 \times (6! + F(7 \times F(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 & := (T(T(7)) \times T(T(4)) + \sqrt{4})/T(\sqrt{4}) & & := -T(T(7)) + (-T(6) + T(T(7))) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{7447} & := 7^4 + F(4)! + 7! & & \mathbf{7686} := 7! + F(F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 \\
 & := 7^4 + T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 7! & & := 7! + T(6) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{7449} & := F(7) \times (4! \times 4! - \sqrt{9}) & & \mathbf{7744} := (F(7) \times 7 - F(4))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 & := (T(7 \times T(4)) - \sqrt{4}) \times \sqrt{9} & & := 7! + (T(7) + 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 \mathbf{7464} & := F(F(7)) \times F(4) + F(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{4})) & & \mathbf{7749} := F(F(-7 + F(7))) + F(4)!/(\sqrt{9})! \\
 & := (-T(T(7)) - T(\sqrt{4}) + 6!) \times 4! & & := T(-7 - 7 + T(T(4))) \times 9 \\
 \mathbf{7475} & := 7! + (F(4)!! - F(F(7))) \times 5 & & \mathbf{7784} := 7! + (-7 + F(8))^{F(4)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(7) \times (-T(7) + \sqrt{T(8)} + T(4!)) \\
 \mathbf{7854} & := (F(F(7)) + F(8) + 5!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 & := (T(7) + \sqrt{T(8)}) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{5+4}))) \\
 \mathbf{7932} & := F(7) \times F(9 + 3!) + 2 \\
 & := (T(T(7)) + T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(3)) - T(T(2))! \\
 \mathbf{7944} & := F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 4! - \sqrt{4} \\
 & := (T(7) + \sqrt{9} + T(4!)) \times 4! \\
 \mathbf{7945} & := F(7)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + F(4)!^5 \\
 & := (T(7) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{7947} & := 7! + (\sqrt{9})!! + F(4)^7 \\
 & := 7! + T(\sqrt{9})! + T(\sqrt{4})^7 \\
 \mathbf{7949} & := F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 4! + \sqrt{9} \\
 & := -7 + T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{7974} & := F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(7) \times 4 \\
 & := T(T(7)) \times 9 + 7! - T(T(\sqrt{4}))! \\
 \mathbf{7986} & := F(F(7)) \times F(9) + 8 \times F(6) \\
 & := 7 \times T(T(9)) + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 6! \\
 \mathbf{7992} & := (F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(9) + 2 \\
 & := (7! - 9 - T(T(9))) \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{8145} & := 81 + F(F(4)!)/5 \\
 & := (\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(-1 + T(T(4))) \times 5 \\
 \mathbf{8247} & := F(8 + 2) + \sqrt{4^{F(7)}} \\
 & := -T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(2)) \times T(4! + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{8297} & := 8! / (2 + \sqrt{9}) + F(F(7)) \\
 & := 8 \times (T(2) + T(T(9))) - 7 \\
 \mathbf{8379} & := F(8)^{F(3)} \times (F(7) + (\sqrt{9})!) \\
 & := (T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times 9 \\
 \mathbf{8469} & := F(8) + F(4!)/6 + (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 & := T(8) \times (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(6))) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{8594} & := F(F(8)) + (-5! + F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 & := -T(T(8)) + T(5) \times T(\sqrt{9})! - T(T(T(4))) \\
 \mathbf{8684} & := F(F(8)) - F(6 + 8) \times F(4)! \\
 & := (-8 + T(6)) \times (T(T(8)) + \sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{8793} & := F(F(8)) + 7 - \sqrt{9} \times 3!! \\
 & := T(8) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{8799} & := (-8 + T(T(7)) + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 & := F(F(8)) + F(7) - \sqrt{9} \times (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 \mathbf{8932} & := (F(F(8)) - 9 \times 3!!) \times 2 \\
 & := (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) + \\
 & \quad + T(T(T(3))) / T(T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{8944} & := (8! / 9 - F(F(4)!)) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 & := 8 \times (T(T(9) + \sqrt{4}) - T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{8947} & := 8! / 9 \times \sqrt{4} - F(7) \\
 & := -(\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{T(\sqrt{4})} + T(T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{9048} & := (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \times F(F(4)! + 8) \\
 & := (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 0!) \times (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{9249} & := F(9)^2 \times F(F(4)!) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 & := 9 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(4) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{9253} & := -F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(F(F(2) + 5))^3 \\
 & := T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{T(2)} - 5 - 3 \\
 \mathbf{9260} & := F(F((\sqrt{9})!))^{F(-2+6)} - 0! \\
 & := T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{T(2)} - (6 \times 0)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$9262 := F(F((\sqrt{9})!))^{F(-2+6)} + F(2)$$

$$:= \sqrt{9} - 2 + T(6)^{T(2)}$$

$$9372 := (F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 3!) \times F(7) - F(2)$$

$$:= T(\sqrt{9})! + T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(2)))$$

$$9282 := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times (F(2) + F(8)^2)$$

$$:= T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(-2 + 8)^{T(2)}$$

$$9378 := (F(\sqrt{9}) + 3!) \times F(7) - 8$$

$$:= T(\sqrt{9})! + (T(3) + 7) \times T(T(8))$$

$$9284 := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + 2 + F(8)^{F(4)}$$

$$:= T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{T(2)} + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + \sqrt{4}$$

$$9381 := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + 3! \times F(8 - 1)$$

$$:= T(T(\sqrt{9}))^3 + (\sqrt{T(8)} - 1)!$$

$$9285 := F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - F(2)) + F(8) \times 5!$$

$$:= (-T(9) - 2 + T(T(8))) \times T(5)$$

$$9384 := (\sqrt{9})!! \times (-F(3!) + F(8)) + 4!$$

$$:= T(T(9) + 3) \times 8 - 4!$$

$$9294 := F(9) - F(2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))^{F(4)}$$

$$:= (T(T(9)) - 2) \times 9 - T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$9387 := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times (3!! - F(8) \times F(7))$$

$$:= (-T(9) + T(3)! + T(T(8))) \times 7$$

$$9324 := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times (F(F(3!))^2 + F(4))$$

$$:= (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(2)) \times T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$9397 := -F(\sqrt{9}) + (3!! + \sqrt{9}) \times F(7)$$

$$:= (T(T(9)) + T(3)) \times 9 + T(7)$$

$$9339 := F(9 - F(3)) \times 3!! - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))$$

$$:= T(9 + 3) + T(T(3))^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$9425 := F((\sqrt{9})! + F(F(4)!)) \times 25$$

$$:= (-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times 5$$

$$9345 := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times (F(F(3!) + F(4))) \times 5$$

$$:= T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times (T(3)! - T(T(4)) \times 5)$$

$$9438 := ((\sqrt{9})! + F(4)!) \times (-F(3!) + F(8))$$

$$:= (9 + 4) \times (T(3)! + \sqrt{T(8)})$$

$$9347 := (-\sqrt{9} + 3!! + \sqrt{4}) \times F(7)$$

$$:= 9 + (T(T(3)) + \sqrt{4}) \times T(T(7))$$

$$9447 := 9 + (F(4)! + F(4)!) \times F(7)$$

$$:= \sqrt{9} - T(4!) + 4! \times T(T(7))$$

$$9352 := -F((\sqrt{9})!) + 3!! \times (F(5 + 2))$$

$$:= T(T(\sqrt{9}))^3 + T(T(5) - 2)$$

$$9450 := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 450$$

$$:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5 + 0)$$

$$9354 := -(\sqrt{9})! + 3!! \times F(5 + \sqrt{4})$$

$$:= -T(\sqrt{9}) + T(3)! \times (T(5) - \sqrt{4})$$

$$9474 := 9^{F(4)} \times F(7) - F(4)$$

$$:= (-\sqrt{9} - T(4!) + 7!) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$9357 := -\sqrt{9} + 3! \times 5! \times F(7)$$

$$:= -\sqrt{9} + T(3)! \times (-T(5) + T(7))$$

$$9494 := F(F((\sqrt{9})!))^{F(4)} + F(9 + 4)$$

$$:= T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + (\sqrt{4} + T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{T(\sqrt{4})})$$

$$9369 := F(9 - F(3)) \times 6! + 9$$

$$:= (T(T(9)) + T(3)) \times (6 + \sqrt{9})$$

$$9495 := (F((\sqrt{9})!) / F(F(F(4)!)) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 5$$

$$:= T(9) \times (4! \times 9 - 5)$$

$$9497 := F(F((\sqrt{9}!))^{F(4)} + \sqrt{9} + F(F(7))) \\ := -9 + \sqrt{4} \times T(97)$$

$$9744 := (-\sqrt{9}!! + F(F(7)) \times 4!) \times \sqrt{4} \\ := T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(7 \times 4) \times 4$$

$$9498 := -((\sqrt{9}!! + 4) \times F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(8))) \\ := T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{T(\sqrt{4})} + T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))$$

$$9753 := F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - F(F(7)) - 5! \times F(3!)) \\ := 9 + T(T(7)) \times (\sqrt{-5 + T(T(3))})!$$

$$9534 := -F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 5 \times F(3!)^4 \\ := -T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(5 \times T(3)) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))$$

$$9772 := (F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) \times F(F(7)) - 7) \times 2 \\ := T(97) + 7! - T(T(T(2)))$$

$$9582 := (\sqrt{9}!) \times F(5!/8 + 2) \\ := (T(95) + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 2$$

$$9774 := (\sqrt{9}!) \times (7 \times F(F(7)) - \sqrt{4}) \\ := (-T(T(9) - T(7)) + 7!) \times \sqrt{4}$$

$$9594 := (\sqrt{9}!! \times 5!/9 - F(4)!) \\ := (\sqrt{9} + 5!) \times T(\sqrt{9} \times 4)$$

$$9786 := F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7 \times (-F(8) + 6!) \\ := (T(T(\sqrt{9})) - 7) \times ((\sqrt{T(8)!}) - T(6))$$

$$9599 := (\sqrt{9}!! \times 5!/9 - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \\ := (T(\sqrt{9}!) \times 5! - 9)/9$$

$$9793 := -9 + F(7) \times (F(9) + 3!!) \\ := T(97) + (T(T(\sqrt{9}))/3)!$$

$$9645 := (9 + F(6)!/F(F(F(4)!))) \times 5 \\ := (T(\sqrt{9}!) - T(T(6))/T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(5)$$

$$9849 := -(\sqrt{9}!! + F(F(8)) - F(F(4)! + F((\sqrt{9}!))) \\ := 9!/T(8) - T(4! - \sqrt{9})$$

$$9647 := (F((\sqrt{9}!)! - F(F(F(6))))/\sqrt{4} - 7! \\ := T(9) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(\sqrt{4}!)! - T(7))$$

$$9864 := 9!/T(8) - 6^{T(\sqrt{4})} \\ := (F(9) + F(8 + 6)) \times 4!$$

$$9667 := F(9) + (6! + F(F(6))) \times F(7) \\ := T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(6) \times T(6) + T(T(7))$$

$$9954 := F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) \times (-\sqrt{9}!) + 5! \times 4) \\ := T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times (9 + T(5!/4))$$

$$9699 := (-F((\sqrt{9}!)! + F(F(F(6))) \times 9)/(\sqrt{9}!) \\ := -\sqrt{9} + T(T(6)) \times (T(9) - \sqrt{9})$$

$$9974 := F(F((\sqrt{9}!))^{F(9)} - 7 + F(4)!) \\ := T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{F(9)} - 7 + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))!$$

$$9723 := (-\sqrt{9} + F(F(7)) \times 2) \times F(F(3!)) \\ := T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 7 \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(3)))$$

$$9981 := F(F((\sqrt{9}!))^{F(9)} + (\sqrt{8+1})! \\ := 9 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(8 \times 1))$$

$$9724 := F(9) \times F(7) \times (-2 + 4!) \\ := (T(\sqrt{9}!) + T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(4))$$

$$9983 := (\sqrt{9}!! + F(\sqrt{9}) + F(8)^3 \\ := (-T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(9) \times T(T(8))))/3$$

$$9740 := ((\sqrt{9}!! - F(F(7))) \times (F(F(F(4)!)) - 0!) \\ := -\sqrt{9} + T(T(7)) \times 4! - 0!$$

$$9984 := (\sqrt{9}!! + \sqrt{9} + F(8)^{F(4)})$$

$$:= 9 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(8)) + T(\sqrt{4})$$

$$:= (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) + 4$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9985 &:= F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) - 8 \times 5! \\ &:= T(9)/\sqrt{9} \times T(T(8)) - 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9995 &:= F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 9 - F((\sqrt{9}!) \times 5! \\ &:= (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9989 &:= F((\sqrt{9}!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} \\ &:= (-\sqrt{9} + T(9) \times T(T(8)))/\sqrt{9} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9996 &:= ((\sqrt{9}!) + F((\sqrt{9}!)) \times F(9) \times F(F(6)) \\ &:= (T(\sqrt{9}) + T(9) \times (-9 + T(T(6)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9993 &:= F(9) - F(F((\sqrt{9}!) + F((\sqrt{9}!)) + F(F(F(3!))) \\ &:= \sqrt{9} + T(9) \times (-9 + T(T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9998 &:= -9! + (F(9) \times (F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) + F(F(8)))) \\ &:= (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$9994 := -(\sqrt{9}!) + (F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9)^4$$

2.4.2 Reverse Order of Digits

• Symmetric

$$3840 := 0 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / F(F(3!)) = 0 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / T(T(3))$$

$$3841 := 1 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / F(F(3!)) = 1 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / T(T(3))$$

$$3842 := 2 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / F(F(3!)) = 2 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / T(T(3))$$

$$3843 := 3 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / F(F(3!)) = 3 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / T(T(3))$$

$$3844 := 4 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / F(F(3!)) = 4 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / T(T(3))$$

$$3845 := 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / F(F(3!)) = 5 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / T(T(3))$$

$$3846 := 6 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / F(F(3!)) = 6 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / T(T(3))$$

$$3847 := 7 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / F(F(3!)) = 7 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / T(T(3))$$

$$3848 := 8 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / F(F(3!)) = 8 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / T(T(3))$$

$$3849 := 9 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / F(F(3!)) = 9 + \sqrt{4} \times 8! / T(T(3))$$

$$4480 := 0 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4)) = 0 + 8! / (T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$4481 := 1 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4)) = 1 + 8! / (T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$4482 := 2 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4)) = 2 + 8! / (T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$4483 := 3 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4)) = 3 + 8! / (T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$4484 := 4 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4)) = 4 + 8! / (T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$4485 := 5 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4)) = 5 + 8! / (T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$4486 := 6 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4)) = 6 + 8! / (T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$4487 := 7 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4)) = 7 + 8! / (T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$4488 := 8 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4)) = 8 + 8! / (T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$4489 := 9 + 8! / (F(4) \times F(4)) = 9 + 8! / (T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(\sqrt{4}))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5490 &:= 0 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) = 0 + T(9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) \\
 5491 &:= 1 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) = 1 + T(9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) \\
 5492 &:= 2 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) = 2 + T(9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) \\
 5493 &:= 3 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) = 3 + T(9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) \\
 5494 &:= 4 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) = 4 + T(9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) \\
 5495 &:= 5 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) = 5 + T(9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) \\
 5496 &:= 6 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) = 6 + T(9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) \\
 5497 &:= 7 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) = 7 + T(9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) \\
 5498 &:= 8 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) = 8 + T(9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!) \\
 5499 &:= 9 + 9 \times F(F(4) \times 5) = 9 + T(9) \times (\sqrt{4} + 5!)
 \end{aligned}$$

• **Nonsymmetric**

$$\begin{aligned}
 42 &:= 2 \times F(F(F(4)!)) & & := T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(3)) - \sqrt{4} \\
 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 48 &:= 8 \times F(4)! & & 441 := F(F(F(1 \times 4)!))\sqrt{4} \\
 &:= 8 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) & & := (T(T(-1 + 4)))\sqrt{4} \\
 284 &:= \sqrt{(F(F(4)!) + 8!) \times 2} & & 442 := F(2) + F(F(F(4)!))\sqrt{4} \\
 &:= T(4!) - 8 \times 2 & & := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4)) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 239 &:= (\sqrt{9})! + F(F(3! + F(2))) & & 443 := F(F(3!))\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} \\
 &:= (-\sqrt{9} + T(3)!)/T(2) & & := T(T(3))\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{4} \\
 297 &:= F(F(7)) + F((\sqrt{9})!)^2 & & 444 := F(F((F(4)!))\sqrt{4} + F(4) \\
 &:= T((\sqrt{7+9})!) - T(2) & & := T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 4! + T(4!) \\
 339 &:= (\sqrt{9})!!/F(3) - F(F(3!)) & & 447 := -F(7) \times F(F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!! \\
 &:= T(T(9))/3 - T(3) & & := 7 \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(4!) \\
 398 &:= F(8) + F((\sqrt{9})! + F(3!)) & & 449 := F(F((\sqrt{9})!))\sqrt{4} + F(F(4)!) \\
 &:= -8 + T(T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))/3)) & & := T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times 4! - T(T(4)) \\
 399 &:= F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times (-\sqrt{9} + F(F(3!))) & & 459 := -F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + 5! \times 4 \\
 &:= 9 \times T(9) - T(3) & & := \sqrt{9} \times T(T(5) + \sqrt{4}) \\
 439 &:= -F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(3!))\sqrt{4} & & 464 := -\sqrt{4^{F(6)}} + F(4)!!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \sqrt{4} \times T(T(6)) + \sqrt{4} & & := 6! - \sqrt{4} + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{474} & := (4 + F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{4} & \mathbf{945} & := 5 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 9 \\
 & := (-T(4!) + 7!)/T(4) & & := (T(5) + T(4!)) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{483} & := F(F(3!)) \times (F(8) + \sqrt{4}) & \mathbf{979} & := F(9 + 7) - F((\sqrt{9})!) \\
 & := -T(T(3)) + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times 4! & & := T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(7) + T(\sqrt{9})! \\
 \mathbf{496} & := -F(6) + 9!/F(4)!! & \mathbf{984} & := F(4! - 8) - \sqrt{9} \\
 & := T(T(6)/\sqrt{9} + 4!) & & := T(4!) - T(8) + T(\sqrt{9})! \\
 \mathbf{594} & := F(4)!! - (\sqrt{9})! - 5! & \mathbf{993} & := F(F(3!) \times F(\sqrt{9})) + (\sqrt{9})! \\
 & := -T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(\sqrt{9})! - 5! & & := ((3 + T(T(9))) - T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{648} & := 8 \times \sqrt{F(4)^{F(6)}} & \mathbf{995} & := F(-5 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) + F((\sqrt{9})!) \\
 & := T(8) \times (4! - 6) & & := 5 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\
 \mathbf{664} & := F(4)!! - F(6)!/6! & \mathbf{0148} & := F(8) \times (F(4)! + 1) + 0! \\
 & := -\sqrt{4} + T(6 \times 6) & & := -\sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(T(4)))/10 \\
 \mathbf{696} & := 6! - \sqrt{9} \times F(6) & \mathbf{0188} & := F(8) \times (8 + 1) - 0! \\
 & := 6! - T(9) + T(6) & & := T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times (8 + 1) - 0! \\
 \mathbf{699} & := (9 - \sqrt{9})! - F(F(6)) & \mathbf{0193} & := F(3!) \times (\sqrt{9} + 1)! + 0! \\
 & := (9 - \sqrt{9})! - T(6) & & := 3 + T(9 + 10) \\
 \mathbf{699} & := (9 - \sqrt{9})! - F(F(6)) & \mathbf{0196} & := (F(6) + (\sqrt{9})!)^{1+0!} \\
 & := (9 - \sqrt{9})! - T(6) & & := 6 + T(9 + 10) \\
 \mathbf{714} & := -F(4)! + (-1 + 7)! & \mathbf{0245} & := (5! + F(4)) \times 2 - 0! \\
 & := -T(T(\sqrt{4})) + (-1 + 7)! & & := T(5)^{\sqrt{4}} + 20 \\
 \mathbf{734} & := F(\sqrt{4}) + 3!! + F(7) & \mathbf{0279} & := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(7) + (2 + 0)! \\
 & := T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(3)! - 7 & & := 9 \times (T(7) + T(2 + 0)) \\
 \mathbf{739} & := (\sqrt{9})! + 3!! + F(7) & \mathbf{0283} & := \sqrt{(F(3!) + 8!) \times 2} - 0! \\
 & := -9 + T(3)! + T(7) & & := -T(3) + T(8) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 0! \\
 \mathbf{746} & := 6! + \sqrt{4} \times F(7) & \mathbf{0284} & := 4 \times \sqrt{(8 - F(2))!} + 0!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := 4 \times (T(8) \times 2 - 0!) & & := (-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 4! + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0297} & := F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9})^{(2+0)!} & \mathbf{0482} & := -F(2) + F(8) \times (4! - 0!) \\
 & := -T(7) + T(T(9) - 20) & & := 2 \times ((\sqrt{T(8)})!/T(\sqrt{4}) + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0394} & := F(4)!!/F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(3!)) + 0! & \mathbf{0489} & := (\sqrt{9})! + F(8) \times (4! - 0!) \\
 & := T(4!) + 93 + 0! & & := T(T(9)) - T(T(8)) + (4 + 0)! \\
 \mathbf{0396} & := 6 \times \sqrt{9} \times (F(F(3!)) + 0!) & \mathbf{0493} & := 3!! + (\sqrt{9})! - F(F(F(4!) + 0!)) \\
 & := (T(6) + T(9)) \times T(3 + 0) & & := -3 + T(-9 + 40) \\
 \mathbf{0419} & := (F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 1) \times F(F(F(4!))) - 0! & \mathbf{0495} & := F(5 \times F(\sqrt{9})) \times (F(F(4!)) + 0!) \\
 & := T(\sqrt{9})! - 1 - T((4 + 0)!) & & := T(5) \times (9 + 4! + 0) \\
 \mathbf{0426} & := 6 \times \sqrt{F(2) + (F(4!) + 0)!} & \mathbf{0499} & := F(\sqrt{9})^9 - F(F(4!) + 0!) \\
 & := 6 \times (T(2) \times 4! - 0!) & & := T(5) \times (9 + 4! + 0) \\
 \mathbf{0427} & := \sqrt{7! + F(2)} \times F(4!) + 0! & \mathbf{0529} & := (F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + 2)^{\sqrt{5-0!}} \\
 & := T(T(7)) + T(2 + 4 + 0) & & := T(9 \times T(2) + 5) + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0463} & := F(F(3!)) + F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}} + 0! & \mathbf{0532} & := -2 + 3! \times F(\sqrt{5! + 0!}) \\
 & := T(T(3)) + T(6)^{\sqrt{4}} + 0! & & := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T((\sqrt{T(T(3))} - 5)!) + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0465} & := F(5 + F(6)) \times \sqrt{4} - 0! & \mathbf{0544} & := -(F(F(4!)) \times (F(F(F(4!))) - F(\sqrt{5! + 0!}))) \\
 & := T(5 \times 6 + 4 \times 0) & & := (4! + T(4)) \times (T(5) + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0467} & := F(7 + 6) \times \sqrt{4} + 0! & \mathbf{0547} & := F(7) + (F(4!) \times F(\sqrt{5! + 0!})) \\
 & := T(T(7)) + T(6) + 40 & & := 7 \times T(\sqrt{4! + 5!}) + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0475} & := (5 + F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{4} - 0! & \mathbf{0549} & := 9 \times (\sqrt{F(4)!! \times 5 + 0!}) \\
 & := T(5) \times T(7) + T(T(4 + 0)) & & := 9 \times (4 \times T(5) + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0478} & := -8 - F(F(7)) + F(4)!! - 0! & \mathbf{0567} & := 7 \times (-F(6) + F(\sqrt{5! + 0!})) \\
 & := \sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(7)) + T(T(4) + 0!) & & := T(7) \times T(6) - T(5 + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0479} & := ((\sqrt{9})! + F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{4} + 0! & \mathbf{0579} & := \sqrt{9} \times F(F(7)) - (5 + 0)! \\
 & := T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - T(7) + T(4! - 0!) & & := T(T(9)) - T(T(7)) - 50 \\
 \mathbf{0481} & := (-1 + F(8)) \times 4! + 0! & \mathbf{0589} & := F(-(\sqrt{9})! + F(8)) - F(F(5 + 0!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(8) - \sqrt{5-0!}) & & := \sqrt{9} \times T(T(5) + 7 + 0) \\
 \mathbf{0594} & := F(4)! \times 9 \times \sqrt{5! + 0!} & & \mathbf{0769} := (\sqrt{9})!! - F(F(6)) + 70 \\
 & := (T(4!) - \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{5-0!} & & := T(\sqrt{9})! + T(6) + T(7+0) \\
 \mathbf{0597} & := -F(7) + F(\sqrt{9} \times (5+0)) & & \mathbf{0792} := F(2) + (\sqrt{9})!! + \sqrt{7! + 0!} \\
 & := T(T(7) + T(\sqrt{9})) + \sqrt{5-0!} & & := 2 \times (-9 + T(T(7)) - 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0599} & := \sqrt{9! - F(9) \times 5! + 0!} & & \mathbf{0794} := F(4)!! + \sqrt{9} + \sqrt{7! + 0!} \\
 & := T(9)/9 \times 5! - 0! & & := \sqrt{4} \times (-9 + T(T(7+0))) \\
 \mathbf{0609} & := F(9+06) - 0! & & \mathbf{0798} := F(8) \times (\sqrt{9} \times F(7) - 0!) \\
 & := T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times (0! + T(6+0!)) & & := T(T(8)/\sqrt{9}) + (7-0!) \\
 \mathbf{0659} & := F(9) + \sqrt{5^{F(6+0)}} & & \mathbf{0853} := 3!! + 5! + F(8-0!) \\
 & := -T(9) - T(5) + 6! - 0! & & := T(3)! - 5! + T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0678} & := -F(8) + F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{F(6) + 0!} & & \mathbf{0867} := 7 \times F(F(6)) + (\sqrt{8+0!})!! \\
 & := -T(8) - 7 + 6! + 0! & & := T(7 \times 6) - T(8+0) \\
 \mathbf{0695} & := 5^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6! \times 0! & & \mathbf{0895} := (5! - F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 8 - 0! \\
 & := T(5) \times T(9) + T(6) - 0! & & := -5! + T(T(9)) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0709} & := (\sqrt{9})!! + 0! - F(7) + 0! & & \mathbf{0896} := (6! + F((\sqrt{9})!) \times (F(8) + 0!)) \\
 & := T(\sqrt{9}) + T(0! + T(7+0!)) & & := T(T(6)) + T(T(\sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{T(8)}) - 0! \\
 \mathbf{0718} & := -F(\sqrt{8+1}) + (7-0!)! & & \mathbf{0924} := 4 \times (-2 + F(F((\sqrt{9})! + 0!))) \\
 & := (\sqrt{T(8)})! - 1 - (7 \times 0!) & & := T(4+2) \times (T(9) - 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0734} & := F(4)! + F(3!) + (7-0!)! & & \mathbf{0932} := F(F(F(2) + 3!)) \times (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \\
 & := T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(3)! + 7 + 0! & & := (2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (\sqrt{9} + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0739} & := (\sqrt{9})! + 3!! + F(7+0) & & \mathbf{0935} := (5! - 3) \times F((\sqrt{9})!) - 0! \\
 & := -9 + T(3)! + T(7+0) & & := -5! + T(T(3)) + T(T(9)) - 0! \\
 \mathbf{0754} & := F(\sqrt{4+5}) \times F(F(7) + 0!) & & \mathbf{0944} := -4^{F(4)!} + ((\sqrt{9})! + 0!)! \\
 & := T(T(4)) \times T(5) - \sqrt{7! + 0!} & & := T(44) - T(9) - 0! \\
 \mathbf{0759} & := F(9) + 5 + (7-0!)! & & \mathbf{0945} := (5! - \sqrt{4}) \times F((\sqrt{9})!) + 0!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(5) \times (4^{\sqrt{9}} - 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0947} & := 7! + \sqrt{4} - T(90) \\
 & := F(F(7)) - F(4)! + (\sqrt{9+0})!! \\
 \mathbf{0951} & := (-1 + 5!) \times F((\sqrt{9})!) - 0! \\
 & := T(T(1+5)) + T(\sqrt{9+0})! \\
 \mathbf{0954} & := -F(4)! + 5! \times (9 - 0!) \\
 & := -T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 5! \times (9 - 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0956} & := F(6) \times 5! - \sqrt{9} - 0! \\
 & := T(T(6)) + 5 + T(\sqrt{9+0})! \\
 \mathbf{0957} & := F(F(7)) + 5 + (\sqrt{9})!! - 0! \\
 & := -T(7+5) + T(T(9+0)) \\
 \mathbf{0961} & := (-1 + 6)! \times F((\sqrt{9})!) + 0! \\
 & := -(-1 + 6)! + T(T(9) + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0963} & := F(F(3) \times F(6)) - (\sqrt{9} + 0!)! \\
 & := -3 + T(6) \times (T(9) + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0965} & := 5! \times F(6) + (\sqrt{9})! - 0! \\
 & := T(5) + T(T(6)) + (T(\sqrt{9}))! - 0! \\
 \mathbf{0967} & := 7 + F(6) \times ((\sqrt{9})! - 0!)! \\
 & := T(T(7)) + T(T(T(6)) / (T(\sqrt{9}) + 0!)) \\
 \mathbf{0968} & := 8 \times ((F(6) - \sqrt{9})! + 0!) \\
 & := 8 \times (T(6+9) + 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0973} & := (3!! - F(F(7))) \times F(\sqrt{9}) - 0! \\
 & := T(3)! + T(7) \times 9 + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0982} & := F(2 \times 8) - (\sqrt{9})! + 0! \\
 & := -2 - \sqrt{T(8)} + T(T(9) - 0!) \\
 \mathbf{0985} & := -5 + T(T(8) + 9 - 0!) \\
 & := F(-5 + F(8)) - \sqrt{9} + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0987} & := F(7 + 8 + (9 \times 0)!) \\
 & := -T(7) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(9)) + 0! \\
 \mathbf{0988} & := F(8 + 8) + (9 \times 0)! \\
 & := T(8 + T(8)) - \sqrt{9} + 0! \\
 \mathbf{1149} & := -(\sqrt{9})!! + F(F(F(4)!)) \times F(11) \\
 & := T(T(9) + \sqrt{4}) + T(T(T(1+1))) \\
 \mathbf{1259} & := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times 5! / 2 - 1 \\
 & := T(9) \times T(5+2) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1369} & := ((\sqrt{9})! + F(F(F(6)))) / F(3! \times 1) \\
 & := -9 + T(T(6) + 31) \\
 \mathbf{1379} & := (-\sqrt{9} + F(F(7))) \times 3! - 1 \\
 & := T(T(9)) + 7^3 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1394} & := -4 + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(F(3! + 1)) \\
 & := T(T(4) \times \sqrt{9}) \times 3 - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1398} & := (8 - F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(F(3! + 1)) \\
 & := ((\sqrt{T(8)})! - T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times (3 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1399} & := (\sqrt{9})! \times F(F(9 - F(3))) + 1 \\
 & := T(T(9) - \sqrt{9}) + T(31) \\
 \mathbf{1428} & := F(8) \times 2 \times F(F(F(4)!)) + 1 \\
 & := T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times (2 + T(T(4) + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1438} & := (8 - 3!) \times (F(4)!! - 1) \\
 & := (\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(3)! - \sqrt{4} \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{1443} & := 3!! + F(4) + (4 - 1)!! \\
 & := T(3)! + T(\sqrt{4}) + T(4 - 1)! \\
 \mathbf{1459} & := \sqrt{9^5} \times F(4)! + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := \sqrt{9^5} \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1467} & := (F(7) + 6!) \times \sqrt{4} + 1 \\
 & := T(7) + 6! \times \sqrt{4} - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1476} & := -6! + F(7)^{F(4)} - 1 \\
 & := 6 \times (-7 + T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1482} & := 2 \times (F(8) + (4 - 1)!) \\
 & := 2 \times T(T(8) + \sqrt{4 \times 1}) \\
 \mathbf{1529} & := (\sqrt{9}!! \times 2 + F(\sqrt{5! + 1})) \\
 & := -9 - 2 + T(T(T(5 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{1574} & := F(\sqrt{4}) + F(7) \times (5! + 1) \\
 & := T(\sqrt{4} \times 7) \times T(5) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1579} & := (\sqrt{9}!) + F(7) \times (5! + 1) \\
 & := -T(9) + T(T(7)) \times (5 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1584} & := 4! \times T(8) + (5 + 1)! \\
 & := F(4 + 8) \times \sqrt{5! + 1} \\
 \mathbf{1593} & := -3 + T(T(9) + \sqrt{5! + 1}) \\
 & := F(F(3!) + 9) - 5 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1597} & := F(-7 + (9 - 5 \times 1)!) \\
 & := T(T(7) \times \sqrt{9 - 5}) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1675} & := -5 + 7! / \sqrt{F(6)} + 1 \\
 & := T(57) + T(6) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1679} & := (-\sqrt{9} + 7!) / \sqrt{F(6)} + 1 \\
 & := T(\sqrt{9} \times T(7)) - T(61) \\
 \mathbf{1696} & := -F(6) \times (F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - F(F(6 + 1))) \\
 & := T(69) - 6! + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1779} & := (F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + F(F(7))) \times 7 + 1 \\
 & := 9 + T(T(T(7)) / 7 + 1) \\
 \mathbf{1793} & := F(3!) \times (-9 + F(F(7))) + 1 \\
 & := T(T(T(3))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(7)) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1799} & := (F((\sqrt{9}!) \times (-F((\sqrt{9}!) + F(F(7)))) - 1 \\
 & := T(\sqrt{9}) \times T((\sqrt{9} + 7)!) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1824} & := (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - 2) / (\sqrt{8 + 1})! \\
 & := T(T(4) \times T(T(2))) - T(\sqrt{8 + 1}) \\
 \mathbf{1833} & := (3! + F(3!)) / (F(8) + 1) \\
 & := 3 + T \left(\sqrt{T(3)! \times (\sqrt{T(8)} - 1)} \right) \\
 \mathbf{1839} & := F((\sqrt{9}!)! / F(F(3!)) - 81 \\
 & := T(T(9)) - T(T(T(3))) + T(T(8 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1843} & := -F(F(3!)) + F(F(4)!) \times F(F(8 - 1)) \\
 & := -T(3) + T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times 8 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{1889} & := (\sqrt{9}!! \times F(8) / 8 - 1 \\
 & := \sqrt{9} \times (T(T(8)) - T(8)) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1898} & := 8! / F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) - F(8) - 1 \\
 & := 8 + \sqrt{9} \times T(T(8) - 1) \\
 \mathbf{1899} & := F((\sqrt{9}!)! / F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) - F(8 \times 1) \\
 & := \sqrt{9} \times (\sqrt{9} + T(T(8) - 1)) \\
 \mathbf{1919} & := F((\sqrt{9}!)! / F(-1 + 9) - 1 \\
 & := (9 - 1)! / T(T(\sqrt{9})) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{1932} & := 2 \times T(T(3)) \times (T(9) + 1) \\
 & := F((F(2) + 3)!) / (\sqrt{9} + 1)! \\
 \mathbf{1943} & := 3!^{F(4)} \times 9 - 1 \\
 & := T(3)^{T(\sqrt{4})} \times 9 - 1 \\
 \mathbf{2099} & := 9 \times F(F((\sqrt{9}!) + 0!)) + 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times 9 - 0! + T(T(T(2))) & & := T(T(T(3))) \times (-4 + T(5)) + 2 \\
 \mathbf{2139} & := \sqrt{9} \times 3!! - F(F((1+2)!)) & \mathbf{2549} & := F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(F(F(4)!)) \times (5! + F(2)) \\
 & := T(93 - 1)/2 & & := -T(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5) \times T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2393} & := 3!! \times \sqrt{9} + F(F(3! + F(2))) & \mathbf{2564} & := \sqrt{4} + F(F(6)) \times (5! + 2) \\
 & := T(T(T(3))) + \sqrt{9} \times (T(3))! + 2 & & := \sqrt{4} + T(6) \times (5! + 2) \\
 \mathbf{2394} & := F(F(F(4)!)) \times (-\sqrt{9})! + (3+2)! & \mathbf{2574} & := (F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{5! + F(2)} \\
 & := T(4! + T(9)) - T(3 \times 2) & & := T(\sqrt{4}) \times (T(T(7)) - 5!) \times T(2) \\
 \mathbf{2438} & := F(F(8) - 3!) \times 4 - 2 & \mathbf{2578} & := -8 + F(F(7) + 5) + 2 \\
 & := \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(3+4)) + 2 & & := (\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(7) + T(5!/2) \\
 \mathbf{2458} & := F(8) \times (5! - F(4) + F(2)) & \mathbf{2579} & := -\sqrt{9} + F(F(7) + 5) - 2 \\
 & := T(8 \times 5) \times T(\sqrt{4}) - 2 & & := T(T(9) + T(7)) - 5! - 2 \\
 \mathbf{2459} & := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times (5! - F(4)) + 2 & \mathbf{2644} & := -\sqrt{4} + F(4)! \times F(F(6))^2 \\
 & := T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times 5! - T(T(4)) - T(T(2)) & & := T(T(T(4))) + 4 \times T(T(6) + 2) \\
 \mathbf{2474} & := -F(4)!! + F(-7 + 4!) \times 2 & \mathbf{2649} & := \sqrt{9} + F(4)! \times F(F(6))^2 \\
 & := 4! + T(\sqrt{7^4}) \times 2 & & := T(\sqrt{9} \times 4!) + T(T(6/2)) \\
 \mathbf{2494} & := F(F(4)!)/\sqrt{9} - F(F(4 \times 2)) & \mathbf{2694} & := F(4)!! + F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(6) \times 2) \\
 & := (T(4!)/T(\sqrt{9}))^{\sqrt{4}} - T(T(2)) & & := T(4!) \times 9 - T(6/2) \\
 \mathbf{2495} & := 5! \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 4! - F(2) & \mathbf{2743} & := (F(F(F((3)!)))/\sqrt{4} + F(7))/2 \\
 & := T(T(5) + T(9)) - T(T(4)) + T(T(2))! & & := T(T(T(3)) \times T(\sqrt{4})) + 7 + T(T(2))! \\
 \mathbf{2496} & := F(6)!/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + 4!^2 & \mathbf{2744} & := (F(4)! + F(F(4)!))^{\sqrt{7+2}} \\
 & := (-6 + T(9)) \times 4^{T(2)} & & := (4! - T(4))^{\sqrt{7+2}} \\
 \mathbf{2497} & := 7!/F(\sqrt{9}) - 4! - F(2) & \mathbf{2747} & := F(F(7)) - F(4)! + 7!/2 \\
 & := T(T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(4)) + T(T(2)) & & := -T(7) + T(\sqrt{4} + 72) \\
 \mathbf{2539} & := -F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(3!)) \times (5! + F(2)) & \mathbf{2792} & := 2 \times ((\sqrt{9})! \times (F(F(7)))) - 2 \\
 & := T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(T(3)) \times 5! - 2 & & := 2 + T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(7) + 2) \\
 \mathbf{2543} & := F(F(3!)) \times (F(\sqrt{4}) + 5!) + 2 & \mathbf{2793} & := -3 + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(F(7)) \times 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(T(3)) \times (T(9+7) - T(2)) & & := T(5 \times 2)^{\sqrt{0!+3}} \\
 \mathbf{2799} & := \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(F(7)) \times 2 & \mathbf{3066} & := (\sqrt{F(6)^6 - 0!}) \times 3! \\
 & := T(9+9) + T(72) & & := T(T(6+6)) - T(-0! + T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{2859} & := -F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + 5! \times (8/2)! & \mathbf{3155} & := -5 \times (F(\sqrt{5!+1}) - 3!!) \\
 & := 9 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) & & := 5 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{2879} & := F((\sqrt{9})!)/(-7 + F(8)) - F(2) & \mathbf{3194} & := \sqrt{4} \times F(F(9)/F(1 \times 3)) \\
 & := -T(T(9)) - T(T(7)) + (\sqrt{T(8)!}) \times T(T(2)) & & := T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 1 + T(3)! \\
 \mathbf{2884} & := (F(4)!! \times 8 + 8)/2 & \mathbf{3347} & := -F(7) + F(F(4)!)/ (F(3) \times 3!) \\
 & := \sqrt{4^8} + T(T(8) \times 2) & & := -T(7) + T(\sqrt{4} + 3)^3 \\
 \mathbf{2894} & := (F(4!)/F((\sqrt{9})!) - 8)/2 & \mathbf{3374} & := (\sqrt{4} + F(7))^3 - F(F(3)) \\
 & := 4 \times T(\sqrt{9})! + 8 + T(T(2)) & & := \sqrt{4} \times (7! + T(T(3)))/3 \\
 \mathbf{2896} & := 6! + F(9) \times 8^2 & \mathbf{3394} & := F(\sqrt{4}) + 9 \times F(3! + F(3!)) \\
 & := (6! + T(\sqrt{9})! + 8) \times 2 & & := T(T(T(4)) - \sqrt{9}) + T(3 \times T(T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{2898} & := F(8) \times (\sqrt{9})! \times (F(8) + 2) & \mathbf{3397} & := (F(F(7)) + \sqrt{9^{F(3)}})/F(3) \\
 & := \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(9) + T(T(8) \times 2) & & := T(79 + 3) - T(3) \\
 \mathbf{2943} & := (3!! + F(4!))/ (F((\sqrt{9})!) \times 2) & \mathbf{3399} & := 9 \times F((\sqrt{9})! + F(3!)) + 3! \\
 & := T(3^4) - T(9 \times T(2)) & & := 9 \times T(9 \times 3) - 3 \\
 \mathbf{2944} & := F(F(4)!) \times 4 \times 92 & \mathbf{3409} & := (F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) + 0! - F(4)!!)/3 \\
 & := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{T(4)}}} \times 92 & & := T(T(T(\sqrt{9}) + 0!)) + T(T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))))/3 \\
 \mathbf{2949} & := \sqrt{9} \times (-4 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!) \times 2)) & \mathbf{3443} & := (3 + 4)! - F(-4 + F(F(3!))) \\
 & := (\sqrt{9} - T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) & & := T(3 + T(T(4))) \times \sqrt{4} + T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{2959} & := (F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + 5!) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 2 & \mathbf{3447} & := 7! + 4 - F(-4 + F(F(3!))) \\
 & := (T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 5!) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) - 2 & & := 7! - T(\sqrt{4}) \times (T(4!) + T(T(T(3)))) \\
 \mathbf{2974} & := T(4! + 7) \times T(\sqrt{9}) - 2 & \mathbf{3459} & := -F(\sqrt{9}) + F(-5 + 4!) - 3!! \\
 & := F(F(F(4)!)) + (-7! + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))))/2 & & := (T(T(9)) + 5!) \times T(\sqrt{4}) - T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3025} & := F(5 \times 2)^{F(03)} & \mathbf{3469} & := F((\sqrt{9})!) + F((F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4})) - 3!! \\
 & & & := \sqrt{9} - 6! + T(T(T(4) + 3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3485 &:= 5 \times (-F(8) - \sqrt{4} + 3!!) \\
 &:= 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(4) + T(T(3))) \\
 3493 &:= F(3!)!/9 - F(4^{F(3)}) \\
 &:= -T(T(T(3)))/\sqrt{9} + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\
 3538 &:= (F(8) + F(3!)) \times (5! + F(3)) \\
 &:= T(T(8)) \times 3 + T\left(T\left(T\left(\sqrt{-5 + T(T(3))}\right)\right)\right) \\
 3574 &:= -\sqrt{4} \times F(7) + 5 \times 3!! \\
 &:= 4 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\
 3592 &:= (2 \times \sqrt{9})! \times 5 - F(3!) \\
 &:= -2^{\sqrt{9}} + 5 \times T(3)! \\
 3593 &:= (3!! - \sqrt{9}) \times 5 + F(3!) \\
 &:= -T(T(3))/\sqrt{9} + 5 \times T(3)! \\
 3595 &:= 5 \times (-T(\sqrt{9}) + 5 + T(3)!) \\
 &:= 5 \times (-F(\sqrt{9-5}) + 3!!) \\
 3596 &:= (6! - F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 + 3! \\
 &:= -\sqrt{6!/T(9)} + 5 \times (T(3))! \\
 3599 &:= (9 - \sqrt{9})! \times 5 - F(F(3)) \\
 &:= -9/9 + 5 \times T(3)! \\
 3684 &:= (4 + F(F(8) - 6)) \times 3! \\
 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (8 \times T(T(6)) - T(3)) \\
 3694 &:= (4 \times F(9) + F(F(F(6))))/3 \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) + \sqrt{9} \times 6! - T(3) \\
 3729 &:= F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 2 \times F(F(7)) \times F(3!) \\
 &:= 9 \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(3)) \\
 3795 &:= 5 \times (\sqrt{9} \times F(7) + 3!!) \\
 &:= T(5) + T(9) \times T(7) \times 3 \\
 3857 &:= (F(7) + 5!) \times (F(8) + F(3!)) \\
 &:= (-7 + T(T(5) \times \sqrt{T(8)})) - T(T(T(3))) \\
 3879 &:= -(\sqrt{9})!! + 7! - F(8)^{F(3)} \\
 &:= -T(T(9)) + 7! - \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(3)) \\
 3897 &:= (-F(F(7)) + (\sqrt{9})!!) \times 8 + F(F(3)) \\
 &:= 7! - T(T(9)) - T(8) \times 3 \\
 3924 &:= 4 \times (F(2 \times F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 3!) \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (-T(2 + 9) + T(3)!) \\
 3936 &:= 6 \times (-F(3)^{(\sqrt{9})!} + 3!!) \\
 &:= -6! + T(3 + 93) \\
 3949 &:= F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 4 \times F(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F((3)!)) \\
 &:= T(T(9 + 4)) - T(\sqrt{9}) - T(T(T(3))) \\
 3976 &:= F(6) \times (-7! + 9!)/3!! \\
 &:= T(T(6 + 7)) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(T(3))) \\
 3984 &:= (4! \times F(8) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times F(3!) \\
 &:= T(T(6 + 7)) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) - T(T(T(3))) \\
 3994 &:= 4^{(\sqrt{9})!} - F(9) \times 3 \\
 &:= -\sqrt{4} + T(T(9) - 9) \times T(3) \\
 4048 &:= 8 \times (4! - 0!)!/(F(F(F(4)!))!) \\
 &:= (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) - T(T(4))) \times (-0! + 4!) \\
 4134 &:= (F(4)!! - 31) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{4}) \times T(-3 + T(T(1 \times 4))) \\
 4157 &:= F(F(7) + 5 + 1) - 4! \\
 &:= T(T(7)) + T(T(\sqrt{5! + 1})) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 4187 &:= F(F(7) + (\sqrt{8 + 1})!) + F(4)! \\
 &:= T(T(7 + \sqrt{T(8)})) + 1^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4189 &:= (F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(F(8) - \sqrt{1 \times 4})) \\
 &:= \sqrt{9} + T(T(8 + 1 + 4)) \\
 4194 &:= (F(4)!! - F(9 - 1)) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(4) + T(91) - \sqrt{4} \\
 4197 &:= (F(F(7)) \times (\sqrt{9})! + 1) \times F(4) \\
 &:= 7 + T(91) + 4 \\
 4229 &:= F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - 2) + 2 \times 4! \\
 &:= T(92) + T(T(2)) - T(T(4)) \\
 4239 &:= F(9) + F(F(F(3!)) - 2) + 4! \\
 &:= T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(3)! - T(2)^4 \\
 4247 &:= -F(F(7)) + F(F(4)!)/(F(2) + F((F(4)!))) \\
 &:= T(T(7 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + T(T(2)) + T(T(4)) \\
 4254 &:= (F(4)!! - \sqrt{5! + F(2)}) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= -4! + T(5! - T(T(2) + 4)) \\
 4294 &:= F(4)! \times (\sqrt{9})!! - 2 - 4! \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(9 + T(2)) + 4 \\
 4295 &:= 5! - (\sqrt{9})! + F(-2 + F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 &:= T(5) + T(92) + \sqrt{4} \\
 4297 &:= 7! - (\sqrt{9})!! + F(2) - 4! \\
 &:= 7 + (T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4))) \\
 4299 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times (\sqrt{9})!! - F(2 \times 4) \\
 &:= T(9) + T(92) - 4! \\
 4307 &:= -F(7) + 03!! \times F(4)! \\
 &:= -7 + (-0! + T(3)!) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 4312 &:= -2 + (-1 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times (-1 + T(3)!) - \sqrt{4} \\
 4313 &:= (3!! - 1) \times 3! - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 &:= -T(3) - 1 + T(3)! \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 4315 &:= -5 + 1 \times 3!! \times F(4)! \\
 &:= -5 + 1 \times T(3)! \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 4319 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times 1 \times 3!! - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 &:= -T(\sqrt{9})! - 1 + (3 + 4)! \\
 4321 &:= (1 + 2)! \times 3!! + F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 &:= 1 + T(2) \times T(3)! \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4322 &:= F(2 + 2)! \times 3!! + \sqrt{4} \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times (2 \times 3)! + \sqrt{4} \\
 4326 &:= (6! \times T(2) + 3) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 &:= (6! + F(2)) \times 3 \times \sqrt{4} \\
 4329 &:= \sqrt{9} + (F(2) + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (2 \times T(3)! + T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 4339 &:= (\sqrt{9} + 3!!) \times 3! + F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 &:= (-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(3)!) \times T(3) + T(T(4)) \\
 4341 &:= (1 + F(4)! + F(F(3!)) - F(4)!! \\
 &:= T(T(-1 + 4)) + T(3)! \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 4342 &:= -2 + (4 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(\sqrt{4}) + T(3)!) + 4 \\
 4345 &:= \sqrt{5^4} + 3!! \times F(4)! \\
 &:= (T(5) + 4^3) \times T(T(4)) \\
 4349 &:= (\sqrt{9})! \times F(4)!! + F(F(3!)) + F(F(4)!) \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times (-4! + T(T(T(3)))) + \sqrt{4} \\
 4351 &:= 1 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 &:= 1 + (5 + T(3)!) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 4353 &:= (3!! + 5) \times 3! + F(4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (T(3)! + 5) \times T(3) + T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{4354} & := 4 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 & := -\sqrt{4} + T(5 + T(3))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 \mathbf{4358} & := 8 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 & := 8 + (5 + T(3)!) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 \mathbf{4359} & := 9 + (5 + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 & := \sqrt{9} + T(5 + T(3))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 \mathbf{4364} & := -4 + (6! + F(3!)) \times F(4)! \\
 & := T(\sqrt{4})^6 \times T(3) - T(4) \\
 \mathbf{4369} & := T(96 - 3) - \sqrt{4} \\
 & := (\sqrt{9})! \times (F(6) + 3!!) + F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{4374} & := F(4)^7 \times 3! / F(4) \\
 & := (-T(4) + T(7)) \times \sqrt{3^{T(4)}} \\
 \mathbf{4376} & := F(6) \times 7 + 3!! \times F(4)! \\
 & := T(T(6 + 7)) + T(T(T(3))) - \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{4385} & := F(F(F((-5 + 8)!))) - 3^{F(F(4)!)}) \\
 & := 5! + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(3)! - T(T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{4389} & := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times (F(F(F(8)/3)) - 4!) \\
 & := T(9) + \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(3)! + 4! \\
 \mathbf{4392} & := (2 \times (\sqrt{9})! + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 & := -T(2) + T(93) + 4! \\
 \mathbf{4393} & := F(F(F(3!))) - \sqrt{9^{F(3!)}} + F(F(4)!) \\
 & := (T(3)! + \sqrt{9}) \times T(3) + T(T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{4398} & := (F(F(8)/\sqrt{9}) + 3!!) \times F(4)! \\
 & := \sqrt{T(8)} \times (9^3 + 4) \\
 \mathbf{4399} & := F((\sqrt{9})!)/9 - 3^4 \\
 & := 9 \times ((T(\sqrt{9}))! - T(T(T(3)))) - \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{4414} & := \sqrt{4} \times (-1 + F(4)!/F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 & := (-4 + T(T(1 + T(4)))) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{4428} & := (F(F(8) + F(2)) + F(\sqrt{4}))/4 \\
 & := T(8) \times (T(2) + (T(4)/\sqrt{4})!) \\
 \mathbf{4438} & := (F(8) + 3!!) \times F(4)! - F(F(4)!) \\
 & := T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}) + T(4))) \\
 \mathbf{4439} & := -9 \times (3!! + F(4)) + F(F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 & := T(T(9)) \times T(3) - T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \\
 \mathbf{4444} & := (F(F(F(4)!)) + F(4)!!) \times F(4)! - \sqrt{4} \\
 & := 4 \times (T(T(\sqrt{4})))! + 4! + T(T(T(4))) \\
 \mathbf{4447} & := (F(7) + F(4)!!) \times F(F(F(4)!)) - F(F(F(F(4)!))) \\
 & := 7! + \sqrt{4} - T(4! + T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{4449} & := ((\sqrt{9})!! + F(F(F(4)!))) \times F(4)! + F(4) \\
 & := T(94) - 4 \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{4452} & := (F(F(2 + 5)) - F(F(F(4)!))) \times F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 & := T(2) \times T(54) - T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{4456} & := F(6)!/(5 + 4) - 4! \\
 & := T(T(6)) + (5! - T(T(4)))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 \mathbf{4459} & := F((\sqrt{9})!)/(5 + 4) - F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 & := \sqrt{9} \times T(54) + 4 \\
 \mathbf{4463} & := 3! \times (6! + 4!) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 & := -3 + T(T(6) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 \mathbf{4469} & := -9 \times 6! + F(F(F(F(4)!))) + F(4) \\
 & := T(96 - \sqrt{4}) + 4 \\
 \mathbf{4473} & := F(F(3) \times 7) + 4^{F(4)!}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7))/\sqrt{4} + T(4)) & & := T(T(8)) \times 9 - 6^4 \\
 \mathbf{4477} & := 7! + F(7) - 4! \times 4! & & \mathbf{4704} := 4! \times (0! + F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 & := 7! - (T(T(7)) + T(T(\sqrt{4}))) / \sqrt{4} & & := (T((4 - (0)!)) \times (T(7)^{\sqrt{4}})) \\
 \mathbf{4479} & := F((\sqrt{9})!) / (F(7) - 4) - F(\sqrt{4}) & & \mathbf{4719} := \sqrt{9} \times (F(17) - 4!) \\
 & := -T(T(\sqrt{9})) + T(7 - \sqrt{4}) \times T(4!) & & := -T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times 1 + 7! - T(4!) \\
 \mathbf{4493} & := F(3!) / 9 + F(F(4) + 4) & & \mathbf{4744} := (F(4)! / \sqrt{4} + F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)!) \\
 & := (-T(T(3)) + T(9) \times T(4!)) / T(\sqrt{4}) & & := \sqrt{4} - T(4!) + 7! + \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{4494} & := F(F(F(4)!)) \times (9 \times 4! - \sqrt{4}) & & \mathbf{4759} := -(\sqrt{9})! + 5 \times (F(F(7)) + F(4)!) \\
 & := (T(4!) + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times (4! - T(4)) & & := T(T(9)) \times 5 - T(T(7)) - T(4) \\
 \mathbf{4497} & := -F(7) - F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + F(4!) / F(4) & & \mathbf{4769} := -F(9) \times F(6) + 7! + F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 & := T(7) + T(94) + 4 & & := -\sqrt{T(\sqrt{9})^6} + 7! - T(T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{4499} & := (F((\sqrt{9})!) / 9 - \sqrt{4} + F(F(F(4)!))) & & \mathbf{4776} := 6! + F(7) \times F(7) \times 4! \\
 & := (-\sqrt{9} + T(9) \times T(4!)) / T(\sqrt{4}) & & := -T(T(6)) / 7 + 7! - T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \\
 \mathbf{4559} & := -F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - 5! + 5^{F(4)!} & & \mathbf{4783} := -F(3)^8 + 7! - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 & := T(95) - 5 + 4 & & := 3 + (\sqrt{T(8)!} + T(T(7)) \times T(4) \\
 \mathbf{4634} & := \sqrt{4} \times (3!! + F(F(F(6)) - 4)) & & \mathbf{4784} := F(4!) / F(8) \times F(7) / F(4)! \\
 & := -T(T(4 + 3)) + (T(6) / T(\sqrt{4}))! & & := -\sqrt{4^8} + (T(7) / 4)! \\
 \mathbf{4644} & := 4 \times (F(4)! + F(F(6))^{\sqrt{4}}) & & \mathbf{4786} := F(6)! / 8 - F(F(7)) - F(F(F(4)!)) \\
 & := T(4! \times 4) - 6 \times \sqrt{4} & & := (6! - T(8)) \times 7 - \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{4674} & := -F(4)! + F(7) \times 6! / \sqrt{4} & & \mathbf{4787} := 7! - F(8) - F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 & := T(4!) + 7! - T(\sqrt{6^4}) & & := 7! - T(-8 + T(7) + \sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{4679} & := (-F(\sqrt{9}) + F(7) \times 6!) / (\sqrt{4}) & & \mathbf{4791} := F(1 + 9 + 7) \times F(4) \\
 & := T(9) - T(T(7)) + (T(6) / T(\sqrt{4}))! & & := -T(1 + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 7! + 4 \\
 \mathbf{4696} & := F(6)! / 9 + 6^{F(4)} & & \mathbf{4792} := F(2) + \sqrt{9} \times F(-7 + 4!) \\
 & := T(T(6)) + T(96 - \sqrt{4}) & & := T(2 \times 9) \times T(7) + 4 \\
 \mathbf{4698} & := (F(8) \times \sqrt{9} + 6!) \times F(4)! & & \mathbf{4793} := F(3) + \sqrt{9} \times F(-7 + 4!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -T(T(T(3))) - T(\sqrt{9}) + 7! - T(4) \\
 \mathbf{4795} & := 5 \times ((\sqrt{9})! + F(F(7)) + F(4)!!) \\
 & := -5 + (9 + 7) \times T(4!) \\
 \mathbf{4807} & := 7! - F(0! + 8 + 4) \\
 & := 7! - T(T(\sqrt{T(08)})) - \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{4809} & := (T(\sqrt{9}) + 0!)! - T(T(8 - \sqrt{4})) \\
 & := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(F(-0! + 8)) - 4 \\
 \mathbf{4851} & := \sqrt{(1 + 5!) \times F(8)^4} \\
 & := T(-1 + T(5) + 84) \\
 \mathbf{4863} & := -F(-3! + F(F(6))) + F(F(8))/\sqrt{4} \\
 & := T(T(3)) \times T(T(6)) + 8 + 4 \\
 \mathbf{4869} & := (F(F(9) - F(F(6)))) \times F(8) - 4! \\
 & := T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(6)) + 8 + T(4) \\
 \mathbf{4874} & := F(\sqrt{4} + F(7)) \times 8 - F(4)! \\
 & := \sqrt{4} \times T(T(7)) \times \sqrt{T(8) + \sqrt{4}} \\
 \mathbf{4879} & := F((\sqrt{9})!) \times F(7 + 8) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 & := -T(T(9)) + 7! - T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 \mathbf{4883} & := F(-3! + F(8)) \times 8 + F(4) \\
 & := T(T(T(3))) \times T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + 8 \times 4 \\
 \mathbf{4885} & := F(5 + 8) \times F(8) - F(F(4)!) \\
 & := T(T(5 + 8)) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + (T(T(\sqrt{4})))! \\
 \mathbf{4891} & := F(F(1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(8) - \sqrt{4} \\
 & := 1 + ((T(\sqrt{9}))! - T(T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times T(4) \\
 \mathbf{4898} & := F(F(8)) \times F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 8! - F(4!) \\
 & := -8 + T(98) + T(T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{4917} & := F(F(7)) \times F(-1 + 9) + 4! \\
 & := 7! - (-1 + T(\sqrt{9}))! - T(\sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{4925} & := 5 \times (-2 + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \\
 & := -T(5) + T(T(2))! \times 9 - T(T(T(4))) \\
 \mathbf{4934} & := F(F(F(4)!)) + (F(3!) + 9)^{F(4)} \\
 & := -T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(3)! \times 9 - T(T(T(4))) \\
 \mathbf{4946} & := (6 + F(\sqrt{4}))! - 94 \\
 & := T((T(6) - T(4)) \times 9) - 4 \\
 \mathbf{4948} & := (8! - F(4)!!) / F((\sqrt{9})!) - \sqrt{4} \\
 & := T(8 + T(4 + 9)) - \sqrt{4} \\
 \mathbf{4949} & := (- (\sqrt{9})!! + F(F(4)!)) / F((\sqrt{9})!) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 & := -T(9 + 4) + (9 - \sqrt{4})! \\
 \mathbf{4955} & := 5 \times (F(-5 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) + 4) \\
 & := 5 + T(5 + 94) \\
 \mathbf{4959} & := (F(\sqrt{9}) + 5)! - \sqrt{9^4} \\
 & := 9 + T(5 + 94) \\
 \mathbf{4964} & := -T(T(4)) - T(6) + (9 - \sqrt{4})! \\
 & := F(4)^{F(6)} - F(F(9)/\sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{4965} & := (5! + F(6)! - (\sqrt{9})!!) / F(F(4)!) \\
 & := -T(56) + 9^4 \\
 \mathbf{4969} & := -9!/6! + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) / \sqrt{4} \\
 & := 9!/6! + T(94) \\
 \mathbf{4972} & := F(2) \times 7! - F(9) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 & := -2 + 7! - T(9 + \sqrt{4}) \\
 \mathbf{4978} & := -8 + 7! - 9 \times F(4)! \\
 & := -8 + 7! - 9 \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) \\
 \mathbf{4979} & := -F(9) + 7! - \sqrt{9} - 4!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -T(9) + 7! - T(\sqrt{9}) - T(4) \\
 \mathbf{4982} & := (-F(2) + 8)! - F(9) - 4! \\
 & := -T(2) + (T(\sqrt{T(8)})/\sqrt{9})! - T(T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{4984} & := (F(4)!! - 8) \times (9 - \sqrt{4}) \\
 & := (T(4)! - 8!)/(\sqrt{9 \times 4})! \\
 \mathbf{4986} & := F(6)!/8 - 9 \times F(4)! \\
 & := 6! \times \sqrt{T(8)} + T(9 \times 4) \\
 \mathbf{4987} & := 7! - F(8) - F(9) + \sqrt{4} \\
 & := 7! - \sqrt{(8 + T(9))^{\sqrt{4}}} \\
 \mathbf{4988} & := (-F(F(8)) + 8!/\sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 & := 8!/8 + \sqrt{9} - T(T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{4992} & := (-2 + 9)! - F(\sqrt{9}) \times 4! \\
 & := 2^{T(\sqrt{9})} \times T(\sqrt{9} \times 4) \\
 \mathbf{4994} & := (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times ((\sqrt{9})!! + 4!) \\
 & := T(4! + 9) \times 9 - T(T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{4997} & := 7! - F(9) - \sqrt{9\sqrt{4}} \\
 & := 7! + T(\sqrt{9}) - T(9) - 4 \\
 \mathbf{5019} & := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! - F(F(0! + 5)) \\
 & := (T(\sqrt{9}) + 1)! - T(0! + 5) \\
 \mathbf{5038} & := (F(8)/3)! - \sqrt{-0! + 5} \\
 & := (T(\sqrt{T(8)})/3)! - \sqrt{\sqrt{0! + T(5)}} \\
 \mathbf{5127} & := 7! - 2 + F(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) \\
 & := 7! + T(T(T(2))) + T(\sqrt{1 + 5!}) \\
 \mathbf{5139} & := -F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + (3! + 1)! + 5! \\
 & := -T(T(\sqrt{9})) + (T(3) + 1)! + 5! \\
 \mathbf{5147} & := 7! - F(F(4)! + 1) + 5! \\
 & := 7! + \sqrt{4} + T(-1 + T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{5157} & := 7! - F(5 - 1) + 5! \\
 & := 7! - T(\sqrt{5 - 1}) + 5! \\
 \mathbf{5159} & := (F(\sqrt{9}) + 5)! - 1 + 5! \\
 & := T(T(9)) \times 5 - 1 - T(5) \\
 \mathbf{5187} & := 7 \times (F(8) + (1 + 5)!) \\
 & := 7 \times T(T(8) + \sqrt{-1 + 5}) \\
 \mathbf{5267} & := F(F(7)) - 6 + (2 + 5)! \\
 & := 7! + T(T(6)) - \sqrt{T(T(T(2)))} - 5 \\
 \mathbf{5279} & := (\sqrt{9})! + F(F(7)) + (2 + 5)! \\
 & := T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 7! + T(2) + 5 \\
 \mathbf{5334} & := (F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F(F(3!)) + F(F(F(3) + 5)))) \\
 & := T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) + T(T(3)) \times 3^5 \\
 \mathbf{5346} & := (F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 3^5 \\
 & := 6 \times (T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + T(3 + T(5))) \\
 \mathbf{5349} & := (F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) - F(F(4)!)) / F(3) - 5! \\
 & := \sqrt{9} \times (T(T(T(4))) + 3^5) \\
 \mathbf{5379} & := \sqrt{9} + 7! + F(3)! / 5! \\
 & := -T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 7! + 3 \times 5! \\
 \mathbf{5394} & := -F(4)! + 9 \times (3!! - 5!) \\
 & := T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(T(3)) - 5)) \\
 \mathbf{5439} & := (-F(9) + F(F(F(3!))) / F(\sqrt{4 + 5})) \\
 & := T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{4 + 5})) \\
 \mathbf{5445} & := (5! + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 45 \\
 & := (T(5) \times 4! + T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5449 &:= F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) / \sqrt{4} - (-F(\sqrt{4}) + 5)! \\ &:= -T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + 4 \times (T(T(T(4)))) - 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5794 &:= -F(4!) / 9 + F(F(F(7) - 5)) \\ &:= -\sqrt{4} + T(T(9)) \times T(7) / 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5469 &:= (F((\sqrt{9}!) - F(F(F(6)))) / (F(4) - 5) \\ &:= T(9) + T(T(6)) \times 4! - 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5795 &:= 5 \times (-\sqrt{9}!) + F(F(7)) \times 5 \\ &:= (-5 + T(T(9)) \times T(7)) / 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5474 &:= 4! \times F(F(7)) + \sqrt{4} - 5! \\ &:= -T(T(\sqrt{4}))! - T(T(7)) + T(T(4)) \times 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5796 &:= F(F(6) \times \sqrt{9}) / (F(7) - 5) \\ &:= -T(6) \times \sqrt{9} \times (T(7) - 5!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5489 &:= F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) + F(F(8)) / \sqrt{4} - 5 \\ &:= -T(T(\sqrt{9} + 8)) + T(T(T(4))) \times 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5799 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! + F(9) + 7! + 5 \\ &:= T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(9)) - T(T(7)) - 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5635 &:= -5! + F(3!) \times 6! - 5 \\ &:= T(T(5) \times T(3)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{T(6) - 5}))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5846 &:= -6! + F(4)^8 + 5 \\ &:= -6! + T(\sqrt{4})^8 + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5649 &:= 9 + F(4)!! \times F(6) - 5! \\ &:= (T(\sqrt{9}))! - T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + T(-T(6) + 5!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5894 &:= F(4!) - F(9) - 8! - 5! \\ &:= -4^{T(\sqrt{9})} + T(T(8)) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5728 &:= F(8)^2 \times F(7) - 5 \\ &:= T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times T(2) + 7! - 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5922 &:= F(2 + 2)! \times F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - 5 \\ &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(2) + 9)) - 5!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5734 &:= F(4)!! - F(F(3!)) + 7! - 5 \\ &:= T(T(\sqrt{4}))! - T(T(3)) + 7! + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5928 &:= -8! + F((F(2) + \sqrt{9})!) - 5! \\ &:= 8 \times T(-2 + T(9) - 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5739 &:= F((\sqrt{9}!) \times 3!! - F(F(7) - 5) \\ &:= (T(9))^3 - 7! / T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5934 &:= F(4!) - F(3)! + (\sqrt{9})! - 5! \\ &:= T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times T(T(T(3))) / 9 + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5744 &:= (F(4)!! - \sqrt{4}) \times (F(7) - 5) \\ &:= T(T(\sqrt{4}))! - T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + 7! + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5944 &:= (F(4)!! + F(F(4)!)) \times F((\sqrt{9}!) + 5! \\ &:= 4 \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) + T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5748 &:= 8 \times F(4)!! - 7 - 5 \\ &:= \sqrt{T(8)} \times (T(T(4)) + T(7! / 5!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5946 &:= 6 \times (4 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) - 5)) \\ &:= 6 \times (-4! + T(T(9))) - 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5749 &:= (\sqrt{9})!! - F(4)! + 7! - 5 \\ &:= T(\sqrt{9})! + 4 + 7! - T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5949 &:= F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) + F(4!) - F((\sqrt{9})!) - 5! \\ &:= 9 \times (T(4 \times 9) - 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5789 &:= F(9) + 8! / 7 - 5 \\ &:= T(T(9)) \times \sqrt{T(8)} - T(T(7)) - T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5968 &:= 8 \times (F(F(6)) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 5) \\ &:= 8 \times (6! + T(T(\sqrt{9})) + 5) \end{aligned}$$

$$5979 := -F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) + 7! + F((\sqrt{9}!) \times 5!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -T(T(\sqrt{9})) + (T(T(7)) - T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(5) & & := (T(T(4)) + T(7)) \times T(\sqrt{4} \times 6) \\
 \mathbf{5997} & := 7! - \sqrt{9} + F((\sqrt{9})!) \times 5! & & \mathbf{6495} := -5 \times F(-F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(F(4)!))) + F(6)! \\
 & := 7! + T(T(9)) - T(-\sqrt{9} + T(5)) & & := T(5) + \sqrt{9\sqrt{4}} \times 6! \\
 \mathbf{6045} & := F(5 \times 4) - (06)! & & \mathbf{6498} := -F(8) \times \sqrt{9} + F(4)^{F(6)} \\
 & := T(5) \times (-T(\sqrt{4}) + T(T(0! + 6))) & & := T(8) + 9 \times (-\sqrt{4} + 6!) \\
 \mathbf{6194} & := F(F(F(F(4)!)))/F(\sqrt{9}) + 1 + 6! & & \mathbf{6499} := F(F(\sqrt{9})) + 9 \times (\sqrt{4} + (6)!) \\
 & := -T(4) + (T(T(9)) - 1) \times 6 & & := 9 \times T(\sqrt{9})! - \sqrt{4} + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{6237} & := (F(F(7)) + F(3!)^2) \times F(F(6)) & & \mathbf{6578} := -8! \times F(7)/5! + F(F(F(6))) \\
 & := T(7 \times 3) \times \sqrt{T(2)^6} & & := T(-\sqrt{T(8)} + T(7)) \times (5 + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{6247} & := -F(F(7)) + F(4)^2 \times 6! & & \mathbf{6579} := F(\sqrt{9} + 7) \times 5! - F(F(6)) \\
 & := 7 + T(\sqrt{4}) \times (T(2^6)) & & := T(T(9)) \times 7 - T(T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{6279} & := F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(7) \times (2 + F(F(6))) & & \mathbf{6624} := F(4!)/(F(2) + \sqrt{6 \times 6}) \\
 & := T(9 \times 7) \times T(2) + T(T(6)) & & := T(\sqrt{4}) \times (-T(2) + T(66)) \\
 \mathbf{6441} & := -(1 + 4)! + F(4)^{F(6)} & & \mathbf{6639} := -9^{F(3)} + F(6)!/6 \\
 & := T(T(-1 + T(4))) \times T(T(\sqrt{4})) + T(T(6)) & & := T(\sqrt{9}) + 3 \times T(66) \\
 \mathbf{6444} & := F(4)^{\sqrt{4}} \times (-4 + 6!) & & \mathbf{6645} := F(5 \times 4) - 6!/6 \\
 & := T(4!) + \sqrt{4^{T(4)}} \times 6 & & := (T(5) \times (\sqrt{4} + (T(6) \times T(6)))) \\
 \mathbf{6448} & := 8 \times (F(4)!! - 4) + 6! & & \mathbf{6669} := 9 \times (F(F(6)) + (\sqrt{6 \times 6})!) \\
 & := (-8 + T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times T(T(4) + T(6)) & & := (\sqrt{9} + (6)) \times (6! + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{6462} & := (-2 + 6!) \times (F(4) + 6) & & \mathbf{6698} := (8! - (\sqrt{9})!)/6 - F(F(6)) \\
 & := (T(2) + 6) \times (-\sqrt{4} + 6!) & & := (8! - T(\sqrt{9}))/6 - T(6) \\
 \mathbf{6464} & := F(4)!! - F(6) \times (\sqrt{4} - 6!) & & \mathbf{6714} := -F(4)! + (1 + 7)!/6 \\
 & := -4 + T(T(6)/T(\sqrt{4})) \times T(T(6)) & & := -T(T(\sqrt{4})) + (1 + 7)!/6 \\
 \mathbf{6467} & := -F(7) + (6 + F(4)) \times 6! & & \mathbf{6739} := F((\sqrt{9})!)/3! + F(7) + 6 \\
 & := T(7) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))/6 & & := 9 \times T(3)! + T(7) + T(T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{6474} & := -F(4)! + (F(7) - 4) \times 6! & & \mathbf{6783} := (3!!/8 + F(F(7))) \times F(F(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (3\sqrt{T(8)} - T(T(7))) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{6794} & := F(4)^{F((\sqrt{9})!)} + F(7 + 6) \\
 & := T(4) \times (T(\sqrt{9}))! - T(7 + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{6798} & := 8!/(\sqrt{9})! + F(7) \times 6 \\
 & := \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(9)) + T(7) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{6885} & := 5! + F(F(8) - F(8 - 6)) \\
 & := -T(5) \times (\sqrt{T(8)} - T(T(8) - 6)) \\
 \mathbf{6888} & := 8 \times F(8) + 8!/6 \\
 & := (((8)!/\sqrt{T(8)}) + (8 \times (6))) \\
 \mathbf{6891} & := F(-1 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) + F(8) \times 6 \\
 & := (1 + 9) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{6928} & := -8! \times 2 + F((\sqrt{9})!) \times F(F(F(6))) \\
 & := (\sqrt{T(8)})! - 2 + T(T(9)) \times 6 \\
 \mathbf{6933} & := F(-F(F(3)) + F(F(3!))) + F((\sqrt{9})!) \times F(F(6)) \\
 & := 3 + T(3) \times T(T(9)) + 6! \\
 \mathbf{6938} & := F(8 + 3!) + \sqrt{9^{F(6)}} \\
 & := 8 + T(3) \times T(T(9)) + 6! \\
 \mathbf{6966} & := 6 \times (F(F(6))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + 6!) \\
 & := (T(6) \times 6 + T(T(9))) \times 6 \\
 \mathbf{6969} & := F(9) \times 6 + F(-F(F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(6))) \\
 & := (T(\sqrt{9}))! - T(T(6)) + 9 \times 6! \\
 \mathbf{6974} & := F(F(F(4)!)) + F(F(7)) + F((\sqrt{9})!)/6 \\
 & := \sqrt{4} \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(-9 + T(6)))) \\
 \mathbf{6984} & := 4! \times F(8) + 9 \times 6! \\
 & := 4! \times (\sqrt{T(8)} \times T(9) + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{7245} & := 5 \times F(F(F(4)!))^2 + 7! \\
 & := (5 + \sqrt{4}) \times T(T(2 + 7)) \\
 \mathbf{7384} & := \sqrt{F(F(4)! \times (8! + F(3!)))} \times F(7) \\
 & := 4 \times ((\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(3)! + T(T(7))) \\
 \mathbf{7441} & := (1 + F(4)!)^4 + 7! \\
 & := (1 + T(T(\sqrt{4})))^4 + 7! \\
 \mathbf{7447} & := 7^4 + F(4)! + 7! \\
 & := 7^4 + T(T(\sqrt{4})) + 7! \\
 \mathbf{7449} & := (-\sqrt{9} + 4! \times 4!) \times F(7) \\
 & := \sqrt{9} \times (-\sqrt{4} + T(T(4) \times 7)) \\
 \mathbf{7464} & := F(F(4)!) + (F(6) + 4!) \times F(F(7)) \\
 & := 4! \times (6! - T(\sqrt{4}) - T(T(7))) \\
 \mathbf{7475} & := 5 \times (-F(F(7)) + F(4)!) + 7! \\
 & := (-5 + T(7)) \times T(-T(\sqrt{4}) + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{7479} & := F(\sqrt{9})^{F(7)} - F(4)!! + 7 \\
 & := T(\sqrt{9}) \times T(T(7)) + T(\sqrt{4}) + 7! \\
 \mathbf{7488} & := (\sqrt{8 + 8})! \times 4! \times F(7) \\
 & := 8 \times T(8) \times (-\sqrt{4} + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{7491} & := (1 - F(9)) \times (F(4)! - F(F(7))) \\
 & := -1 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{7494} & := F(4!)/(\sqrt{9})! - F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(7)) \\
 & := T(T(4)) \times T(9) - T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) + 7! \\
 \mathbf{7497} & := F(7) \times 9 \times F(F(F(4)!)) + 7! \\
 & := (T(7) + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \times T(4! - 7) \\
 \mathbf{7539} & := \sqrt{9} \times (F(F(3!)) \times 5! - 7) \\
 & := \sqrt{9} \times (T(T(3)) \times 5! - 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7599 &:= \sqrt{9} \times (F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) \times 5! + F(7)) \\ &:= T(9 \times 9) + T(5! - T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7629 &:= (\sqrt{9}!! + F(2 \times F(6))) \times 7 \\ &:= (T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times (-6! + T(T(7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7665 &:= \sqrt{5^6} \times F(F(6)) + 7! \\ &:= \sqrt{5^6} \times T(6) + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7679 &:= ((\sqrt{9}!! + F(-7 + F(F(6)))) \times 7 \\ &:= T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times (T(T(7)) - T(6)) - T(T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7686 &:= F(F(6)) \times F(8) \times 6 + 7! \\ &:= T(6) \times \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(6) + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7694 &:= F(4!) / (\sqrt{9}!) - F(F(6)) - F(7) \\ &:= T(4!) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}} - T(T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7749 &:= F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) \times (-F(F(4)!) + F(7 + 7)) \\ &:= 9 \times T(T(T(4))) - 7 - 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7759 &:= \sqrt{9} \times F(5 + F(7)) + 7 \\ &:= T(T(\sqrt{9}!)) / (T(5)! \times 7!) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7844 &:= F(F(F((F(4)!))) - (F(4)! + 8!) / F(7) \\ &:= (-T(4) + T(T(T(T(\sqrt{4})))) \times (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7854 &:= F(F((F(4)!)) \times (5! + F(8) + F(F(7))) \\ &:= T(T(T(\sqrt{4+5}))) \times (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7899 &:= -F(F((\sqrt{9}!)) + (\sqrt{9} + 8)! / 7! \\ &:= -T(T(\sqrt{9})) + ((\sqrt{9} + 8)! / 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7932 &:= 2 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7) \\ &:= -T(T(2))! + T(T(3)) \times (T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7935 &:= 5 + F(3! + 9) \times F(7) \\ &:= T(5) + (T(T(T(3))) / T(T(\sqrt{9})))! / 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7938 &:= F(8) \times 3! \times 9 \times 7 \\ &:= \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(T(3)) \times 9 \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7947 &:= 7! + F(4)!! + \sqrt{9^7} \\ &:= 7! + T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + \sqrt{9^7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7952 &:= -2 \times 5! + F(\sqrt{9})^{F(7)} \\ &:= T(T(T(2)))! / (T(5) + \sqrt{9})! - T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7974 &:= 4 \times F(7) + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ &:= -(T(T(\sqrt{4})))! + T(T(7)) \times 9 + 7! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7986 &:= F(6) \times 8 + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ &:= 6! + T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(9)) \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7994 &:= 4! \times \sqrt{9} + F(9) \times F(F(7)) \\ &:= T(4!) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) / \sqrt{9} - T(T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8043 &:= F(3!)! / (4 + 0!) - F(8) \\ &:= T(T(T(T(3)))) / T(\sqrt{4}) + (-0! + 8)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8064 &:= 4 \times F(6)! / (-0! + F(8)) \\ &:= (\sqrt{4} + 6)! / (-0! + \sqrt{T(8)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8361 &:= -1 - F(6 \times 3) + F(F(8)) \\ &:= (1 + 6)! + T(\sqrt{3^6}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8367 &:= F(F(7)) \times 6^{F(3)} - F(8) \\ &:= 7! + 6 + T(\sqrt{3^6}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8379 &:= ((\sqrt{9}! + F(7)) \times F(F(3!)) \times F(8) \\ &:= 9 \times (T(7) + T(T(3) + T(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8427 &:= (-7! + 2) / \sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \\ &:= (T(T(7)) - T(2)) \times T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8496 &:= (6! + (\sqrt{9}!) \sqrt{4+F(8)}) \\ &:= (6! / \sqrt{9} - 4) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8546 &:= (-F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4})) \times 5! + F(F(8)) &:= -3 - 5 + T(T(T(2)))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 &:= T(6)^{T(\sqrt{4})} + 5 - (\sqrt{T(8)})! \\
 8594 &:= F(F(F(4)!)) \times (F((\sqrt{9})!) - 5!) + F(F(8)) &:= T(T(2)) \times (8^{T(2)} + T(T(9))) \\
 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(\sqrt{9})! \times T(5) - T(T(8)) \\
 8629 &:= (9!/2 - T(T(6)))/T(\sqrt{T(8)}) &:= \sqrt{4} + T(\sqrt{T(8)})^{T(2)} + T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 &:= -F(F(9)/2) - 6! + F(F(8)) \\
 8684 &:= -F(4)! \times F(8 + 6) + F(F(8)) &:= \sqrt{4} + T(\sqrt{T(8)})^{T(2)} + T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 &:= (\sqrt{4} + T(T(8))) \times (T(6) - 8) \\
 8793 &:= -3!! \times \sqrt{9} + 7 + F(F(8)) &:= T(5) \times (T(T(8)) - 2 - T(9)) \\
 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(7)) + T(8) \\
 8799 &:= -(\sqrt{9})!! \times \sqrt{9} + F(7) + F(F(8)) &:= 8 \times (F(8)^2 + (\sqrt{9})!) \\
 &:= (-T(\sqrt{9})! + T(T(9))) \times T(7) - T(\sqrt{T(8)}) &:= \sqrt{T(8)} \times T(8) \times (-2 + T(9)) \\
 8932 &:= 2 \times (-3!! \times 9 + F(F(8))) &:= F(F(F(4!)))^{\sqrt{9}} - F(2) + F(9) \\
 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(3)))) + &:= -T(\sqrt{4}) + (T(T(9)) - 2) \times 9 \\
 &\quad + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))))/\sqrt{T(8)} \\
 8944 &:= \sqrt{4} \times (F(F(4)!)/9 - 8) &:= F(F(F(4!)) + 3) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 &:= (-T(4) + T(\sqrt{4} + T(9))) \times 8 &:= T(\sqrt{4}) \times (T(2) + 3 \times T(T(9))) \\
 9048 &:= (F(8 + F(4)!)) \times (0! + \sqrt{9})! &:= F(9 - F(3)) \times 3!! - F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 &:= (T(8) + T(\sqrt{4})) \times (0! + T(T(T(\sqrt{9})))) &:= T(9 + 3) + T(T(3))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 9238 &:= F(8)^3 - 2 - F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) &:= 5 \times F(F(F(4!)) \times F(F(3) + 9) \\
 &:= (T(\sqrt{T(8)})^3 - 2 - T(T(\sqrt{9}))) &:= (-5 \times T(T(4)) + T(3)!) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 9243 &:= F(F(3!))^{F(4)} - 2 \times 9 &:= F(7) \times (-4 + 3!! + \sqrt{9}) \\
 &:= 3 \times T((4! + 2) \times \sqrt{9}) &:= T(T(7)) \times (\sqrt{4} + T(T(3))) + 9 \\
 9249 &:= F(F((\sqrt{9})!))^{F(4)} - 2 \times (\sqrt{9})! &:= F(F(8)) - F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(3!) + 9) \\
 &:= T(T(9) + T(4)) \times T(T(2)) + 9 &:= (T(\sqrt{T(8)}) + T(T(T(4)))) - 3) \times T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 9253 &:= F(F(3!))^{5-2} - F((\sqrt{9})!) &:= F(2 + 5) \times 3!! - F((\sqrt{9})!) \\
 & &:= T(-2 + T(5)) + T(T(3))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 & &:= F(\sqrt{4} + 5) \times 3!! - (\sqrt{9})! \\
 & &:= (-\sqrt{4} + T(5)) \times T(3)! - T(\sqrt{9})
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9357 &:= F(7) \times 5! \times 3! - \sqrt{9} \\
 &:= (T(7) - T(5)) \times T(3)! - \sqrt{9} \\
 9366 &:= (F(F(6)) - F(6)) \times 3!! + (\sqrt{9})! \\
 &:= 6 \times \left(T(6) + T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{T(3)!/T(9)} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9369 &:= (F(9) - F(F(6))) \times 3!! + 9 \\
 &:= (T(T(9)) + 6) \times 3 \times \sqrt{9} \\
 9378 &:= F(8) + F(7) \times 3!! - \sqrt{9} \\
 &:= T(T(8)) \times (7 + T(3)) + T(\sqrt{9})! \\
 9381 &:= F(-1 + 8) \times 3!! + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 &:= (-1 + \sqrt{T(8)})! + T(T(3))^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 9387 &:= (-F(7) \times F(8) + 3!!) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 &:= 7 \times (T(T(8)) + T(3)! - T(9)) \\
 9394 &:= (4 + 9) \times 3!! + F(9) \\
 &:= (T(T(4) \times T(\sqrt{9}))) \times T(T(T(3)))/T(9) \\
 9397 &:= F(7) \times (\sqrt{9} + 3!!) - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 &:= T(7) + (T(T(9)) + T(3)) \times 9 \\
 9424 &:= F(4)!! + 2^{F(F(4)!)} \times F(9) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(2) \times T(4! \times \sqrt{9}) \\
 9425 &:= 5^2 \times F(F(4)! + F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 &:= (5 + T(T(2))!) \times (4 + 9) \\
 9429 &:= (F(F((\sqrt{9})!))^2 + F(F(4)!)) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 &:= (9!/T(T(2))! - T(T(4))) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 9438 &:= F(F(8)/3) \times (F(4)! + (\sqrt{9})!!) \\
 &:= (\sqrt{T(8)} + T(3)!) \times (4 + 9) \\
 9447 &:= F(7) \times (F(4)! + F(4)!!) + 9 \\
 &:= T(T(7)) \times 4! - T(4!) + \sqrt{9} \\
 9472 &:= \sqrt{2^{F(7)} \times (F(4)! + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))))} \\
 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(7)) + T(-\sqrt{4} + T(9)) \\
 9476 &:= (-F(6)! + 7!)/4! + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 &:= (6 + T(T(7))) \times (\sqrt{4} + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 9486 &:= (6! - F(8)^{\sqrt{4}}) \times F(9) \\
 &:= 6 \times ((\sqrt{T(8)})! + T(-4 + T(9))) \\
 9494 &:= F(F(F(4)!))^{\sqrt{9}} + F(4 + 9) \\
 &:= (\sqrt{4} + T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{T(\sqrt{4})}) + T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 9495 &:= (5! + T(9 + 4)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= 5 \times ((F((\sqrt{9})!)/F(F(F(4)!))) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \\
 9498 &:= F(F(8)) - (\sqrt{9})!! - F(4)!! - F((\sqrt{9})!) \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{T(\sqrt{4})} + T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 9534 &:= 4^3! \times 5 - F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 &:= T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))) \times T(T(3) \times 5) - T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 9548 &:= F(F(8)) - F(F((\sqrt{4} + 5))) \times (\sqrt{9})! \\
 &:= T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times (4 + 5!)/\sqrt{9} \\
 9587 &:= -F(7) + 8! \times 5/F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(T(8)) \times T(5) + \sqrt{9} \\
 9594 &:= F(4)!!/9 \times 5! - (\sqrt{9})! \\
 &:= T(4 \times \sqrt{9}) \times (5! + \sqrt{9}) \\
 9599 &:= (\sqrt{9})!!/9 \times 5! - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 &:= (-9 + (T(\sqrt{9}))! \times 5!)/9 \\
 9644 &:= -F(4)!^4 + F(F(F(6))) - (\sqrt{9})! \\
 &:= 4 \times (-4 + T(69)) \\
 9645 &:= 5! \times 4! + F(F(F(6)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -T(5) + 4 \times T(69) & & := (4 \times 5! - T(\sqrt{9})) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{9647} & := (7! \times F(4)! - F(F(F(6)))) / F(\sqrt{9}) & & \mathbf{9974} := F(4)!! - 7 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))^{9} \\
 & := -T(7) - T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + T(T(6)) \times T(9) & & := T(T(\sqrt{4}))! + (-7 + T(T(\sqrt{9}))^{9}) \\
 \mathbf{9674} & := F(F(F(F(4)!))) - (F(F(7)) - F(F(6))) \times (\sqrt{9})! & & \mathbf{9981} := F(1 \times 8)^{\sqrt{9}} + (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 & := \sqrt{4} \times 7! - T(T(T(6)/\sqrt{9})) & & := T(T(1 \times 8)) + 9 \times T(T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{9699} & := (-F((\sqrt{9})!) + 9 \times F(F(F(6)))) / (\sqrt{9})! & & \mathbf{9983} := 3!! + F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} + F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 & := (T(9) - \sqrt{9}) \times T(T(6)) - \sqrt{9} & & := (-T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) \times T(9)) / \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{9723} & := F(F(3!)) \times (2 \times F(F(7)) - \sqrt{9}) & & \mathbf{9984} := F(4)!! + F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{9} \\
 & := T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(2)) \times 7 + T(T(\sqrt{9})) & & := \sqrt{4^8} \times (T(9) - T(\sqrt{9})) \\
 \mathbf{9744} & := (F(4!) \times \sqrt{4} - 7!) / 9 & & \mathbf{9985} := -5! \times 8 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 & := 4! \times T(4! + \sqrt{7+9}) & & := T(5) \times T(T(8)) - T(9) / 9 \\
 \mathbf{9753} & := -F(3!) \times 5! - F(F(7)) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) & & \mathbf{9989} := F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} + (\sqrt{9})!! \\
 & := (\sqrt{T(T(3)) - 5})! \times T(T(7)) + 9 & & := (T(9) \times T(T(8)) - \sqrt{9}) / \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{9774} & := F(4)! \times (7 \times F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{9})) & & \mathbf{9993} := F(F(F(3!))) + F(9) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!) + F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 & := -T(4!) + 7! + 7! - T(\sqrt{9}) & & := (T(T(T(3))) - 9) \times T(9) + \sqrt{9} \\
 \mathbf{9786} & := (6 + 8) \times F(F(7)) \times \sqrt{9} & & \mathbf{9994} := T(4)^{\sqrt{(T(\sqrt{9})!) / T(9)}} - T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 & := (-T(6) + (\sqrt{T(8)})!) \times (-7 + T(T(\sqrt{9}))) & & := F(F(F(F(4)!))) - (F(9) - (\sqrt{9})!) \times F(9) \\
 \mathbf{9849} & := -F((\sqrt{9})! + F(F(4)!)) + F(F(8)) - (\sqrt{9})!! & & \mathbf{9995} := -5! \times F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) + 9 \\
 & := (-T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(8) \times T(T(\sqrt{9})) & & := (5 + ((T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9))) \\
 \mathbf{9864} & := 4! \times (F(6 + 8) + F(9)) & & \mathbf{9996} := F(F(6)) \times ((\sqrt{9})! + F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(9) \\
 & := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(8))) \times T(\sqrt{9}) & & := (T(T(6)) - 9) \times T(9) + T(\sqrt{9}) \\
 \mathbf{9947} & := 7^{F(4)} \times (F((\sqrt{9})!) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) & & \mathbf{9998} := (F(F(8)) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times F(9) - 9! \\
 & := -T(T(7)) + T(4) \times T(T(9)) + \sqrt{9} & & := 8 + (T(T(T(\sqrt{9}))) - 9) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{9954} & := (4 \times 5! - (\sqrt{9})!) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!))
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Patterned Numbers

There are numbers those can be extended just multiplying by 10 without loss of properties, and so on. This types of numbers, we call **patterned numbers**. This kind of numbers first introduced by Madachy [4], 1966, pp. 174-175. Also refer Taneja [21] for recent work. This section deals with **selfie patterned numbers** having **Fibonacci sequence** and **triangular numbers** simultaneously.

$$48 := F(4)! \times 8 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 8$$

$$480 := F(4)! \times 80 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 80$$

$$4800 := F(4)! \times 800 = T(T(\sqrt{4})) \times 800$$

$$63 := F(F(6)) \times 3 = T(6) \times 3$$

$$630 := F(F(6)) \times 30 = T(6) \times 30$$

$$6300 := F(F(6)) \times 300 = T(6) \times 300$$

$$84 := F(8) \times 4 = T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times 4$$

$$840 := F(8) \times 40 = T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times 40$$

$$8400 := F(8) \times 400 = T(\sqrt{T(8)}) \times 400$$

$$147 := 1 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 7 = T(T(-1 + 4)) \times 7$$

$$1470 := 1 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 70 = T(T(-1 + 4)) \times 70$$

$$14700 := 1 \times F(F(F(4)!)) \times 700 = T(T(-1 + 4)) \times 700$$

$$315 := F(F(3!)) \times 15 = T(T(3)) \times 15$$

$$3150 := F(F(3!)) \times 150 = T(T(3)) \times 150$$

$$31500 := F(F(3!)) \times 1500 = T(T(3)) \times 1500$$

$$486 := \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 6 = \left(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^8} \right) \times 6$$

$$4860 := \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 60 = \left(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^8} \right) \times 60$$

$$48600 := \sqrt{F(4)^8} \times 600 = \left(\sqrt{T(\sqrt{4})^8} \right) \times 600$$

$$564 := (5! + F(F(6))) \times 4 = (5! + T(6)) \times 4$$

$$5640 := (5! + F(F(6))) \times 40 = (5! + T(6)) \times 40$$

$$56400 := (5! + F(F(6))) \times 400 = (5! + T(6)) \times 400$$

$$1165 := F(F(1 \times 1 + 6)) \times 5 = (1 + 1 + T(T(6))) \times 5$$

$$11650 := F(F(1 \times 1 + 6)) \times 50 = (1 + 1 + T(T(6))) \times 50$$

$$116500 := F(F(1 \times 1 + 6)) \times 500 = (1 + 1 + T(T(6))) \times 500$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1365 &:= 13 \times F(F(6)) \times 5 = 13 \times T(6) \times 5 \\ 13650 &:= 13 \times F(F(6)) \times 50 = 13 \times T(6) \times 50 \\ 136500 &:= 13 \times F(F(6)) \times 500 = 13 \times T(6) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1575 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times 75 = T(1+5) \times 75 \\ 15750 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times 750 = T(1+5) \times 750 \\ 157500 &:= F(F(1+5)) \times 7500 = T(1+5) \times 7500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1645 &:= F(16)/F(4) \times 5 = (-1 + 6 \times T(T(4))) \times 5 \\ 16450 &:= F(16)/F(4) \times 50 = (-1 + 6 \times T(T(4))) \times 50 \\ 164500 &:= F(16)/F(4) \times 500 = (-1 + 6 \times T(T(4))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1885 &:= F(1+F(8)-8) \times 5 = (-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 5 \\ 18850 &:= F(1+F(8)-8) \times 50 = (-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 50 \\ 188500 &:= F(1+F(8)-8) \times 500 = (-1 + T(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(\sqrt{T(8)}))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2079 &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9 = T(T(2) \times 07) \times 9 \\ 20790 &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 90 = T(T(2) \times 07) \times 90 \\ 207900 &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 900 = T(T(2) \times 07) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2435 &:= (-F(F(F(2) + F(4)!)) + 3!!) \times 5 = ((T(T(2)))! - \sqrt{4} - T(T(T(3)))) \times 5 \\ 24350 &:= (-F(F(F(2) + F(4)!)) + 3!!) \times 50 = ((T(T(2)))! - \sqrt{4} - T(T(T(3)))) \times 50 \\ 243500 &:= (-F(F(F(2) + F(4)!)) + 3!!) \times 500 = ((T(T(2)))! - \sqrt{4} - T(T(T(3)))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2645 &:= (2 + F(F(6)))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 = (2 + T(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 5 \\ 26450 &:= (2 + F(F(6)))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 50 = (2 + T(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 50 \\ 264500 &:= (2 + F(F(6)))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 500 = (2 + T(6))^{\sqrt{4}} \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2688 &:= 2 \times F(6) \times F(8) \times 8 = 2 \times T(6) \times 8 \times 8 \\ 26880 &:= 2 \times F(6) \times F(8) \times 80 = 2 \times T(6) \times 8 \times 80 \\ 268800 &:= 2 \times F(6) \times F(8) \times 800 = 2 \times T(6) \times 8 \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3087 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(08) \times 7 = T(T(3)) \times T(\sqrt{T(08)}) \times 7 \\ 30870 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(08) \times 70 = T(T(3)) \times T(\sqrt{T(08)}) \times 70 \\ 308700 &:= F(F(3!)) \times F(08) \times 700 = T(T(3)) \times T(\sqrt{T(08)}) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$3325 := (3!! - F(F(3!) + 2)) \times 5 = (T(3)! - T(T(T(3) - 2))) \times 5$$

$$33250 := (3!! - F(F(3!) + 2)) \times 50 = (T(3)! - T(T(T(3) - 2))) \times 50$$

$$332500 := (3!! - F(F(3!) + 2)) \times 500 = (T(3)! - T(T(T(3) - 2))) \times 500$$

$$3375 := 3 \times (-F(3!) + F(F(7))) \times 5 = T(3 \times 3) \times 75$$

$$33750 := 3 \times (-F(3!) + F(F(7))) \times 50 = T(3 \times 3) \times 750$$

$$337500 := 3 \times (-F(3!) + F(F(7))) \times 500 = T(3 \times 3) \times 7500$$

$$3485 := (3!! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 5 = (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 5$$

$$34850 := (3!! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 50 = (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 50$$

$$348500 := (3!! - \sqrt{4} - F(8)) \times 500 = (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 500$$

$$3525 := (F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 25 = (T(T(3)) + 5!) \times 25$$

$$35250 := (F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 250 = (T(T(3)) + 5!) \times 250$$

$$352500 := (F(F(3!)) + 5!) \times 2500 = (T(T(3)) + 5!) \times 2500$$

$$3528 := F(3 + 5)^2 \times 8 = (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 8$$

$$35280 := F(3 + 5)^2 \times 80 = (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 80$$

$$352800 := F(3 + 5)^2 \times 800 = (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 800$$

$$3545 := (3!! - 5 - F(4!)) \times 5 = (T(3)! - T(5) + 4) \times 5$$

$$35450 := (3!! + 5 - F(4!)) \times 50 = (T(3)! - T(5) + 4) \times 50$$

$$354500 := (3!! + 5 - F(4!)) \times 500 = (T(3)! - T(5) + 4) \times 500$$

$$3605 := (F(3) + 6! - 0!) \times 5 = (T(3)! + (6 \times 0!)) \times 5$$

$$36050 := (F(3) + 6! - 0!) \times 50 = (T(3)! + (6 \times 0!)) \times 50$$

$$360500 := (F(3) + 6! - 0!) \times 500 = (T(3)! + (6 \times 0!)) \times 500$$

$$3635 := (3^6 - F(3)) \times 5 = (T(3)! + T(6)/3) \times 5$$

$$36350 := (3^6 - F(3)) \times 50 = (T(3)! + T(6)/3) \times 50$$

$$363500 := (3^6 - F(3)) \times 500 = (T(3)! + T(6)/3) \times 500$$

$$3705 := (3!! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 5 = T(37 + 0!) \times 5$$

$$37050 := (3!! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 50 = T(37 + 0!) \times 50$$

$$370500 := (3!! + F(7 + 0!)) \times 500 = T(37 + 0!) \times 500$$

$$3944 := (-F(F(3)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 4 = (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$39440 := (-F(F(3)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 40 = (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 40$$

$$394400 := (-F(F(3)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})^4)) \times 400 = (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 400$$

$$4293 := (F(4)!! \times 2 - 9) \times 3 = T(4! + 29) \times 3$$

$$42930 := (F(4)!! \times 2 - 9) \times 30 = T(4! + 29) \times 30$$

$$429300 := (F(4)!! \times 2 - 9) \times 300 = T(4! + 29) \times 300$$

$$5187 := ((5 + 1)! + F(8)) \times 7 = T(\sqrt{5 - 1} + T(8)) \times 7$$

$$51870 := ((5 + 1)! + F(8)) \times 70 = T(\sqrt{5 - 1} + T(8)) \times 70$$

$$518700 := ((5 + 1)! + F(8)) \times 700 = T(\sqrt{5 - 1} + T(8)) \times 700$$

$$5825 := F(5 + 8) \times 25 = 5 \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 2) \times 5$$

$$58250 := F(5 + 8) \times 250 = 5 \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 2) \times 50$$

$$582500 := F(5 + 8) \times 2500 = 5 \times (T(T(\sqrt{T(8)})) + 2) \times 500$$

$$6615 := F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)) \times 15 = T(6) \times T(6) \times 15$$

$$66150 := F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)) \times 150 = T(6) \times T(6) \times 150$$

$$661500 := F(F(6)) \times F(F(6)) \times 1500 = T(6) \times T(6) \times 1500$$

$$7875 := (F(F(7)) - 8) \times 7 \times 5 = T(-7 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 75$$

$$78750 := (F(F(7)) - 8) \times 7 \times 50 = T(-7 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 750$$

$$787500 := (F(F(7)) - 8) \times 7 \times 500 = T(-7 + T(\sqrt{T(8)})) \times 7500$$

$$9425 := F((\sqrt{9})! + F(F(4)!)) \times 25 = (-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times 5$$

$$94250 := F((\sqrt{9})! + F(F(4)!)) \times 250 = (-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times 50$$

$$942500 := F((\sqrt{9})! + F(F(4)!)) \times 2500 = (-T(\sqrt{9}) + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))) \times 500$$

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References

- [1] J. BARTON, Centered Polygonal Numbers, <http://www.virtuescience.com/centered-polygonal.html>.
- [2] H.E. DUDENEY, Amusements in Mathematics, EBD E-Books Directory.com, 1917.
- [3] R. KNOTT, Polygonal Numbers, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Figurate/figurate.html>.
- [4] J.S. MADACHY, Mathematics on Vacations, Charlars Scriber's Son, New York, 1966.

- [5] N.J.A. SLONE, Triangular numbers: $a(n) = \text{binomial}(n + 1, 2) = n(n + 1)/2 = 0 + 1 + 2 + \dots + n$, The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, <https://oeis.org/A000217>.
- [6] WOLFRAM MATH WORLD, Polygonal Numbers, <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/PolygonalNumber.html>
- [7] WOLFRAM MATH WORLD, Centered Polygonal Numbers, <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/CenteredPolygonalNumber.html>
- [8] TANEJA, I.J., Selfie Numbers: Consecutive Representations in Increasing and Decreasing Orders, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 17(2014), Article 140, pp. 1-57. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v17/v17a140.pdf>.
- [9] I.J. TANEJA, Different Types of Pretty Wild Narcissistic Numbers: Selfie Representations - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 18(2015), Article 32, pp.1-43. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a32.pdf>.
- [10] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers: Representations in Increasing and Decreasing Orders of Non Consecutive Digits, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 18(2015), Article 70, pp.1-104. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a70.pdf>.
- [11] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers - I: Symmetrical and Unified Representations, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 18(2015), Article 174, pp.1-94. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a174.pdf>.
- [12] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers - II: Six Digits Symmetrical, Unified and Patterned Representations Without Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 18(2015), Article 175, pp.1-41. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a175.pdf>.
- [13] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers - III: With Factorial and Without Square-Root - Up To Five Digits, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 19(2016), Article 16, pp.1-52, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a16.pdf>.
- [14] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers - IV: Addition, Subtraction and Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 19(2016), Article 163, pp.1-42, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a163.pdf>.
- [15] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers - V: Six Digits Symmetrical Representations with Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 19(2016), Article 164, pp.1-60, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a164.pdf>.
- [16] I.J. TANEJA, S-gonal and Centered Polygonal Selfie Numbers, and Connections with Binomials Coefficients, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 20(2017), pp. 1-42, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a43.pdf>.
- [17] I.J. TANEJA, Simultaneous Representations of Selfie Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci and Triangular Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 20(2017), Art. 55, pp. 1-87, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a55.pdf>.
- [18] I.J. TANEJA, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers, Selfie Numbers, Fibonacci Sequence, and Selfie Fractions, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 19(2016), Article 179, pp.1-37, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a179.pdf>.
- [19] I.J. TANEJA, Hardy-Ramanujan Number - 1729, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 20(2017), pp.1-50, Art 6, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a06.pdf>

- [20] I.J. TANEJA, 2019 In Numbers, **Zenodo**, December 31, 2019, pp. 1-27, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2529103>.
- [21] I.J. TANEJA, Patterns in Selfie and Semi-Selfie Numbers. **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 6, 2019, pp. 1-51, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2563202>.
- [22] I.J. TANEJA, Permutable Powers Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 15, 2019, pp. 1-227, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2566445>.
- [23] I.J. TANEJA, Triangular-Type Selfie Numebrs, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 17, 2019, pp. 1-91, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567571>.
- [24] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 18, 2019, pp. 1-116, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571472>.
- [25] I.J. TANEJA, Fibonacci Sequence and Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 19, 2019, pp. 1-233, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572044>.
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